

**Value Relevance and Corporate Environmental, Social, and Governance
(ESG) Sustainability Performance. Evidence from FTSE100, FTSE250 and
Small-cap Companies.**

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this work has not been previously accepted in substance for any degree and is not being concurrently submitted for any other degree.

I also declare that this thesis is a result of my own independent work and research, except where otherwise stated (a bibliography is attached).

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the value relevance of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) sustainability performance for FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies. There has been an increasing demand from stakeholder groups for incremental ESG sustainability practices within business activities. In response to stakeholder demand, firms adopted costly sustainability approach integrated within the operation. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the financial implications of sustainability performance on market value of share.

This study employed Ohlson's (1995) model to test the association between the market value of the share and sustainability performance. Using a sample of 1210 companies between 2017 and 2020, this study estimates the role of environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance on firm value. The results indicate that sustainability performance provides additional decision useful information to the investors. Overall, this study found positive association for the ESG, social and governance performance and negative association for the environmental performance. The negative impact of lower sustainability performance is higher for the bigger firm compared to the smaller firm. Investors penalise large firms more severely for operating in environmentally sensitive industries than smaller firms. Surprisingly, younger firms have better sustainability performance and higher market value.

This study investigated the role of corporate sustainability performance from several theoretical reference points. The most notable achievement has been identifying the varying levels of value relevance for environmental, social, and governance performance separately and combinedly and found different levels of association for FTSE4Good and FTSE100, FTSE250 and Small-cap companies. The findings have practical implications for corporate managers, investors, shareholders, lenders, banks, regulators, and standard setters. The incremental value relevance of sustainability performance encourages firms to adopt more sustainability practices, while investors invest in sustainability projects in the long term.

Table of Contents

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.2. BACKGROUND.....	2
1.3. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND GAPS IN THE EXISTING LITERATURE.....	4
1.4. RATIONALE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THIS RESEARCH	8
1.5. RESEARCH QUESTIONS	10
1.6. RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVES	11
1.7. CONTRIBUTIONS OF THIS RESEARCH	11
1.8. STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS.....	13
 CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW.....	 14
2.1. INTRODUCTION.....	14
2.2. CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABILITY	14
2.2.1. <i>Sustainable development</i>	15
2.2.1.1. Economic sustainability.....	16
2.2.1.2. Environmental sustainability.....	17
2.2.1.3. Social sustainability	17
2.3. ORGANISATIONAL PERSPECTIVES OF SUSTAINABILITY.....	18
2.3.1. <i>Sustainability accounting</i>	21
2.3.2. <i>Reporting sustainability performance</i>	24
2.3.4. <i>Corporate sustainability performance reporting regulations</i>	27
2.3.5. <i>The role of corporate sustainability reporting</i>	28
2.4. CONCEPT OF VALUE RELEVANCE	29
2.4.1. <i>Measurements of firm value</i>	31
2.4.2. <i>Model to assess the value-relevance studies</i>	32
2.4.3. <i>Sources of value-enhancing capabilities</i>	35
2.4.4. <i>Firms' CSR performance and value maximisation</i>	35
2.4.5. <i>Capital market benefits of CSR sustainability</i>	38
2.5. THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES ON SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING PRACTICE	40
2.5.1. <i>Functionalist perspectives</i>	41
2.5.1.1. Decision usefulness studies.....	41
2.5.1.2. Economic theory perspective.....	43
2.5.2. <i>Interpretative perspective</i>	44
2.5.2.1. Stakeholder theory.....	45
2.5.2.2. Legitimacy theory.....	46

2.5.3. <i>Radical perspectives</i>	48
2.5.3.1. Political economy theory	49
2.5.3.2. Theory of accountability	50
2.5.3.3. Media agenda-setting and sustainability reporting	52
2.6. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT	53
2.6.1. <i>Development of the conceptual framework</i>	53
2.6.2. <i>Development of hypotheses</i>	57
H1: Value relevance of sustainability performance	57
H2: Environmental performance	58
H3: Social performance.....	59
H4: Governance performance.....	59
H5: Firm size.....	60
H6: Sustainability reputation	60
H7: Industrial background.....	61
H8: Age of Stock Market Listing of firms.....	62
2.7. SUMMARY	63
CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	64
3.1. INTRODUCTION.....	64
3.2. PHILOSOPHICAL BACKGROUND.....	64
3.3. THE PHILOSOPHICAL ASSUMPTION UNDERPINNING THIS STUDY	65
3.3.1. <i>Ontological assumption</i>	65
3.3.2. <i>Epistemological assumption</i>	66
3.3.3. <i>Axiological assumption</i>	67
3.4. RESEARCH DESIGN	68
3.4.1. <i>Research approach</i>	68
3.4.2 <i>Research methods</i>	69
3.5. RESEARCH DATA, SAMPLE SIZE AND SELECTION	70
3.5.1. <i>Financial and other non-financial data</i>	73
3.5.2. <i>Corporate sustainability data</i>	73
3.6. DATA ANALYSIS.....	79
3.6.1. <i>Regression model</i>	79
3.6.2. <i>Data scaling</i>	86
3.6.3. <i>Assumptions of regression analysis</i>	88
3.6.3.1. Normality of data	89
3.6.3.2. Assumption of a linear relationship	90
3.6.3.3. Constant error variance/homoscedasticity/no heteroscedasticity	93
3.6.3.4. Independent error terms/no autocorrelation.....	94

3.6.3.5. No multicollinearity.....	95
3.7. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION	96
3.8. SUMMARY	96
CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.....	98
4.1. INTRODUCTION.....	98
4.2. DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF VARIABLES	98
4.4. REGRESSION RESULTS.....	104
4.4.1. <i>Regression Model 1</i>	106
4.4.2. <i>Regression Model 2</i>	107
4.4.3. <i>Regression Model 3</i>	110
4.4.4. <i>Regression Model 4</i>	114
4.4.7. <i>Regression Model 5</i>	116
4.5. HYPOTHESIS RESULTS	122
<i>Hypothesis Result – H1</i>	124
<i>Hypothesis Result – H2</i>	126
<i>Hypothesis Result – H3</i>	128
<i>Hypothesis Result – H4</i>	130
<i>Hypothesis Result – H5</i>	133
<i>Hypothesis Result – H6</i>	133
<i>Hypothesis Result – H7</i>	134
<i>Hypothesis Result – H8</i>	136
4.6. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS	136
4.7. ROBUSTNESS CHECK	138
4.8. SUMMARY	140
CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS.....	141
5.1. INTRODUCTION.....	141
5.2. ESG PERFORMANCE	142
5.2.1. <i>Summary of the findings</i>	142
5.2.2. <i>Discussions and evaluation of the findings</i>	142
5.2.3. <i>Practical implications of the findings to the stakeholders</i>	145
5.3. ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE	149
5.3.1. <i>Summary of the findings</i>	149
5.3.2. <i>Discussions and evaluation of the findings</i>	149
5.3.3. <i>Practical implications of the findings to the stakeholders</i>	151
5.4. SOCIAL PERFORMANCE	153

5.4.1. <i>Summary of the findings</i>	153
5.4.2. <i>Discussion and evaluation of the findings</i>	153
5.4.3. <i>Practical implications of the findings</i>	155
5.5. GOVERNANCE PERFORMANCE	156
5.5.1. <i>Summary of the findings</i>	156
5.5.2. <i>Discussions and evaluation of the findings</i>	156
5.5.3. <i>Practical implications of the findings</i>	158
5.6. CORPORATE SIZE EFFECTS ON SUSTAINABILITY AND SHARE PRICE	159
5.6.1. <i>Summary of the findings</i>	159
5.6.2. <i>Discussions and evaluation of the findings</i>	159
5.6.3. <i>Practical implications of the findings to the stakeholders</i>	161
5.7. SUSTAINABILITY REPUTATION	162
5.7.1. <i>Summary of the findings</i>	162
5.7.2. <i>Discussions and evaluation of the findings</i>	162
5.7.3. <i>Practical implication of the findings</i>	164
5.8. INDUSTRY BACKGROUND AND ITS EFFECT ON SUSTAINABILITY AND SHARE PRICE	165
5.8.1. <i>Summary of the findings</i>	165
5.8.2. <i>Discussions and evaluation of the findings</i>	166
5.8.3. <i>Practical implications of the findings</i>	168
5.9. AGE OF FIRM'S STOCK MARKET LISTING	169
5.9.1 <i>Summary of the findings</i>	169
5.9.2. <i>Discussions and evaluation of the findings</i>	169
5.9.3. <i>Practical implications of the findings to the stakeholders</i>	170
5.10. INVESTORS' PREFERENCE FOR INDIVIDUAL PERFORMANCE OVER THE COMBINED PERFORMANCE	170
5.10.1. <i>Summary of the findings</i>	170
5.10.2. <i>Discussion and evaluation of the findings</i>	171
5.10.3. <i>Practical implications</i>	172
5.11. SUSTAINABILITY FIRM VALUE ECOSYSTEMS	173
5.12. SUMMARY	177
CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION	180
6.1. INTRODUCTION	180
6.2. ACHIEVING THE RESEARCH OBJECTIVES	180
6.2.1. <i>Objective One</i>	180
6.2.2. <i>Objective Two</i>	181
6.2.3. <i>Objective Three</i>	182
6.2.4. <i>Objective Four</i>	183

6.2.5. <i>Objective Five</i>	184
6.3. CONTRIBUTIONS OF THIS STUDY	184
6.3.1. <i>Theoretical contributions</i>	184
6.3.2. <i>Contribution to the professional practice</i>	186
6.4. RECOMMENDATIONS	190
6.5. LIMITATION OF THIS RESEARCH.....	193
6.6. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDIES	193
6.7. SUMMARY	195
REFERENCES.....	196

List of Table

Table 1: Skewness and kurtosis test of MV.....	87
Table 2: Skewness and kurtosis test results of all variables.	88
Table 3: Results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests.	89
Table 4: Skewness and kurtosis of all variables.	90
Table 5: ANOVA Table.....	94
Table 6: Results of the Durbin-Watson test.....	94
Table 7: Results of collinearity statistics.	95
Table 8: Descriptive statistics results of the full sample.....	99
Table 9: Descriptive statistics results of the FTSE100 sample group.	99
Table 10: Descriptive statistics results of the FTSE250 sample group.	99
Table 11: Descriptive statistics results of the Small-cap sample group.....	100
Table 12: Descriptive statistics results of the FTSE4Good sample group.....	100
Table 13: Descriptive statistics results of the NonFTSE4Good companies.	100
Table 14: Descriptive statistics of all variables for the full sample.	104
Table 15: Regression results of Models 1 to 5 for the full sample.	105
Table 16: Regression Results 1 to 3 for FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies. ...	106
Table 17: Regression Results 1 to 3 for FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good companies.....	106
Table 18: Regression results dependent variables lnMcap vs lnMV.....	137
Table 19: Comparison of Regression coefficient OLS vs R essentials.	138

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Interconnection of benefits and costs among the economy, environment, and society.	19
Figure 2: Overview of concept and terminology in sustainability reporting (adopted from Hahn and Kuhnen, 2013, p. 44).	21
Figure 3: CSR benefits for the business (from Malik, 2014).	37
Figure 4: Theoretical perspective of corporate sustainability (adopted from Gray et al., 2009, p. 12).	41
Figure 5: Conceptual framework.	57
Figure 6: Breakdown of sample based on FTSE constituent.	72
Figure 7: Breakdown of sample based on FTSE4Good membership.	72
Figure 8: ESG Scoring mechanism – broad categories.	75
Figure 9: ESG scoring mechanism – scoring metrics distribution.	76
Figure 10: FTSE4Good ESG rating score measurement.	78
Figure 11: FTSE4Good inclusion and exclusion point table.	78
Figure 12: Histogram of lnMV (dependent variable).	91
Figure 13: P-P plot of regression standardized residual of lnMV (dependent variable).	92
Figure 14: Scatterplot of regression standardized residual of lnMV (dependent variable).	92
Figure 15: Firm’s Sustainability Journey.	174

List of Acronyms

3P	Profit, People and Planet
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
BV	Book Value
CSP	Corporate Sustainability Performance
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DJSI	Dow Jones Sustainability Index
EMH	Efficient Market Hypothesis
Env	Environmental Sustainability
EPS	Earnings Per Share
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance Sustainability
ESI	Ethical Sustainability Index
FTSE	Financial Times Stock Exchange
GAAP	Generally Accepted Accounting Principle
Gov	Governance Sustainability
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative
IFRS	International Financial Reporting Standard
IPA	International Perspectives on Accounting
IPO	Initial Public Offerings
IPPC	Integrated Pollution Prevention Inventory
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
LSE	London Stock Exchange
MNC	Multinational Corporation
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium

SAM	Sustainable Asset Management
SRI	Socially Responsible Index
SRT	Sustainability Reporting Tools
Soc	Social Sustainability
TBL	Triple Bottom Line
TOL	Tolerance Limit
TRI	Toxic Release Inventory
UN	United Nation
UK	United Kingdom
US	United States
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
VIF	Variance Influence Factor
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1. Introduction

This study analyses the value relevance of corporate sustainability performance, particularly environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance, and whether investors and existing shareholders consider such information when making investment decisions. The idea of socially responsible investment has emerged as a worldwide social movement since 1990 (Borghesi et al., 2014). Following socially and environmentally responsible investment principles, the total investment fund expanded from USD \$13.3tn in 2012 to 21.4tn in 2014 (Global Sustainable Investment Alliance, 2014). As a result of the development of corporate sustainability practices, relevant standards and regulations, such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), have also been developed. As a result, corporate sustainability information becomes more available to investors, along with traditional accounting and financial variables for investment decision making.

The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD, 2002) asserted that companies and society benefit from a clear long-term sustainability strategy based on business integrity and values. Artiach et al. (2010) defined corporate sustainability as how and to what extent a firm accommodates economic, social, environmental, and governance issues within the strategy and operation of the business and, eventually, its impacts on society. The firm shows increased accountability to diverse stakeholder groups rather than only shareholders (Cho et al., 2013). Corporations disclose more sustainability information due to increasing environmental and social concerns, media attention, and public awareness (Kolk, 2003). There has been growing demand from wider stakeholders, particularly customers, employees, communities, governments, and shareholders, to adopt social and environmental policies (El Ghoul et al., 2011; Clarkson et al., 2013). Therefore, reporting environmental and social factors has become an increasingly regular practice for many companies (Clarkson et al., 2013). KPMG (2011) reported that 95% of Fortune Global 250 companies published their social and environmental information either by integrated reporting or standalone sustainability reports in 2010.

Investors' awareness of corporate operational activities has grown gradually over the years (Zhou et al., 2013). Investors consider corporate sustainability performance incrementally as a key performance indicator for evaluating overall business success (Kaspereit & Lopatta, 2016). Although financial consideration plays a pivotal part in decision making in socially responsible investment, there is a broader emphasis on investment decisions based on ethical, social, and environmental standards (Consolandi et al., 2009). This study aims to investigate the impact of corporate sustainability performance on a firm's value through understanding the current practices of corporate sustainability performance and practice.

1.2. Background

Corporate debates typically start from the unwise use of resources, because this negatively affects society and the environment (Dilling, 2010). Responsible behaviours and sustainable practices can reduce negative effects on society and the environment while increasing social and environmental security (Hubbard, 2009). The increasing levels of pressure from stakeholders, such as customers, investors, and governments, force corporations to take responsibility for their activities and impacts (Henri & Journeault, 2008). Potential investors and existing shareholders seek evidence to ensure that they have invested in an environmentally friendly business with acceptable social and environmental risk management strategies (Heinkel et al., 2011). Customers prefer to know the product's origin before they buy. Additionally, environmentally and socially responsible firms get extra attention from the potential employees than their competitors (Belal & Momin, 2009).

To fulfil the growing demand for social and environmental information from the stakeholder group, particularly the investors, firms need more commitment to providing the required information by disclosing sustainability reports (Adams & Frost, 2009). However, to meet the increasing need for sustainability and CSR information, several reporting guidelines, frameworks, and standards, such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Guideline, Sustainable Development Guideline (AA1000), and the Social and Ethical Accountability Guideline, have been developed. However, so far, sustainability performance reporting has remained a voluntary activity of the company and is involved with the minimum level of regulatory bindings in this process (KPMG, 2013).

Since the 1990s, stakeholders have been increasingly using sustainability reporting because of growing awareness of social and environmental issues (Jones et al., 2016). Initially, sustainability performance reporting was not structured and organised as it is today, as there were no universally agreed-upon standards and frameworks (Watts, 2015). Some organisations have developed sustainability reporting guidelines, frameworks, and standards thus far. Among these frameworks, the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) framework has been one of the most used and acceptable since its inception in 1999 (Michealon et al., 2015). Significant development has been noticed in the form, content, structure, and reporting variable in the GRI reporting guideline.

Initially, sustainability reporting involved publishing only the positive side of corporate activities while ignoring the negative side, as it is voluntary disclosure with no mandatory standards (Chen et al., 2015). Therefore, the question of the credibility of the report has been raised (Kolk & Perego, 2010). Lock and Seele (2016) claimed that the GRI and other sustainability reporting frameworks had increased the report's quality and credibility by standardising corporate sustainability reporting regulations. Adams and Frost (2009) claimed that corporate sustainability is essential in fostering accountability and transparency of corporate strategy and activities. However, to extend the report's credibility, some firms include assurance statements issued by independent verifiers, such as audit firms (Jones & Solomon, 2010).

Sustainability indices are of great use to international investors who intend to make sustainable investment decisions anywhere in the world. In the last 25 years, the world has experienced significant development of several sustainability indices and ratings worldwide to facilitate comparisons among corporations and industries. Indices such as Dow Jones, FTSE4Good Index, Sustainable Asset Management (SAM), and MSCI ESG ratings play a considerable role in categorising a company based on its sustainability practices and performance (Morse, 2015). FTSE4Good and the Dow Jones Sustainability Index apply the same standard for all the companies under consideration and report to what extent they possess sustainable practices.

Indices allow for making cross-border, cross-continent, and cross-industry comparisons and help find which corporation holds the most socially and environmentally acceptable activities, behaviour, and future strategy. Although each index has unique evaluation criteria for corporate actions, the ultimate goal is almost the same: to facilitate stakeholders in making informed decisions.

1.3. Problem statement and gaps in the existing literature

The demand for environmental protection brought millions of people to the streets on the first Earth Day in April 1970. Since then the situation, instead of getting better, is far worse. Fossil fuels are still 80% of total energy sources, a scenario that has not altered since 1970. The CO₂ in the atmosphere has been at its highest level at any time in the last 800,000 years (Climate Central, 2013). The temperature of the oceans is rising, corals are dying, the planet is heating up, and frequent natural disasters are causing irrecoverable damage, while we are receiving more and more warnings of catastrophe from scientists (Rathi, 2018). Both governments and businesses are working together to reduce carbon emissions and tackle climate change. Investors are concerned about ensuring that they are not indirectly encouraging social and environmental wrongdoing. Corporate sustainability is a tool used to measure organisational sustainability practices aimed towards sustainable development and reporting to internal and external stakeholders (Global Reporting Initiative, 2006). Firms are responsible for their activities and their impacts on society and the environment (Hahn & Kuhnen, 2013). Stakeholders believe firms have more responsibilities to society and the environment beyond profit maximisation (Nikolaeva & Bicho, 2011).

Corporate sustainability as a research topic has been investigated on many occasions in recent years. Each investigation focused on different aspects of corporate sustainability. Some research studies have focused on corporate social responsibility and corporate financial performance (e.g., Ameer & Othman, 2012; Barnett & Salomon, 2011; Garcia-Castro et al., 2010). Studies such as Al-Kassar and Al-Nidawiy (2014) have investigated the role of corporate social and sustainability reporting under stakeholder theory. Studies have investigated the value relevance of corporate sustainability reporting with firms' values, such as Baboukardos and Rimmel (2016) and de Klerk and de Villiers (2012). Few studies have

investigated the effects of social and environmental performance on the cost of capital and debt financing (Ahmed et al., 2019; El Ghouli et al., 2011; Sharfman & Fernando, 2008).

On the other hand, many of these corporate sustainability and value-relevance studies have been carried out in specific legislative settings and countries, such as the US (Herremans et al., 1993; Lo & Sheu, 2007; Guidry & Patten, 2010), Canada (Berthelot et al., 2012), and Australia (Bachoo et al., 2013). However, the results are still inconclusive (Schadewitz & Niskala, 2010). Therefore, this study reveals several gaps in the existing literature on corporate sustainability performance and firm value.

Gap One

To tackle growing environmental and social issues, firms need to take responsibility for their activities in terms of social and environmental consequences (Porter & Kramer, 2006). Stakeholder groups such as investors, shareholders, customers, and governments only know a firm's sustainability strategy and practice when the firm communicates through reporting (Schadewitz & Niskala, 2010). However, to reduce the information asymmetry between internal and external stakeholders, corporate sustainability disclosure plays a significant role in communicating environmental, social, and governance activities (Schadewitz & Niskala, 2010). Sustainability performance reporting is an effective tool to enhance the firm's transparency to external stakeholders while considering tools to influence management decision making in social and environmental issues (Gary et al., 1996; Burritt & Schaltegger, 2010).

Investors and shareholders need sustainability information to make investment decisions, such as retaining or selling their shares. Several studies have been carried out to assess the value relevance of sustainability reporting, but different legislative regimes, the uneven presence of institutional investors, and different levels of stock market efficiency make it more challenging to replicate findings with another capital market, economy, and stakeholders. Eccles et al. (2014), Lawrence et al. (2017), and Lourenço et al. (2012) have attempted to investigate corporate sustainability worldwide. Still, very few studies have addressed the value relevance of sustainability performance in the UK.

However, the results of value-relevance studies are still inconclusive. Therefore, there are considerable gaps in the existing literature on the role of corporate sustainability performance in a firm's value creation process in UK companies (Hermundsdottir and Aspelund (2021) . This study addresses these gaps by analysing the value relevance of corporate sustainability in UK companies.

Gap Two

Sustainability reporting is one of the main tools for communicating corporate sustainability initiatives and practices to stakeholders (Castello et al., 2014). To establish effective communication with stakeholders, corporate sustainability reporting needs to overcome many of its current limitations, such as minimal regulatory control, lack of unified reporting standards, and voluntary adoption (Lock & Seele, 2016). Lourenço and Branco (2013) claimed that sustainability reporting hardly carries any negative information, as it is voluntary. After examining eco-efficiency information in the Netherlands, Asif et al. (2012) claimed that quantitative data do not support the narrative in sustainability disclosure. He also reported that only very few companies disclosed their non-compliance in the sustainability reports. The author also asked for the standardisation of the reporting guidelines to make the sustainability reporting meaningful and reduce the wide variation in quality.

Sustainability reporting indicates what firms say they are doing, which could be completely different from actual practices (Ahmed et al., 2019). The reported sustainability disclosures are sometimes greenwashed, narrative, and qualitative (e.g., Higgins, 2013; Castello et al., 2014; Chen et al., 2015). It is challenging to link this non-quantitative information with share prices (Chen et al., 2015), although previous value-relevance studies have been conducted based on firms' sustainability reporting.

Rating agencies apply the same evaluation methods for every company, making it easy to compare companies. At the same time, most value-relevance studies use binary variables regarding whether firms publish sustainability reports. The binary variables do not represent actual corporate sustainability performance or activities. Therefore, in the existing literature on the value relevance of corporate sustainability, there is a gap in evaluating actual corporate sustainability performance based on sustainability performance scores assessed by independent organisations, such as rating agencies, rather than on sustainability reporting or binary

variables. This study addresses this gap by analysing the value relevance of corporate sustainability performance using a quantitative sustainability performance measure evaluated by independent rating agencies, such as the FTSE4Good Index and Thompson Reuters.

Gap Three

This study primarily focuses on investors' perspectives of sustainability performance and whether sustainability performance creates additional value or diminishes shareholders' value. Sustainability performance includes many aspects of corporate social, environmental, and governance issues, while each investor weighs each sustainability element differently. It is an argument between cost-centred and investment-centred views. The cost-centred view assumes that sustainability activities are carried out at shareholders' cost, while the investment-centred view assumes that sustainability expenditures are investments in the long-term future.

Only a few previous studies have attempted to analyse the relative importance of each element of corporate sustainability on the share price. Some investors could weigh environmental performance more than social and governance performance, while others could weigh it differently (Rajesh, 2020). Therefore, there is a gap in the literature on comparing the value relevance of each element of corporate sustainability environmental, social, and governance performance separately rather than one sustainability value. This study addresses this gap by analysing the value relevance of corporate environmental, social, and governance (ESG) sustainability separately and combinedly using a quantitative performance score evaluated by independent rating agencies in UK companies.

Gap Four

The determinants of corporate sustainability, such as firm size, industry, growth potential, floating cash, business type, and industrial background, vary from firm to firm (Kuzey & Uyar, 2017). Some corporate characteristics influence sustainability performance and firm value, while others can moderate those relationships (Kuzey & Uyar, 2017). Some studies have used particular corporate characteristics, such as industrial background, in their value-relevance studies (such as Hassel et al. 2005). However, in most cases, corporate characteristics have been ignored when assessing the impact of corporate sustainability performance on share prices. In the literature, only a few previous studies have extensively analysed corporate

characteristics' role in the sustainability–share price association. Therefore, this study addresses this gap and assesses the role of firm size, sustainability reputation, industrial background, and age of stock market listing to determine precisely the association between corporate sustainability performance and share price.

Gap Five

Value-relevance studies have been conducted on many occasions in the past and present. However, because of the unavailability of sustainability information from external sources, most value-relevance studies have been conducted on large companies (Kuzey & Uyar, 2017). Big corporations efficiently communicate sustainability practices and performance with stakeholders. At the same time, the sustainability performance of relatively smaller corporations has always been ignored. The literature suggests a difference in sustainability approaches between large and small corporations. Therefore, the effectiveness of their sustainability performance may vary. It is essential to compare and contrast sustainability performance and its effectiveness between different groups of companies based on identical companies.

1.4. Rationale and significance of this research

Stakeholder versus stockholder is a strong argument for establishing a business's prime objectives (Margolis et al., 2009). Servaes and Tamayo (2013) and Fombrun (2005) supported the argument for corporate sustainability spending by initiating the term 'doing well by doing good'. At the same time, some studies support Friedman's (1970) argument that the primary aim of business is to maximise profit and treat CSR activities merely as an unwise use of corporate resources. Therefore, reconciliation between stakeholders and stockholders becomes essential. Robert (2004) argued that serving both shareholders and society is not a mutually exclusive choice. He claims that 'firms are a social organisation formed to serve social needs' (Robert, 2004, p. 20).

It is essential to take care of the relevant interests of society, together with the interests of the investors (Margolis et al., 2009). The current debate on "stockholder vs. stakeholder" forces corporate leaders and scholars to identify whether sustainability spending can create value for

the shareholder. Some recent studies (e.g., de Klerk & de Villiers, 2012; Guenter et al., 2011; Kaspereit & Lopata, 2016; Plumlee et al., 2015) have found that corporate sustainability can enhance firm value in the long term and positively affect the share price. Therefore, sustainability spending can create value for shareholders while caring for other stakeholders, such as customers, employees, and local communities.

Determining the impacts of corporate sustainability performance on share price is the main objective of this study and the primary motivation behind this study. However, while many studies (e.g., Margolis et al., 2009; Choi & Jungh, 2008) have investigated the relationship between CSR and corporate performance, only a few studies address the issue of shareholder value. Recent sustainability reporting increases have driven the issue to analyse and establish the sustainability performance–share price relationship. Therefore, whether capital market prices affect corporate sustainability performance is an open question. This study introduces several new measures to address the existing gaps in the literature as part of the methodologies used to answer this question. Although investors have increased the use of corporate sustainability information, there is no such evidence of its role in investors' assessment of a firm's value. Unlike previous studies using binary variables for sustainability reporting, this study uses all three elements of the environmental, social, and governance (ESG) sustainability performance score evaluated by an independent organisation. At the same time, this study will help determine the relative importance of environmental, social, and governance performance and whether these carry the same level of weighting in value relevance. This study also uses company size, age, reputation, and industrial background in the value-relevance analysis to determine the moderating role between sustainability performance and share price.

Several indices have been developed that link with the financial market to make more informed investment decisions and assess corporate sustainability performance, such as the Dow Jones Sustainability Index (DJSI), the FTSE4Good Index and the MCCI ESG index. Combined ESG sustainability has been added to sustainability indices because of its potential impact on risks and stock prices, which are crucial for optimising investment portfolios (Bos, 2014). As this study focuses on UK-listed companies, FTSE4Good Index membership has been used in the value-relevance analysis to determine whether investors are interested in sustainability index membership, as very little is known about the use of these sustainability indices.

1.5. Research questions

Since the last quarter of 2019, the world has realised that no one is safe until everyone is safe (Seth Berkley, 2021). At the same time, a climate emergency has emerged that affects every inhabitant on Earth. Therefore, corporate sustainability emerges as the leading player in ensuring safety, security, and equality, as the business is the predominant source that generates resources (Nazari et al., 2015). Firms have considered dealing with environmental, social, and governance issues as one of their primary duties while allocating a significant portion of the fund to ensure smooth sustainability activities (Al-Kassar & Al-Nidawiy, 2014). One question that needs to be answered is how investors evaluate sustainability spending. Are they willing to pay more for a firm that does more for environmental and social safety?

Therefore, this study seeks to answer the following fundamental questions:

RQ1: Does corporate sustainability performance provide any new information to investors?

RQ2: Does corporate sustainability performance create value for a company?

RQ3: Does ESG sustainability performance have a similar level of impact across all listed companies in the UK?

This study seeks to answer the above research questions regarding whether corporate sustainability performance changes stock prices. It is essential to assess shareholders' gain (loss) when their money is allocated and spent for the betterment of other business stakeholders. This research will address the above research questions based on the investigation of listed companies on the London Stock Exchange.

1.6. Research aim and objectives

This research aims to critically appraise the value relevance of corporate environmental, social, and governance (ESG) sustainability. This study solely concentrates on UK companies while taking the sample from distinct groups of FTSE100, FTSE250, Small-cap companies, and FTSE4Good companies.

This study set the following objectives:

- To critically review the concept and current practices of environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance, value relevance, and existing theories.
- To appraise and evaluate the value relevance of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) sustainability performance individually and combinedly based on the sustainability performance.
- To assess the moderating role of firm size, industrial background, sustainability reputation, and age of stock market listing on the existing relationship between corporate sustainability and share price.
- To determine the managerial implications of environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance on firms' value.
- To make recommendations on how corporate sustainability performance can be used in practice to maximise stakeholders' interest.

1.7. Contributions of this research

This study makes several specific contributions to the body of knowledge, literature, and organisational practices. This study examines the value relevance of corporate sustainability performance in the UK context using FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, as well as FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies, to compare and contrast the findings. Most previous studies have investigated the value relevance of CSR or sustainability

disclosure (Dhaliwal et al., 2011; Clarkson et al., 2013; Plumlee et al., 2015), ignoring actual sustainability performance.

In addition, this study analyses the moderating role of corporate characteristics, such as firm size, firm's sustainability reputation, industrial background, and age of stock market listing. Comparing and contrasting the findings of FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, as well as FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies, large firms versus small firms, environmentally sensitive industrial background versus service industry firms, high sustainability performance versus low-sustainability performance, old versus new firms, can offer an in-depth relationship between sustainability performance and share price. The in-depth findings could be a significant contribution to this study.

Second, the findings of this study have significant implications for management, investors, lenders, and fund managers. Management can set up sustainability and business strategy, setting preferences among the elements of corporate sustainability based on corporate characteristics that help them maximise firm value. Investors and fund managers can optimise their investment portfolio based on sustainability performance, associated risk, perceived return, and growth potential. The findings can link non-financial ESG performance with financial performance (for example, profitability, and share price) to the management to deal with the potential challenges of identifying, measuring, classifying, and reporting financial performance and ESG (non-financial) performance.

Finally, this study enriches the literature on the value relevance of corporate sustainability as one of the non-financial variables beyond traditional financial variables, such as book value and earnings (Barth & McNichols 1994; Amir & Lev 1996; Hirschey et al. 2001; Choi & Jungh 2008; Pae & Choi 2011). Previous studies have revealed that the value relevance of conventional financial measures decreases over time due to the increasing importance of non-financial information in stock valuation. Now, investors are keen to have non-financial data not reported in the annual report, such as environmental and social performance. Some earlier studies have identified a significant association between the market price of equity and non-financial information, such as environmental performance (Hassel et al., 2005; Lourenço et al., 2012), eco-efficiency (Sinkin et al., 2008), and social and environmental reporting (Berthelot et al., 2012). As this study investigates several aspects of corporate sustainability and firm

characteristics, the findings can validate and justify previous studies on the same topics. This study extends the existing literature on the value relevance of sustainability reporting in the UK.

1.8. Structure of the thesis

Chapter Two has four sections. The first section discusses the basic concept of sustainability and its linkage with corporations. The second section reviews the concept of value relevance of sustainability from an organisational perspective. The third section reviews existing theories that explain sustainability in corporate settings. The final section displays the conceptual framework of this study and the hypotheses.

Chapter Three outlines the details of the methodology and research design. This chapter also discusses details of the sampling procedure, data analysis tools and techniques, measurement scale, systematic development of multiple regression models, data transformation, and regression analysis assumptions.

Chapter Four presents the findings of the statistical tests. This chapter first discusses the descriptive statistics of the variables, followed by the results of each regression model and the results of each hypothesis.

Chapter Five summarises, discusses, and evaluates the findings of this study. This chapter also puts forward the practical implications of each result.

Chapter Six summarises the primary outcomes and contributions of this study. An in-depth set of recommendations is made for the stakeholders. This chapter also suggests some areas for future researchers where further investigation is required.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

This chapter explores and discusses theories and literature related to corporate sustainability performance. The concept of corporate sustainability emerged fairly recently (Searcy & Elkhawas, 2012); this is the predominant term currently in use, along with a range of similar terms such as sustainability and corporate social responsibility (CSR) corporate citizenship. However, this is a growing field that is fundamentally related to the claim of reality and action to address the issue (Tinker & Gray, 2003). Sustainability is a concept that relates to several types of interpretations. The differences in interpretation arise basically from different viewpoints. This viewpoint includes issues from environmental survival, governmental policy making, and individual perspectives (Gray, 2010).

2.2. Concept of sustainability

From an organisational point of view, sustainability combines an organisation's economic, environmental, and social considerations (Banerjee & Linstead, 2009). The World Commission of Environment and Development (1987) provided an idealistic definition of sustainability: "Sustainable development is a development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (WCED, 1987, p.41). Two critical points outlined in this definition are as follows:

- the need for an essential requirement of the world that priority should be given to
- the concept of limitation is related to the ability of the natural environment to fulfil present demands and future needs (WCED, 1987).

Most firms accept only the first part of the UN's definition of sustainability as their responsibility. At the same time, they argue that the other two fundamental ideas, equitable development and limit to development, are not solely applicable to them (Gray & Bebbington, 2001). They believe that it is the government's responsibility to ensure the last two. Milne and Gray (2013) have seen this omission as simplifying the organisational view of sustainability. However, some scholars (e.g., Schaltegger & Burritt, 2006, cited in Elkington, 1998) have

argued that more organisation-centric views have compromised some of the broader macro factors emphasising the future ahead and, as an alternative, proposing the use of an integrated triple bottom line (TBL) concept.

Banerjee & Linstead, (2009) Blowfield & Murray, (2008) have questioned the motivation of removing these two key concepts through simplification of the business definition of sustainability, as they argued that economic growth is by means of opposite to environmental safety and the concept of the use of limited resources, as we believe limitless consumption carries a serious risk for Earth (Birkin, Polesie, & Lewis, 2009). However, the organisation-centric view of sustainability focuses on some core issues, such as organisational transparency, which leads them to be more open to the stakeholder. It is essential to evaluate organisational motivation towards increasing evidence of their behaviour on sustainability (Gray & Bebbington, 2001).

2.2.1. Sustainable development

The fundamental idea of sustainable development is extensive, and it encompasses long-term approaches and justification to ensure economic, social, and ecological development in our society. This development could be achieved through the effective use of resources, minimising energy consumption, reusing, and recycling (Ogunbiyi et al., 2014). However, in the literature, the term ‘sustainable development’ mainly refers to the effective use of natural resources and greenhouse gas reduction; thus, a broader investigation is required to quantify the actual sustainable outcome of any specific project (Doloi, 2012).

The UN Commission on Environment and Development first used the term sustainable development in 1987 to link sustainability to human effort (Murray & Cotgrov, 2007). Sustainable development has been one of the primary concerns for global development since the Rio Summit in 1992, reaching a peak right now because of the worldwide Covid-19 pandemic. At the same time, sustainable development is one of the biggest challenges to world communities, and most social and environmental performance indicators are falling behind (Djeflat, 2010).

An ecological footprint is one of the most important indicators of how a corporation relates to sustainability. Economic, environmental, and social impacts are equally crucial in longer-term sustainable development, affecting how corporations manage these issues (Eskerod & Huemann, 2013).

To understand the concept of sustainable development, it is vital to define sustainability and its three components—the economic, environmental, and social perspectives (Abidin et al., 2013). Cavagnaro and Curiel (2012) stated that the main purpose of sustainable development is to ensure a quality life for all now and in the future through accountability in financial growth, impartial social progress, and the protection of the environment. This notion of environmental, social, and economic consequences is developed based on the triple bottom line style, which incorporates a systems theory that emphasises sustainable development and can only be ensured when all three elements are taken care of.

Thus, sufficient knowledge of sustainability can effectively solve several sustainability issues (Craig et al., 2013), expertise systems can form a network by linking essential actors, stakeholders, organisations, objectives, and multiple functions (Dyllick & Hockerts, 2002). This network can direct organisations towards using natural resources, cutting CO₂ emissions, reducing carbon footprints, improving biodiversity and developing human, social, and ethical legislation. Sustainable development is a continuous process, not a single goal, and it is a continuously moving goal whose exact domain constantly shifts together with the dynamics of the three imperatives moving (Abidin et al., 2013). Thus, sustainable development aims to explore the equilibrium among constantly moving ecological, social, and economic imperatives.

2.2.1.1. Economic sustainability

The economic bottom line is the main bottom line in the triple bottom line model, which involves financial output and related truthfulness (Zhou et al., 2013). A sustainable financial bottom line can be achieved by making an economic profit. In contrast, profit is seen as the reward for employees' satisfaction and communities within the sustainability framework (Elkington, 1994). For example, financial sustainability can be achieved through steady economic growth while building reputation by not damaging the environment' capacity, and

treating employees fairly. According to Zadek et al. (2005), economic sustainability creates material wealth, which includes financial income and assets. Zadek et al. (2005) also claimed that if a firm wishes to adopt the sustainability principle in its strategies, operation, and communication, it first needs to understand how financial impacts are associated with social and environmental outcomes.

2.2.1.2. Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability involves protecting the environment and biodiversity through minimising waste, stopping pollution and ensuring the efficient use of natural resources (OGC, 2007). Environmental performance entails compliance with environmental laws, regulations, and government guidance, operating in environmentally friendly ways, minimising the use of natural resources, and focusing on renewable energy (Renukappa, 2012). Sustainable environmental performance advocates minimising carbon footprints or net-zero carbon emissions if possible so that natural ecosystems do not degrade (Opoku & Ahmed, 2014). The environmental bottom line implies a firm's performance on natural environmental issues (Renukappa, 2012).

2.2.1.3. Social sustainability

According to Renukappa (2012), sustainability is a broader term that includes financial and environmental issues. It discusses the social aspects of sustainability, and emphasises equitable, ethical, and positive business practices with employees, customers, communities, and the countries where they operate (Jones et al., 2014). The social perspectives of sustainability are the organisation's social and people's performance due to its impacts on employees, consumers, and communities (Renukappa, 2012). Thus, the role of social sustainability is to ensure the social well-being of individuals (OGC, 2007). Furthermore, social sustainability implies stakeholder management, particularly with the workforce and community, by reflecting financial, legal, and ethical behaviour favouring them (Renukappa, 2012).

2.3. Organisational perspectives of sustainability

Barter and Bebbington (2010) and Banerjee and Linstead (2009) have seen corporate sustainability as a firm's perception of social, environmental, and economic issues. However, all three elements of sustainability do not receive equal emphasis. 'Although there is much discussion on sustainability to set higher importance on environmental aspects, it is an environmental and a social perception' (Gray & Bebbington, 2001, p. 296). In ordering the concept, Schneider (2014) recommended prioritising the economic issues first, the environmental second, and the social third. However, Gray and Bebbington (2001, pp. 313) noted that 'there has been a little systematic examination of what social sustainability would mean for an organisation'.

Some research on corporate sustainability has been conducted in recent years; however, best practices have not yet been explored (Schneider, 2014). Therefore, the economic, environmental, and social strands are still to be further investigated to develop a compatible shape. The most conventional view of business is that the sole objective of a business is to make a profit (Friedman, 1970). However, corporate sustainability does not mean prioritising economic elements and ignoring the other two as corporate responsibilities.

However, strategic business objectives can be achieved at the maximum level through social incentives and by meeting the social aims and aspirations of the surroundings (Husted & Salazer, 2006). There are two driving forces—in this case, altruism (self-motivation of a business) and coerced egotism (society forces a business)—that led the business to set its strategic objectives in alignment with the social objectives of the business (Revell & Blackburn, 2007; Unerman & O'Dwyer, 2007).

Schneider (2014) criticised the organisation-centric view of sustainability because of the dominance of the profit motive over sustainability and the failure to balance the three strands of sustainability: the economic, environmental, and social elements. Economic strands are always dominant, while environmental and social factors remain subservient to economic strands (Schneider, 2014). There is increasing concern about balancing these three strands for the organisation, which tends to be seen as sustainable. Examples have been found regarding the different treatment of sustainability strands in various organisations. Each of the three sustainability strands is treated as an independent pillar that supports the issue separately, as

three intersecting elements that frequently override each other, or as three integrated elements independently characterised while indirectly integrated within another aspect (Barter & Bebbington, 2010; Barter, 2009). Schaltegger and Burritt (2000, p. 93) showed the movement among three strands of sustainability and their direction and implications.

Figure 1: Interconnection of benefits and costs among the economy, environment, and society.

One of the essential objectives of this research is to understand corporate sustainability and engagement with the business community within which the business operates and controlled (Schneider, 2014). The approach exhibited in Figure 1 is perhaps one of the most acceptable views of sustainability and several generally recognised stakeholders in firms. Market-led sustainability often overrides sustainability logic in an organisation because of economic motivation when both elements run together (Schneider, 2014). It is commonly accepted in an organisation where the financial aspects run parallel with the other two elements and support them; however, it is commonly assumed that if there is any divergence, then economic elements are the first that count (Schneider, 2014).

There is an acceptable approach to sustainability called reflexivity that can help to develop sustainability logic. Schneider (2014, p. 8) defined reflexivity as ‘the continuous consideration of the economic, environmental, and social aspect of sustainability under the explicit observation of particular assumptions, objectives, and power of all organisational stakeholders’. This approach initiates continuous collective learning inside the firms, collaborative discussion, collective choice, and stable outcomes and runs the organisation more sustainably (Schneider, 2014).

A debate on sustainability relates to three interconnected strands of economic, environmental, and social aspects. Milne and Gray (2013) claimed that this sustainability approach is fundamentally the triple bottom line (TBL) style of sustainability practices, although they stated that this is an inadequate term for organisational sustainability and may mislead management. Milne and Gray (2014) argued that the traditional TBL approach is a win-win scenario; therefore, it requires no substantial organisational change. Milne and Gray (2013, p. 14) claimed that sustainability practice requires a firm to change its attitude from a ‘change-but-no-change rhetoric’. Cohen et al. (2008) used a new valuation model aligned with economic, social, and environmental concepts. In their model, they used sustainability variables as a dependent variable, and they renamed these variables performance (economic), promise (social), and perpetuity (environmental) variables. They developed a valuation model that considers the multi-dimensional dependent variable and draws the attention of new research in this area.

Ketola (2010) attempted to establish the nature of corporate sustainability as relative or absolute. From his investigation, Ketola (2010) posited that an organisation typically starts to serve society, while monetary intention comes afterwards. In this way, corporate sustainability objectives can be reached without damaging the environment and society.

2.3.1. Sustainability accounting

Sustainability reporting mainly involves some current reporting practices, including corporate social reporting, corporate citizenship, integrated reporting, and sustainable entrepreneurship (Reddy and Gordon, 2010). Sustainability reporting fundamentally relates to disclosing economic prosperity, social equity, and environmental protection to ensure sustainable development in society. Hahn and Kuhanen, (2013) three-stage process for an effective sustainability performance and reporting structure.

Figure 2: Overview of concept and terminology in sustainability reporting (adopted from Hahn and Kuhnen, 2013, p. 44).

The original thinking point starts from the overarching idea of sustainability and organisational CSR. To start from the beginning of the concept point, we need to go back to the initial reference point of the definition of sustainability and CSR provided by the European Commission. They define sustainability as ‘the responsibilities of an enterprise for their impacts on society to integrate social, environmental, ethical, human rights and consumer concerns into their business operation and core strategy’ (European Commission, 2011, p. 6). In the same way, the ISO 26000 worldwide standard defines organisational responsibilities as ‘responsibility for an organisation for the impacts for its decision and activities on society and environment, through transparent and ethical behaviour’ (International Organisation for Standardization, 2010:3). They also emphasise the point of maximising involvement in sustainable development as the corporation’s overarching objectives.

All of these definitions lead to comprehensive thinking of sustainability as a whole. Dyllick and Hockerts (2002, p.131) define corporate sustainability as ‘meeting the need of a firm’s direct and indirect stakeholders without compromising its ability to meet the needs of future stakeholders’. To attain this goal, the organisation is required ‘to maintain their economic, social, and environmental capital base’ (Dyllick & Hockerts, 2002, p.132), which is similar to Elkington’s (1997) triple bottom line concept.

Lozano and Huisingh (2011) introduce the time dimension of sustainability as short-, long-, and longer-term corporate sustainability. They claimed the interconnection of sustainability elements while having a dynamic and simultaneous interrelation among them over time. Therefore, it is evident that the concepts of sustainability and CSR converge over time (Hahn, 2011). Corporate sustainability and CSR performance are currently measured through sustainability accounting. This part of accounting relates to managing authentic sustainability information to support a firm’s management decision making process.

Sustainability reporting is now gaining increasing relevance in businesses, investors, society, and other stakeholder groups. Sustainability reporting communicates sustainability information regarding the current status and development of corporate sustainability with a broader stakeholder group of the organisation through a formal report (Schaltegger et al., 2006). Sustainability accounting generates extensive internal benefits by measuring organisations’ sustainability performance and provides the basis for sustainability reporting (Lambert, 2005).

The sustainability reporting practice is currently solely voluntary in the corporate reporting regime; therefore, the management board enjoys greater flexibility in disclosing information (Chen & Bouvain, 2009). Therefore, flexibility has led to the use of various names for sustainability reports, such as corporate citizenship reports, corporate responsibility reports, sustainable development reports, sustainable value and sustainability reports, and CSR reports. Almost all the reports possess the underlying normative concepts of sustainability and CSR.

A growing trend has been noticed in disclosing multi-dimensional corporate reports to stakeholders (Kolk, 2010). Integrated reporting is one of the most recent additions to the reporting regime, incorporating sustainability information and conventional accounting data into a single report to offer a rich picture of the organisation (KPMG, 2011). A report must contain simultaneous information on all three dimensions of sustainability elements to be recognised as a sustainability report (Kolk, 2008). In contrast, a one-dimensional report is just an isolated sustainability-related report. On the other hand, some so-called sustainability reports sometimes exclude critical sustainability elements, mainly the financial information they disclose in separate annual financial statements.

There is inconsistency in the literature on terminology in sustainability reporting because even sustainability reporting guidelines try to keep each dimension of reporting separate and ignore their interrelationship (Lozano and Huisingh, 2011; Lozano, 2013). Thus, the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) standardises sustainability reporting language, terminology, and variables for the organisation to adopt as a voluntary guideline. GRI is a sustainability reporting framework that aims to provide a 'globally shared framework of concepts, consistent language and metrics to communicate clearly and openly about sustainability' (GRI, 2011b, p. 3). GRI framework focuses on reporting social and environmental issues addressing only a few economic indicators and leaves the detailed financial part to be reported under existing financial reporting frameworks such as the Generally Accepted Accounting Principle (GAAP) and the International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS).

2.3.2. Reporting sustainability performance

Firms use numerous names and labels to communicate their performance towards social, environmental, and governance issues in their social and environmental reports. The following names have been used as report names:

- Environment Reports – Boeing (2000)
- Social and Environment Report – BP Amoco (1998), IKEA (2003)
- Environment Health and Safety Report – Eni (2005), Xerox (2011)
- Social Responsibility Report – Petrobras (2003)
- Corporate Social Responsibility Report – The Hershey Company (2011)
- Sustainability Report – Coca-Cola (2010), Royal Dutch Shell (2010), Volkswagen (2010)

There is still massive confusion over the most frequently used terminology in the social and environmental accounting literature because of various names and the lack of unified terminology (Gray, 2007). Scholars, corporations, and stakeholders use standard terms such as corporate social responsibility reporting, sustainability performance disclosure, health, and safety reports, and triple bottom line reporting; however, a significant difference exists among the terms (Aras & Crowthers, 2009). Therefore, this section will critically analyse the various terms used in the social and environmental reporting literature to understand the reporting terminology.

John Elkington (1997) first used the term ‘triple bottom line’ to explain sustainable development. He claimed that a firm needs to extend its current reporting practices from only a single bottom line of financial performance to a triple bottom line reporting approach, which eventually includes the financial, social, and environmental bottom line. In addition, the triple bottom line reporting concept emerges from the idea of the 3Ps, which relates to profit, people, and the planet. This reporting concept recognises the firm’s accountability to report performance on profit, people and planet issues.

Both the triple bottom line and sustainability disclosure address all three major sustainability elements: financial, social, and environmental activities; therefore, both terms can be argued as analogous. However, Ball and Gray (2008) claimed that triple bottom line reporting is inadequate to serve the purpose of sustainability. Lamberton (2005) argued that triple bottom line reporting and sustainability are not linked to each other, while, GRI performance indicators and corporate sustainability performance show sufficient linkage. Elkington (1997) also acknowledges that forcing companies to report to what extent they are reducing the options open to the next generation is challenging. Milne et al. (2008) claimed that TBL reporting is merely a step in full accountability of the company's activities and a progression map towards sustainability.

Gary et al. (1995, p. 47) defined corporate social reporting as 'the process of communicating the social and environmental effects of an organisation's economic activities to particular interest groups within society and society at large. Thus, it involves extending the accountability of the organisation beyond the traditional role of providing a financial account to the owners of capital, particularly shareholders.'

Gray et al. (1995) recognised that the firm has the responsibility and obligation to make a profit for the shareholder, while other stakeholder groups are interested in the company's sustainability performance. Gray et al. (1995, p.48) explained corporate social reporting as 'all possible forms of accounting that includes both self-reporting by the organisation and reporting about the organisation by third parties, information in the annual report and any other form of communication, both public domain and private information, information in any medium (financial, non-financial, quantitative, non-quantitative), it is not restricted necessarily by reference to the selected recipient, and the information deemed to be CSR may, ultimately, embrace any subject'.

Social accounting literature assumes that CSR reports are intended to disclose specific areas of firms' activities, which usually affect the environment, employees, ethical issues related to consumers and products, and local and international communities. Therefore, CSR reporting involves acknowledging a firm's responsibilities beyond economic accountability and disclosing a formal report regarding social and environmental activities to a broader set of stakeholders.

The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) defined a sustainability report as a corporate picture of economic, environmental, and social dimensions reported to internal or external stakeholders or the public. In summary, sustainability reports tend to disclose firms' contributions to overall sustainable development (WBCSD, 2002). Therefore, from the definition of sustainability reporting, it is clear that it reports on the three distinct pillars of sustainability and a firm's contribution to global sustainable development.

Both sustainability reporting and triple bottom line reporting are integrated reporting that involves reporting on environmental, social, and economic aspects of a firm's activities. In contrast, CSR reporting is usually a standalone report relating to social and environmental activities and performance. However, sustainability reporting characteristically contains a statement on the firm's involvement in sustainable development, and the concept of sustainable development is missing in triple bottom line or CSR reporting.

Sustainability reporting is treated as the most advanced means of communicating a firm's accountability (Cooper & Owen, 2007). This form of reporting remains the top among all social and environmental reporting media. While triple bottom line reporting is placed second from the top of the hierarchy after sustainability reporting, this kind of report does not contribute to global sustainable development. On the other hand, corporate social responsibility reporting generally carries social and environmental information but no financial information. Therefore, CSR reporting stands third at the top of the reporting hierarchy. On the other hand, standalone reports, such as environmental reports, social reports, and health and safety reports, mainly disclose only one aspect of sustainability; therefore, these means of reporting stand in fourth place in the hierarchy.

Reporting complexity typically grows upward. In reality, the scenario is not similar to the academic literature. Firms sometimes choose the terminology for their reporting to disclose and outline their sustainability reporting. Sometimes, the reporting title does not give an accurate picture of the disclosure; for example, a company's sustainability report may include only environment-related disclosure. However, this study assumes that sustainability reporting denotes the whole universe of social and environmental disclosures through integrated reporting or standalone reports.

2.3.4. Corporate sustainability performance reporting regulations

Corporate sustainability reporting tools (SRT) are mainly categorised into the framework, standards, ratings and indices. The framework primarily denotes principles and guidelines for corporations to disclose sustainability efforts (Siew, 2015). On the other hand, standards are characterised similarly to the framework but in a more formalised way that pinpoints the additional precise requirements and specifications to ensure consistency in sustainability reporting (Siew, 2015). Ratings and indices are an assessment carried out by an independent third party to evaluate corporate sustainability performance while facilitating inter-firm comparison (Siew, 2015).

The framework is the general guideline for reporting sustainability performance to the information user. Several sustainability reporting frameworks are commonly used in practice, and the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) is the most dominant (Siew, 2015). The UNEP first introduced GRI in 1997 to encourage sustainability reporting, such as financial reporting (Dilling, 2010). Several environmental regulations have been reconciled within the GRI framework to develop a commonly acceptable reporting mechanism, including the Kyoto Protocol, the Montreal Protocol, and the Greenhouse Gas Protocol (Hedberg & Von Malmborg, 2003). GRI framework has 79 qualitative and quantitative performance indicators, among which 50 are categorised as core performance indicators. In contrast, the remaining 29 indicators are classified as additional to the reporting entity that could or may not apply to all entities (Dilling, 2010). GRI frameworks are voluntary, while GRI advocates reporting the vision and strategy, corporate profile, governance structure, management systems, GRI content index, and performance criteria (Adams & Narayanan, 2007).

Sustainability indices serve as intermediaries between companies and stakeholders. Sustainability indices are considered objective and professional benchmarks prepared by neutral intermediaries through a rigorous evaluation of a company's sustainability information and practices (Robinson et al., 2011). The prime objective of indices and rating agencies is to understand corporate behaviour in the context of information asymmetry and signalling theory.

Sustainability indices report corporate sustainability. Among the current sustainability indices, the Dow Jones Sustainability Index (DJSI), FTSE4Good Index, KLD index, Ethical Sustainability Index (ESI), Socially Responsible Index (SRI), and Domini 400 Social Index are

the most prominent (Robinson et al., 2011). ESG rating institutions collect and analyse a large volume of sustainability performance data for many companies. Some of these data are extra-financial in nature, while others are financial and non-financial to evaluate firms' value and sustainability in the longer term (Siew, 2015).

Rating agencies compile data from companies through questionnaires, collect information from published sources, and then analyse data through an interdisciplinary workforce to prepare the report. The post-2008 financial crisis forced some rating agencies to consolidate to bolster reporting quality. However, financial stakeholders and investment decision makers are the primary users of the indices and ratings (Siew, 2015).

2.3.5. The role of corporate sustainability reporting

Corporate sustainability reporting communicates a firm's behaviour on environmental and social issues with stakeholders (Morsing & Schultz, 2006). Sustainability reporting is vital in communicating a firm's performance on social and environmental issues with external information users. Gray et al. (2011) stated that the controllers of resources are accountable to society and should disclose how efficiently they use the resources. This kind of disclosure must flow freely within a democratic society. This is a way for the firm to discharge corporate accountability. Corporate accountability is the duty of those activities for which a firm is held responsible (Gray et al., 1996). Therefore, sustainability reporting is one of the robust tools used to fulfil accountability and ensure a continuous supply of information (Gray, 2007). In addition to the accountability and free flow of information, the firm must emphasise that the reported information is useful to the stakeholders (Cooper & Owen, 2007).

Generally, information carries limited or no value if it fails to influence a decision. GRI (2002, p. 9) stated that 'report alone provides a little value if it fails to inform stakeholders or support a dialogue that influences the reporting organisation's decisions and behaviour and its stakeholders'. Stakeholders are crucial parts of the business, as the business exists for them; therefore, they possess considerable power to influence corporate behaviour (Adams & Whelan, 2009). Thus, stakeholders' feedback on information supplied through sustainability reports is crucial, as it shapes the firm's future behaviour.

Sustainability reporting also brings transparency and increases the visibility of the organisation to society (Gray et al., 1997). Additionally, Lehman (1995) claimed that organisational transparency ensures that the accountability relationship has been fulfilled.

Sustainability disclosure can significantly impact a firm's behaviour relating to management decisions on CSR. Burritt and Schaltegger (2010) claimed that the role of sustainability accounting is to inflow information for management decision making. When reliable and relevant information is provided, managers and the board can only make accurate decisions to promote global sustainable development. Thus, adequate and reliable information is one of the prerequisites for improving managers' decision effectiveness in a firm's sustainability practices (Burritt & Schaltegger, 2010). In this regard, Prakash and Rappaport (1977) used a new term called information inductance, which they defined as a systematic practice in which the report characteristics can be affected by the nature of the information to be communicated. In the same way, sustainability reporting makes the reporter more informed and conscious of sustainability practices, as well as conflicts of interest (Gray & Bebbington, 2001). At the same time, Lehman (1995) claimed that sustainability disclosure bolsters a firm's awareness.

Another vital role of sustainability reporting is to make stakeholders know the effects of a firm's activities on society and the environment (Gray, 2007). He stated that 'addressing accountability through substantive accountability reporting would be a first significant and sensible step to begin to expose the extent to which the potential doomsday scenarios are worthy of our attention or not. The action that such accountability might prompt could, in turn, actually releases shareholders value in the sense that it might lead to activities that ensured shareholders might still be alive' (Gray, 2006, p.810). An accountant plays an essential role in providing relevant information to evaluate social and environmental utilisation (Lehman, 1995).

2.4. Concept of value relevance

Information is regarded as relevant only when it possesses the capacity to influence decisions. Value-relevant information is that which affects shareholders in their investment decision making (Barth et al., 2001). A financial statement carries an organisation's financial

information to facilitate shareholders and investors in making informed investment decisions (Deegan & Blomquist, 2006). Accounting numbers and capital market variables have been investigated through capital market research and market-based accounting research. Market-based accounting research based on the efficient market hypothesis is the primary assumption for analysing the value relevance of accounting numbers to define stock market buying behaviour (Barth et al., 2001). The capital market is assumed to be efficient when all available information is reflected in the share price (Fama, 1991).

The Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) is mainly apparent in three forms of market efficiency: weak, semi-strong, and strong (Fama, 1991). The market share price is determined primarily by historical public information available to the shareholder under the weak form of market efficiency (Fama, 1991). In the strong form of market efficiency, any current information, even if not published, reflects on the current share price (Fama, 1991). However, in the semi-strong form of market efficiency, all relevant publicly available information immediately reflects the share price. According to Ball and Brown (1968), market-based accounting research is mainly based on semi-strong efficiency. The financial market reacts as soon as new accounting numbers are released; this notion of explaining stock market reactions or changes in the share price is called the value relevance of accounting numbers in investment decisions. This explains the relevance of information in valuing equity.

Francis and Schipper (1999) explained value relevance with four different interpretations. According to Francis and Schipper (1999, p. 352), 'accounting information is value-relevant when:

- it captures the intrinsic value towards which share prices drift
- it compares information in the valuation model
- it changes investor's expectations
- there is a relation between this information and the firm's market value'.

However, most value-relevance studies have been carried out based on Francis and Schipper's fourth interpretation. Accounting numbers are one of the many information sources an investor uses in an investment decision. Therefore, the objective of value-relevance studies is to identify whether a particular set of information affects investment decisions.

From the empirical evidence, Holthausen and Watts (2001) identified three value-relevance studies: event studies, relative studies, and incremental association studies. Event studies mainly test the stock market reaction when new information becomes available or when any declaration comes (Holthausen & Watts, 2001). Brown and Ball (1968) used one of the first event studies to test stock price fluctuations before and after the earnings announcement. On the other hand, association studies measure the explanatory power (R^2) of accounting numbers over some time. This study mainly focuses on whether the R^2 changes by adding and deducting any accounting variable or separating bottom-line numbers under different standards or legislation (Holthausen & Watts, 2001). This study is based on relative and incremental association studies to analyse the value relevance of corporate sustainability performance. An incremental value-relevant study measures the value relevance of the accounting variable through the variable coefficient, which is assumed to be significantly different from zero (Holthausen & Watts, 2001). This method is most widely used to measure the value relevance of non-financial reports or voluntary disclosures, in addition to financial statements.

2.4.1. Measurements of firm value

A firm's value is a financial measure that reflects the firm's financial price allocated to its shareholders. The easiest way of calculating firm value is by adding up the price of ordinary shares and deducting net liabilities (Holthausen & Watts, 2001). There are several measures to calculate a firm's value using a range of variables; however, each method provides a different value for the firm. Net worth is the difference between total equity and total debt, also called a firm's total value. Therefore, valuing the firm mainly depends on valuing debt that is predominantly fixed claims from the debtholders and valuing equity, which is not very straightforward, as the equity holders are the residual claimant (Fatemi et al., 2015).

One of the simplest methods of calculating firm value is the net book value method, which is simply the total assets less total liabilities. The researcher does not advise using net book value methods in valuation, as this method uses balance sheet reporting and follows the historical cost approach (Mervelskemper & Streit, 2017). Therefore, the net book value method ignores the future potential of a firm. At the same time, another measure of a firm's valuation is to use all outstanding shares' market value. Using the market price of an outstanding share is a

market-based measure of valuation widely used in recent times (Mervelskemper & Streit, 2017). This market-based valuation method assumes a strong form of market efficiency; therefore, the share value reflects all available information and future potential. However, in reality, the existence of a strong form of an efficient market is hard to find. Scholars and academicians have acknowledged this method to calculate the firm value by using the market value of the outstanding share as a proxy (Choi & Jungh, 2008).

Another common method of calculating equity is the discounting cash flow method developed by using Miller and Modigliani's (1961) arguments. This technique is also called the Gordon growth model or dividend discount model (Gordon & Shapiro, 1956; Gordon, 1959), which considers all possible future dividend payments and discounts them to the present value.

There is another method of equity valuation called the residual income valuation model, developed by Edwards and Bell (1961) and modified by Peasnell (1982) and Ohlson (1995). This model uses traditional accounting information measured by the total book value and the present value of expected future residual income. To calculate the firm value, any of these methods can be used, while all these methods aim to determine the real economic value using historical and present performance and future potential.

2.4.2. Model to assess the value-relevance studies

Value-relevance studies assess the relationship between the accounting information of financial statements and market share price. This methodology examines whether the stock price is dependent on the accounting information disclosed in the financial statement in a cross-sectional or time series analysis. Most valuation models have been developed based on the firm's value measured by share price (Miller & Modigliani, 1961; Ohlson, 1995). There is an alternative approach to assessing value relevance by observing changes in stock prices (market return). The particular valuation equation depends on the model used, such as Ohlson (1995). Assessing the stock price variation eliminates the base price and investigates the price variation rather than the full stock price. However, the selection of the measurement approach relies on the nature and characteristics of the research.

Barth et al. (2001) explained value relevance as the perceived quality of information to investors. Value relevance involves reflecting particular variables' capability to influence investors' decision making. However, the precise meaning of value-relevance study is to investigate the relationship between expected share price and market share price. Value-relevance research suggests that the financial statement's fundamental motive is to attract equity investment. This association was first investigated in 1960 by Modigliani and Miller (1961), while the term 'value relevance' was first used to describe this association by Amir, Harris, and Venuti (1993).

There are two fundamental criteria to be met before deciding whether the information is value-relevant: relevance and reliability. A predicted variable can only be concluded as significant if it has a significant association with share price and the information relevant to the investors when valuing a firm and can be measured reliably (Amir & Baruch, 1996). Financial statement information is treated as relevant only when it makes a difference in the user's decision. Ohlson's (1995) model was developed based on the book value of assets and earnings from the financial statement; thus, the accounting standards relevant to the preparation of financial statements are worth considering. Barth (2000) pointed out that this information does not need to be new.

Additionally, Barth (2000) differentiated between the terms 'value relevance' and 'decision relevance' of information. Financial statement information can sometimes be value relevant but not decision relevant if it overlaps with up-to-date data. Therefore, testing value relevance means testing both relevance and reliability; thus, value relevance also indicates the reliability of the information, at least to some extent (Barth et al., 2001). However, the accounting standard or conceptual framework for preparing a financial statement does not indicate the extent of reliability and relevance adequate for meeting the indicated standards.

Regarding the objectives and implications of the value-relevance study, Barth (2000) pointed out that this study has significant implications for the issue of interest to academic and non-academic users; however, it does not make any particular policy recommendations. Some previous value-relevance studies openly discuss the caveats that policy implications cannot be made. In this context, Barth (1991) pointed out that the value-relevance study focuses on the relevance and reliability of the other choices for shareholders and investors to apply. There is

no concrete definition of relevance and reliability, and according to Barth (1991), it is complicated and hypercritical. As a result, value-relevance research tends not to measure the firm's market value; as a fundamental analysis, its objective is to concentrate on whether any specific accounting value is value relevant, and can thus be used as an essential element to determine a firm's value.

Fundamental analysis studies include all possible variables, including those not disclosed in the financial statement, which can have some input in predicting current or future value. Therefore, fundamental analysis studies do not concentrate on whether the information is relevant for valuation purposes. On the other hand, value-relevance studies include selective accounting variables in estimating equations to identify whether the selected variables have valuation characteristics. This current research study employed a basic valuation model developed by Ohlson (1995), which was also subsequently modified by Feltham and Ohlson (1995), Feltham and Ohlson (1996), Ohlson (1998), and Ohlson (2001). In the first valuation model, Ohlson (1995) described firm value as a linear function of the book value of equity and the present value of expected future abnormal earnings.

However, with this primary thought, Ohlson (1995) revised the model, as firm value is the linear function of the book value of equity, net income, dividends, and other information. According to Ohlson (1995), both balance sheet-based and earning-based valuation models are two different extremes based on the restrictive supposition of the tenacity of abnormal earnings.

Feltham and Ohlson (1995, 1996) first modified Ohlson's (1995) valuation model by differentiating financing and operating activities by adding aspects involved with the integrity of conservative accounting information in valuation. For a firm, financing relates to the firm's assets and liabilities, which can be traded in the perfect market; thus, book value and market value are equal. On the other hand, operating assets and liabilities cannot be traded in the ideal market; therefore, accruals require cash flow adjustments. As a result of the differences between the book value and the operating assets' market value, the intangible asset value arises.

However, in terms of debt, Olson's (1995) model adopts the basic concept of Modigliani and Miller (1961), which assumes a firm's borrowing and lending produces zero net present value because they are both classed as financial assets. Therefore, the value of the firm's equity and financial and operating assets will be equal. In Feltham and Ohlson's (1995, 1996) model, an

additional adjustment was made to determine the expected growth in operating assets. Ohlson's (1995) valuation model is one of the most frequently used models in value-relevance research. It brings both the bottom surplus of the financial statement, net profit, and net asset in equity valuation and offers maximum credibility of the financial statement as being value-relevant (de Klerk & de Villiers, 2012).

2.4.3. Sources of value-enhancing capabilities

Creating value for shareholders has been the prime objective of business since the inception of the corporate form of business. This value incorporates the short-term profitability and longer-term effects of business strategy, management decisions, and future growth prospects. An organisation can adopt unique business strategies to increase its value by maximising revenue and minimising expenses. Firm value is mainly dominated by profit maximisation; however, some unique ideas, market extension, competitive advantages, and the creation of a loyal customer base, can lead to increased company value (Malik, 2014). On the other hand, reducing expenses, such as suppliers' costs, litigation and compliance costs, and increased productivity results in higher profitability and firm value (Malik, 2014). A large part of the firm's value depends on the associated risk; therefore, risk management is vital for the supply chain (Gramlich & Finster, 2013). Business risk leads to an increased cost of capital, which means less present value of future cash flow and low firm value. Thus, the firm's value can be maximised by increasing profit, decreasing cost, and managing business risk (Malik, 2014).

2.4.4. Firms' CSR performance and value maximisation

Corporate social responsibility is integral to business, and people hardly dispute this argument. However, some people dispute whether the expenses for firms' social responsibility behaviour comply with the shareholders' value maximisation assumption (Kansal et al., 2016). CSR generates benefits in numerous forms; some directly influence the firm's performance directly, while others indirectly (Malik, 2014). Some argue that CSR incurs additional expenses that disadvantage the firm financially (Aupperle et al., 1985). Other arguments have shown that

CSR incurred relatively smaller expenses than the benefits it produces (Alexander & Buchholz, 1978; McWilliams & Siegel, 2000).

A positive stock market return is one of those direct benefits that can be enhanced through superior environmental, social, and governmental behaviour. Malik (2014) pointed out some other benefits that outstanding CSR produce, including but not limited to product-market benefits, worker efficiency, operational productivity, company branding, a better relationship with wider stakeholders, and increased profitability. All of these benefits from better CSR behaviour ultimately direct the firm to enjoy increased value.

Figure 3: CSR benefits for the business (from Malik, 2014).

Figure 3 shows how CSR can generate benefits for corporations in recent times. CSR and sustainability can enhance the firm's value through many aspects of the business, including employees, customers, communities, the environment, investors, regulators, and supplies (see Figure 3). According to Malik (2014), better CSR performance increases employee productivity, creates staff motivation, build up employer reputation and attract top employee to work for. Regarding customer benefits, Malik (2014) mentioned that CSR performance increases brand value, creates customer loyalty and increases sales revenue.

For the community, CSR helps to develop corporate branding, get positive media coverage and provide a positive signal to society. To the environment, CSR produces an environmental reputation and minimise regulatory fine. CSR enhance many benefits to investors, which includes better market return (Du et al. 2017), reduced cost of capital (El Ghoul et al. 2011), and minimising information asymmetry. Malik (2014) also claimed CSR firm earn some additional facilities from the regulators, such as CSR reducing regulatory risk, getting favourable treatments and influencing policy development. Additionally, from the supplier's side, CSR firms receive lower-cost supplies, extending the diversity and favourable credit terms.

2.4.5. Capital market benefits of CSR sustainability

Nobody debates the social responsibility of a business. However, the previous literature provides evidence in support of and against the notion of value creation through sustainability activities. Previous literature (Dhaliwal et al., 2011; Blacconiere & Patten, 1994; Kaspereit & Lopatta, 2016) investigated the potential benefit of superior sustainability performance, such as higher stock market yields, lower cost of capital, and lower market risk while reducing information asymmetry.

Prior research indicates a positive relationship between CSR sustainability and stock market return, market capitalisation, and market-to-book value (de Klerk & de Villiers, 2012; Garcia-Castro et al., 2010). The other benefits of CSR sustainability include higher productivity, increased customer loyalty, enhanced firm reputation, and increased regulatory and supervisory assistance, which ultimately positively affect the firm's value in the long run (Waddock & Graves, 1997; Luo & Bhattacharya, 2009; Eccles et al., 2013).

Wang et al. (2011) investigated CSR impacts on investment decisions and found uneven investor responses across various global stock markets. Dijken (2007) claimed that not all CSR activities help stock market gains, but only value-driven CSR activities outperform the stock market. Bird and Smucker (2007) revealed that firms that strategically accept a broader stakeholder policy frequently unknowingly sacrifice stockholder interests.

Dhaliwal et al. (2011) investigated the impacts of CSR sustainability practices on the cost of equity capital and found a strong negative association. At the same time, Humphrey et al. (2012) noticed no considerable relationship between these two variables. In addition to the lower cost of equity capital, Ye and Zhang (2011) claimed that CSR sustainability can help firms reduce borrowing costs. Investigating US data, Cheng et al. (2012) revealed that higher CSR-performing companies have good access to wider sources of finance. The environmental perspectives of CSR sustainability predominantly drive this better access.

At the same time, Renneboog et al. (2008) claimed that the socially responsible investment portfolio's actual risk-adjusted returns are not significantly different from those of traditional investment funds. In particular, their study reported a -2.2% to -6.5% lower return compared to the domestic average after investigating US, UK, European, and Asia Pacific markets. At the same time, this research revealed that there is no significant difference between the risk-adjusted returns of socially responsible investment portfolios and traditional investment funds in countries such as France, Japan, and Sweden.

DeVilliers and Van Staden (2010) conducted a study in South Africa that revealed that individual investors required environmental sustainability information for their investment decisions. It is the manager's responsibility to provide such information, as firms are accountable for their environmental activities. Some early studies have been conducted to assess the value relevance of CSR sustainability in the short term using event studies (e.g., Blacconiere and Patten, 1994; Dasgupta et al., 2006; Hamilton, 1995; Patten, 1990). These studies concentrated on bad sustainability performance and its impact on market share prices. They concluded that investors penalise poorly performing firms, which ultimately affects their value. Freedman and Patten (2004) suggested that extensive reporting can help to mitigate the negative impacts of bad environmental performance.

Hassel et al. (2005) used Ohlson's (1995) valuation model to investigate the relationship between environmental performance ratings for stock market purposes and the share price on the Stockholm stock exchange. Their findings revealed that environmental performance is negatively associated with stock prices. Their study supported the cost-centred view of sustainability, which suggests that environmental investment predominantly incurred additional costs compared to its related benefit. Their findings also indicated no significant

differences in terms of the negative stock price association between manufacturing and service companies. The primary role of corporate sustainability is to ensure long-term sustainable development. The literature suggests both positive and negative associations between corporate sustainability and share prices. However, when sustainability information influences investors' decisions, then the information is treated as value-relevant. This study aims to assess the value relevance of corporate sustainability performance for various types of companies.

2.5. Theoretical perspectives on sustainability reporting practice

Several researchers (e.g., Adams and Whelan, 2009; Deegan, 2002; Parker, 2005) have claimed there are no agreed-upon theoretical perspectives for corporate sustainability performance and practice. Researchers have used several theoretical perspectives to explain corporate sustainability practices. Gray et al. (2009) classified these theoretical perspectives into three distinct classes:

- decision usefulness studies
- economic theory studies
- social and political theory studies

Mathews (1987), Tilt (1994), and Gray et al. (2009) divided sustainability practice and disclosure theories into three main paradigms. These theoretical paradigms are functionalist, interpretivist, and radical theoretical perspectives.

	Functionalist	Interpretative	Radical
	Metaphor : Economic / rationalist	Metaphor : Political / sociological	Metaphor : Political / sociological
Meta – theory			Marxian political economy
Meso/ sub- systems level			Bourgeois political economy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accountability • Media agenda setting
Micro 1 /organisational	Decision usefulness Economic theory	Legitimacy theory Stakeholder theory	

Figure 4: Theoretical perspective of corporate sustainability (adopted from Gray et al., 2009, p. 12).

This diagram presents three levels of theoretical resolutions: meta-theory, meso-subsystem level, and Micro I-organisational level. However, this theoretical model also includes two more theoretical resolution levels: Micro II - internal organisation level and Micro III - individual level. The details of each theoretical perspective and relevant theories are explained in the following 2.5.1 to 2.5.3.

2.5.1. Functionalist perspectives

The functionalist perspective reflects only the financial association between the firm and its stakeholders, such as individual-level users, including investors and shareholders. According to Gray et al. (2009), functionalist perspectives generally include conventional management theories. Decision usefulness studies and economic theory studies are the two dominant theories under this theoretical paradigm.

2.5.1.1. Decision usefulness studies

The decision usefulness studies advocate the use of corporate sustainability information in investment decision making (Dierkes & Antal, 1985; Milne & Chan, 1999). According to the decision usefulness argument, corporate disclosure needs to be prepared in such a way that the information is useful to investors or other stakeholders (Gray et al., 2009). Decision usefulness theoretical perspective motivates researchers to investigate two different issues. These are

investors' information requirements (Buzby & Falk, 1978; Epstein & Freedman, 1994; Harte, Lewis, & Owen, 1991; Milne & Chan, 1999; Rockness & Williams, 1988). Second, the stock market reacts to sustainability information such as ESG (Anderson & Frankle, 1980; Belkaoui, 1976; Guidry & Patten, 2010; Murray, Sinclair, Power, & Gray, 2006).

The results of previous studies that investigated the investor's information needs are mixed. One of the first studies on this topic conducted by Buzby and Falk (1978) was based on the mutual fund survey, which resulted in some social and environmental issues, including illegal business practices and environmental pollution, which are considered useful in investment decision making. The survey also revealed that eight of the nine social issues ranked in lower importance than the six financial indicators. A study of 3,000 individual investors was conducted by Epstein and Freedman (1994) to investigate investors' social and environmental information needs. The results advocated investors' information needs, such as product quality, environmental activities, corporate integrity, workers' welfare, and social connection.

Deegan and Rankin (1997) conducted empirical studies in the Australian context to examine the effectiveness of financial statement disclosures. They reported that stockbrokers and financial analysts prefer environmental indicators in investment decision making rather than financial indicators. In contrast, environmental information was found to be material to other stakeholders, particularly shareholders. Therefore, there is a mixed view of the usefulness of social and environmental information, where some find that these are material in investment decisions, while others do not.

The reliability of ESG information disclosed in sustainability disclosures is one of the most significant parts of reporting under constant threat since its inception. Rockness and Williams (1988, p. 408) stated that 'the managers consistently cited the lack of adequate social performance information'. On the other hand, Epstein and Freedman (1994) claimed that most shareholders in their survey preferred to have audited sustainability disclosures to boost their confidence in the reliability issue. Epstein and Freedman (1994) also noted that the report should be audited so that it looks credible and the readers of the statement get a positive impression regarding the authenticity of the data disclosed. As a result, the reliability of information disclosed in the sustainability report assumed significance in the usefulness of such information in investment decision making.

The second thought of the decision usefulness perspective persuades researchers to investigate ESG sustainability impacts on stock valuation or stock market reactions in the short and long term. This stance is based on the efficient market hypothesis, which states that any information relevant to investors should be reflected in stock prices (Fama, 1991). If the stock price changes or the stock market reacts to the availability of sustainability information, it means that the investor must use it when making an investment decision (Epstein & Freedman, 1994). Empirical studies have found mixed results. Guidry and Patten (2010) conducted a research study of first-time disclosure of sustainability reports in the US market and concluded no significant stock market reaction. They further investigated whether the reports' quality affects the research finding and concluded that higher-quality reports attract more positive responses than lower-quality ones.

However, since the beginning of corporate sustainability practice, disclosure guidance and legislation have changed significantly, while different reporting regimes give this issue different weighting (Gray et al., 2015). The recent climate movement, ethical investment issues, corporate social responsibilities and governance issues in the UK motivate this thesis to be conducted in the UK based on data from the London Stock Exchange, one of the three best-known stock markets in the world.

2.5.1.2. Economic theory perspective

The second thought of the functionalist theory perspective of corporate sustainability is an economic theory that is mainly consistent with the main arguments of agency theory proposed by Watts and Zimmerman (1978). According to the economic theory perspective, a corporation mainly involves voluntary sustainability activities and disclosures to avoid government regulations (Watts, 2015). Government regulations are always mandatory and offer less flexibility regarding the issue of increased costs (Adler & Milne, 1997). Ness and Mirza (1991) advised that voluntary social activities are mainly based on the corporation's welfare, based on the agency theory view. At the same time, Belakoui and Karpik (1989) concluded that corporations mainly involve sustainability activities to reduce net profit so that corporations can reduce their political visibility. Empirical evidence suggests that voluntary disclosure of social information is significantly associated with a higher level of profitability; alternatively,

a highly profitable corporation possesses more capacity to spend resources on social issues. Ness and Mirza (1991) investigated companies in polluting industries and revealed that they are likely to disclose environmental performance more comprehensively to reduce their visibility. Ness and Mirza (1991) also argued that management only chooses information that increases its benefits based on agency theory.

Like the decision usefulness theory, the economic theory perspective also considers sustainability reporting as an accounting tool that is eventually used to increase value. However, Deegan (2004) claimed that both decision usefulness and economic theory perspectives are subject to criticism because they try to explain corporate sustainability performance. Lehman (1995), who relied solely on decision usefulness to explain the whole corporate sustainability disclosure, is misleading. According to Lehman (1991), it is too narrow to view sustainability from investor perspectives; corporate sustainability information is only useful to investors when it can affect the economic position. The information disclosed on sustainability performance targets comprehensive stakeholder groups (Deegan, 2004; Gray et al., 2009; Gray et al., 1988; Lehman, 1995). However, the power of social and environmental sustainability disclosure to influence stakeholder decision making has not been tested broadly (Deegan, 2004; Gray et al., 2009; Gray et al., 1988; Lehman, 1995). While using agency theory, the economic perspective has occasionally been investigated, with inconsistent findings (Gray et al., 2009).

2.5.2. Interpretative perspective

The interpretative perspective discusses the role of sustainability performance in the existing association between organisations and society (Tilt, 1994). Gray et al. (2009) predominantly included stakeholder theory and legitimacy theory under this theoretical paradigm. Both stakeholder theory and legitimacy theory are organisational-level classifications that deal with individual or organisational relationships between society and organisation. The interpretative perspective considers the whole stakeholder group rather than only financial stakeholders, such as the functionalist perspective. Spence et al. (2010) stated that this theoretical perspective has been used extensively to justify corporate sustainability practices.

2.5.2.1. Stakeholder theory

Freeman (1984, p. 25) defined corporate stakeholders as ‘any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organisation’s objectives’. Freeman’s (1984) definition of a corporate stakeholder is frequently cited in the literature (Laplume, Sonpar, & Litz, 2008). Freeman (1984, p. 25) identified the following stakeholders from the organisation’s perspective: owner, suppliers, employees, competitors, customers, media, governments, environmentalists, and local community organisations. However, Gray et al. (1996) expanded the existing directory of stakeholders by including future generations and nonhuman life.

In considering the list of stakeholders, there are multiple groups of stakeholders. Stakeholder theory mainly involves integrating the stakeholders’ expectations into the organisation’s strategy and planning to get the stakeholders’ support (Parker, 2005). Some stakeholders, such as regulatory authorities, government agencies, and environmental groups, have confrontational relationships with the organisation (Freeman, 1984). Stakeholder theory carries a dynamic and complex notion of interaction between an organisation and its vast surroundings (Gray et al., 2009; Gray et al., 1996), which mainly deals with how a corporation manages its stakeholders (Grey et al., 1997; Gray et al., 1995). Stakeholders are assumed to strongly influence a firm’s success as they own the assets (Maltby, 1997).

Empirical evidence suggests that the organisation that serves the stakeholders’ requirements performs better than its counterparts (Maltby, 1997; Ullmann, 1985). This theory involves looking after the whole stakeholder group, including some less influential groups, rather than focusing only on the shareholder, which is precisely the opposite of the organisation’s capitalist view (Alam, 2006; Kolk & Pinkse, 2006).

Stakeholders can be classified in several ways: internal and external (Freeman, 1984), or primary and secondary (Clarkson, 1995). However, Driscoll and Starik (2004) strongly advocated including the natural environment as an organisational stakeholder from a sustainability point of view. Among all stakeholder groups, some groups possess significant salience, importance, and power compared to others (Mitchell et al., 1997). Salience is defined ‘as the degree to which managers prioritise competing stakeholders’ claims’ that depend on power, legitimacy, and urgency. Dominant stakeholders receive higher priority from the

management, while management would embrace proactive or reactive environmental policy mainly depending on the dominant stakeholders' demands and expectations (Henriques & Sadosky, 1999).

Although stakeholder theory explains a large part of the motivation to disclose corporate sustainability performance and practice and release stakeholder pressure, it is still underdeveloped in sustainability literature, as many fundamental questions need to be answered. Only few studies have investigated stakeholders' influence on sustainability disclosure (Elijido-Ten, Kloot, & Clarkson, 2010). Among these empirical studies, Epstein and Freedman (1994) investigated the information needs of individual stockholders, de Villiers and Staden (2012) examined the stakeholder's attitude, while Deegan and Blomquist (2006), Elijido-Ten et al. (2010), O'Dwyer, Unerman, and Hession (2005), and Tilt (1994) investigated the non-financial information needs of investors. Tilt (1994) investigated the pressure group's perceptions and concluded that the social and environmental information reported was not adequate for their purpose.

2.5.2.2. Legitimacy theory

Legitimacy theory explains the general association between an organisation and its stakeholders (Gray et al., 1996; Spence et al., 2010). Corporate legitimacy is described as a generalised view that an entity's activities are necessary and appropriate within some social practices of norms, values, and beliefs (Suchman, 1995). Therefore, legitimacy is merely the acceptable behaviour of the corporate body endorsed by society (Suchman, 1995). Each corporate entity holds an automatically legitimate status within the value systems of the community. Discrepancies caused within these value systems generate a threat to the automatic taken-for-granted legitimacy (Woodward, Edwards, & Birkin, 1996), while they can adversely affect the economic and reputational outcome of the company (Deegan, 2002).

Legitimacy theory is consistent with Shocker and Sethi's (1973) social contract theory. Shocker and Sethi (1973) described a social contract as 'any social institution and business is no exception operates in a society via a social contract expressed or implied whether it's survival and growth are based on the delivery of some socially desirable ends to society in general and the distribution of economic, social, or political benefits to groups from which it derives its

power'. Guthrie and Parker (1989) explained that the availability of a social contract ensures a firm's consent to deliver social requirements for survival by approving its objectives. Therefore, failure to deliver social obligations may result in the withdrawal of the right to continue operations (Deegan and Rankin, 1997). Consequently, the customer could refuse to buy products, investors could offer a lower price for the share, and the regulator may impose penalties for non-compliance (Deegan, 2002).

Nowadays, society and its citizens are increasingly concerned about social and environmental issues; therefore, inappropriate activity or performance on these issues may cause a threat to a legitimate position (Bansal & Clelland, 2004; Branco, Eugenio, & Ribeiro, 2008). Brown and Deegan (1998) recommended organisational pro-activity to maintain corporate legitimacy smoothly.

According to Gray et al. (2009), the corporation uses sustainability disclosure as a management tool to communicate social, environmental, and governance activities incongruent with social value systems to bolster its position. Therefore, it is important to continuously develop the performance and elements of disclosure with the dynamism of changing societal expectations (Deegan and Gordon, 1996). Lindblom (1994) claimed that some firms use sustainability disclosure as a symbolic activity to gain legitimacy. Hooghiemstra (2000) claimed that sustainability disclosure is a corporate mechanism that positively changes stakeholder perception, where the actual reflection of organisational activities may not be presented. The organisation used more symbolic actions than changing its fundamental behaviour to gain and manage legitimacy (Buhr, 1998; Oliver, 1991).

Buhr (1998, p. 165) provided further evidence on the topic and claimed that the firm gains automatic legitimacy through its appearance to carry out suitable activities or not be involved in any wrongdoing within the social systems. The organisation used sustainability performance reporting to communicate and answer outside interests to maintain legitimacy. Therefore, legitimacy theory can explain why firms desire to disclose only positive information in their sustainability reporting. The literature also observed that organisations enhance the frequency or volume of positive reporting when involved in a negative incident or when legitimacy is threatened (Deegan et al., 2000; Patten, 1992). Branco et al. (2008) obtained further evidence

of using sustainability reporting for legitimacy when finding firms on media and public scrutiny for disputed environmental, social, and governance issues.

In the corporate sustainability literature, legitimacy theory has been referred to extensively, but some issues still need to be answered clearly. Deegan (2006) outlined some issues, such as social contracts, appropriate strategies to manage societal expectations, and organisational legitimacy. Tilling and Tilt (2009) identified another issue relating to the measurement of legitimacy or the ranking of an organisation based on legitimacy. According to them, legitimacy is an abstract concept that has tangible consequences; therefore, any measure of sustainability will be subjective. Tilling and Tilt (2009) described legitimacy as an organisation's essential resources to operate, and this concept is closely linked with a resource-based view. Ashforth and Gibbs (1990) and Tilling and Tilt (2009) identified four different phases of legitimacy: establishing legitimacy, maintaining legitimacy, extending legitimacy, and defending legitimacy, while previous studies mainly focused on defending legitimacy.

Elijido-Ten et al. (2010) claimed that stakeholder theory and legitimacy theory sometimes overlap and are treated as complementary, while the main differences lie in the level of resolution. Both theories focus on management perspectives; stakeholder theory illustrates the association between organisation and stakeholders, while legitimacy theory focuses on organisation and society. Therefore, society grants the legitimate right of the organisation to operate. Thus, legitimacy theory overlaps with stakeholder theory, as an organisation can only serve its stakeholders when society permits legitimacy (Elijido-Ten et al., 2010). When comparing stakeholder theory with legitimacy theory, legitimacy theory possesses a broader scope, and thus legitimacy theory possibly holds more expansive explanatory power of the current practice of sustainability performance.

2.5.3. Radical perspectives

Tilt (1994) explains the undelaying philosophy of the radical perspective. According to him, the social structure shapes all that goes on within it. Gray et al. (2009) classified radical theoretical perspectives as political economy, accountability, and media agenda-setting theories. The details of each theory are explained in the following sections.

2.5.3.1. Political economy theory

According to Tilt (1994), the political economy theory is the main theoretical perspective under the radical sustainability perspective. Gray et al. (1995) explained political economy theory as the economic factor that cannot be considered on its own without considering its political, social, and institutional context within its surroundings, while Tilt (1994, p.49) stated that the ‘structure of the society shapes all that goes on within it’. Political economy is defined as ‘the social, political, and economic framework within which human life takes place’ (Gray et al., 1996, p. 47).

Spence et al. (2010) claimed that accounting is a mechanism to bolster the interest of capital. The political economy theory acknowledges the wide range of information users and financial stakeholders while focusing on the conflicting interests of information users (Adams et al., 1995; Cooper & Sherer, 1984). Therefore, sustainability reporting is designed to supply information from the management side to explain stakeholder conflicts (Guthrie & Parker, 1989). Parker (2005) claimed that sustainability performance could create its own economic, social, and political environment by communicating its story and value and clarifying its position.

Gray et al. (1995) identified two main political economy classes: classical (Marxist) political economy and bourgeois political economy. A classical political economy involves structural conflict and inequality, while the role of the state stays at the centre of the analysis (Gray et al., 2009). In contrast, the bourgeois political economy focuses on the interaction among the group where more than one party is present, for example, the interaction between a corporation and an environmental pressure group (Gray et al., 2009). Therefore, the differences between the two ideologies are the level of resolution of analysis: bourgeois political economy in social accounting tends to legitimise a particular part of the system, such as business organisations. In contrast, the classical political economy tends to legitimise the systems themselves. Although there are some differences between them, Parker (2005, p.847) revealed: ‘classical economy theory and bourgeois political economy share a common recognition that accounting disclosure is an economic, social, and political mechanism to construct and sustain ideologies and relevant financial and institutional arrangement that helps the reporting organisation’s personal interest’.

Gray et al. (1996) explained the application of bourgeois political economy theory through the non-compliance of regulation or nondisclosure of sustainability information. Adams et al. (1995) revealed UK companies' non-reporting of equal opportunity while it was a legal requirement. They explained this corporate notion using political economy theory. The company was aware of the non-compliance of regulations, as adequate policies were not in place, while reporting non-compliance made them more vulnerable. Therefore, non-selective reporting is to ensure the firm's best interest, as Guthrie and Parker (1989, p.351) noted, 'management tends to tell its own story or refrain from doing so according to its self-interest'.

However, the current increasing trend in sustainability disclosure can be interpreted by classical political economy theory. For example, a corporation may be reporting more sustainability activities to satisfy that it is behaving according to the pressure group. Gray et al. (1996) describe this effort as satisfying social and environmental agendas to protect capital systems (Gray et al. 1996). Classical political economy theory can also interpret the government initiative as a mandatory requirement of sustainability information to legitimise capitalist systems (Gray et al., 1996). Several research pieces have been conducted on sustainability reporting based on political economy theory. Spence et al. (2010) pointed out some inconsistencies in the literature where the theory has not been applied appropriately, such as studies not making any differences between micro and macro levels of resolution. Spence et al. (2010) concluded that the theory needs to be clearly defined to ensure consistency in output using political economy theory within the field.

2.5.3.2. Theory of accountability

Accountability mainly relates to dual organisational duties (Gray et al., 1996). According to Williams (1987), accountability is an obligatory connection that evolves through the interaction of two parties, where one party is supposedly accountable for its activities to the counterparty. By using corporate sustainability performance, firms can satisfy their duty of accountability for their activities in society and the environment (Gray, 2006; Unerman & O'Dwyer, 2007). To ensure dual responsibilities, the organisation manages its resources and then, as a second responsibility, they provide an account to the stakeholder on how they manage their resources. According to Gray (2007), an organisation holds rights simultaneously, and they have the

responsibility to be accountable for financial, social, and ecological concerns. Organisations disclose financial reports as a part of accountability in financial affairs, which are primarily regulated while reporting sustainability information to account for their environmental and social commitment (Gray, 2007).

The right to information is the fundamental concept underlying reciprocal accountability of the organisation towards society (Gray, 2007), while the firm is responsible for supplying information to fulfil the accountability relationship. Sustainability disclosure relates to wider stakeholders, and each relationship has a separate form of right to information ranging from legal, quasi-legal, and moral (Gray, 2007). The legal requirements are mainly regulated by law. The organisation is bound to provide certain information; an example of a legal requirement is EU directive 2003/51, which mandates the provision of social and environmental data in the annual report. The legal requirement may also require the organisation to report health and safety reports to the authorities and report chemical release under the Toxic Release Inventory (TRI) in the US, while in the UK, a firm is required to report CO₂ emissions to the environment agency under the Integrated Pollution Prevention Inventory (IPPC). Government and regulatory bodies might sometimes have the legal right to information, while most aspects of sustainability disclosure remain unregulated (KPMG, 2015). As a result, relying on the legal requirement to confirm organisational accountability for sustainability aspects, particularly social and environmental, is insufficient.

The accountability relationship tends to be quasi-legal when an organisation voluntarily adopts responsibility (Gray, 2007). A quasi-legal responsibility example includes the United Nations Global Compact 2013, under which organisations may issue a special section in annual reports to clarify their position. In a quasi-legal relationship, the overall responsibility is based on the organisation's subscription (Gray et al. 1996).

Besides the legal and quasi-legal relationship, organisations hold the moral responsibility to supply information with limited regulation to account for organisational activities (Gray et al., 1996). When there is a lack of rigorous regulatory obligation, moral responsibility becomes inevitable to ensure the responsibility to account. Therefore, sustainability performance emerges as an effective mechanism to discharge accountability beyond the legally defined point of responsibility. The form of moral responsibility is not explicitly defined or described.

Gray et al. (1996) distinguished two forms of ethical responsibilities: absolute, which does not change with place and time, and relative, which changes with time and place. Therefore, moral responsibility is difficult to define at once, and it may evolve and alter with time.

2.5.3.3. Media agenda-setting and sustainability reporting

Media agenda-setting theory is part of political economy theory, which mainly links legitimacy and current sustainability practices followed by a specific incident to defend legitimacy (Islam & Deegan, 2010). Media agenda perception assumes that the media is a strong stakeholder that has a significant influence on public and social agendas; thus, any issue that is vital to the media is also important to the public and society (Tilling & Tilt, 2009). Organisations tackle media scrutiny through incremental good behaviour and more frequent positive disclosure to manage adverse news reporting (Deegan et al., 2000; Islam & Deegan, 2010).

Previous research on sustainability disclosure has been conducted based on media agenda-setting and legitimacy theory. Deegan et al. (2000) examined five significant incidents in the oil production, underground mining, and chemical industries that had significantly impacted Australia's environmental and social parameters. They examined changes in the content of the annual and sustainability reports. Any further reports contain such information and report that organisations in the affected industries disclose more detailed information and positive information related to the incident than before.

Islam and Deegan (2010) studied the sustainability disclosure of two international sports giants for media attention relating to substandard working conditions and the use of child labour in third-world countries. They found a positive correlation between negative media reports of working environments and the employment of child labour, with detailed positive disclosure in annual and sustainability disclosure. In the same study, Deegan et al. (2000) noted that one among the five cases received less media attention; thus, their performance and report content seemed to have no significant change following the incident. Therefore, media agenda-setting theory explains how media pressure can shape the practice and behaviour of corporate sustainability and the public agenda, while also telling us how organisations react to a negative media report.

2.6. Conceptual framework and hypothesis development

2.6.1. Development of the conceptual framework

Scholars rarely dispute the roles that corporations need to play in society. However, there is considerable disagreement about whether socially responsible corporate behaviour stands against the widely accepted conventional business objectives of value maximisation for the shareholder. Some of the earlier researchers, such as Ameer and Othman (2012), Barnett and Salomon (2011), and Reddy and Gordon (2010), have analysed the role of CSR activities on corporate financial performance.

In contrast, several studies, such as Al-Kassar and Al-Nidawiy (2014), Deegan (2004), and Uwuigbe (2013), investigated the role of CSR disclosure on the firm's value and potential investors' behaviours. In particular, few previous studies purely focused on whether superior sustainable behaviour and disclosures generated any capital market benefits for the corporation, including increasing share price (e.g., Al-Kassar and Al-Nidawiy, 2014), reducing capital cost (e.g., Ahmed et al., 2019), reducing information asymmetry (e.g., Martínez-Ferrero et al., 2016), and reducing risk profile (e.g., Cai et al., 2016). These capital market benefits result from a firm's increasing value in both the short and long terms.

The existing literature reported a positive relationship between CSR activities and stock market return measured by the market value of the stock, book value of the stock, and market-to-book value ratio (Anderson & Frankle, 1980; Freedman & Stagliano, 1991; Klassen & McLaughlin, 1996; Caroline, 2013). That tends to continue in the future, making a positive impression on potential investors. Sustainable performance generates other benefits, including higher employee productivity, increased employee retention ratio, superior brand value, increased corporate reputation, and enlarged regulatory support (Malik, 2014). Therefore, better sustainable behaviour and disclosure produce increased stock value in the short and long run (Waddock & Graves, 1997; Luo & Bhattacharya, 2009; Eccles et al., 2013).

Some earlier research has examined the effect of CSR and subsequent reports on investors' decision making (Belkaoui, 1980; Chan & Milne, 1999; Wang et al., 2011). Smith et al. (2010) reported a mixed investor reaction while claiming investors' decisions differ across countries. On the other hand, Dijken (2007) claimed that not all CSR activities improve the stock market return. Still, only value-driven activities can enhance stock market returns (Dijken, 2007).

Li et al. (2018) presented five arguments for how a firm's value could be enhanced due to better sustainability performance. First, a firm's ESG information is classed as non-financial information in addition to the financial data derived from the financial statements. There has been increasing demand for non-financial information among investors over the past few decades. Because of the declining trend of valuing market capitalisation based on tangible assets, investors equally value non-financial and non-balance sheet items. Eccles et al. (2011) reported that the contribution of tangible assets to a firm's market valuation dropped from 82% to 19% between 1975 and 2009. ESG performance is an excellent source of the firm's internal information, such as manufacturing technology, type of raw material used in the manufacturing process, employee satisfaction, firm's association with regulators and society, overall governance systems, and long-term strategies (Duuren et al., 2016). Therefore, this diversified non-financial information offers further attributes above the balance sheet approach, which carries additional price informativeness (Goldstein & Yang, 2015).

Second, strong ESG performance results from strong internal management systems that tend to learn from the market. According to Chen et al. (2006), managers improve their knowledge of their stock prices over time from the stock market and apply this expertise to investment decisions. Therefore, strong ESG practice creates an improved knowledge base, which could further encourage the manager to bring greater transparency on governance, internal control, compliance with guidelines, and delivery of great stakeholder interest (Cheng et al. 2014). Improved ESG performance helps firms develop better B2B relationships with suppliers and other business stakeholders (Dhaliwal et al., 2011). Thus, ESG practice and performance enhance a firm's value in the medium to long term.

Third, ESG performance and reporting effectively reduce information asymmetry between a firm's internal and external information. Strong ESG performance and disclosure can reduce the information gap between the inside and outside. Therefore, strong sustainability performance leads to better association with communities, employees, regulators, and customers, leading to more robust operating performance and productivity through customer loyalty, better staff behaviour, attractive investment opportunities and better access to funding and finance.

Cheng et al. (2012) reported that firms could access finance better if they have better sustainability performance and subsequent communication through reporting. Superior sustainability performance reduces operational, legal, technological, and environmental risks and improves risk management systems that eventually increase the firm's value.

Fourth, ESG sustainability performance increases the brand visibility of an entity regarding its environmental, social and governance aspects. Investors' awareness of corporate operational activities has grown gradually over the years (Zhou et al., 2013). Investors consider corporate sustainability performance incrementally as a key performance indicator for evaluating overall business success (Kaspereit & Lopatta, 2016). Although financial considerations play a pivotal part in decision making in socially responsible investment, there is a broader emphasis on investment decisions based on ethical, social, and environmental standards (Consolandi et al., 2009). Durren et al. (2016) claimed that the socially responsible investment fund manager and the conventional fund manager also consider ESG sustainability performance when making an investment decision. Therefore, higher sustainability practices contribute to better risk assessment and more precise investment decisions.

Finally, ESG disclosure ensures greater transparency and better stakeholder engagement, leading to lower agency costs. Increased sustainability performance signals positive management performance and governance systems. Better sustainability disclosure relates to improved stakeholder engagement, which can reduce the chance of making inappropriate decisions. Frequent and timely communication of sustainability attributes can minimise the information asymmetry between insiders and outsiders; therefore, it can reduce managers' tendency to aggressive earning management, short-termism, and insider trading (Zo & Kim, 2007), which enables the firm to boost value in the long term.

Additionally, based on signalling theory, strong sustainability performance provides an effective indication to investors and shareholders regarding environmental, social, and governance strategies. The operational and environmental risks are also minimised by environmental policies. When a firm adopts ESG sustainability reporting guidelines, frameworks, and standards, it enhances the firm's credibility with potential investors (Michealon et al., 2015).

Therefore, investors and shareholders get a clear indication of management's efficiency and the long-term view of top management. As a result of these positive signals from the firm, the share is more attractive, and investors are willing to prioritise ESG firms compared to other firms. These stock market priorities, which attract more capital investment, offer additional value in the long term (Spanos, 2005).

The conceptual framework (Figure 5) addresses the gaps identified in Section 1.3 based on currently available literature and existing theories. The conceptual framework expects direct relationships between the share price and corporate environmental, social, and governance sustainability elements. On the other hand, firm size, sustainability reputation, environmentally sensitive industrial background, and age of stock market listing play moderating roles that affect the existing relationship between sustainability and share price. The relationship between share price and corporate sustainability performance requires several theoretical explanations, including agency theory, decision usefulness theory, and signalling theory. However, the whole conceptual model is developed based on the efficient market hypothesis, which claims that share price reflects all available information.

Figure 5: Conceptual framework.

2.6.2. Development of hypotheses

H1: Value relevance of sustainability performance

Sustainability is now regarded as one of the crucial implicit principles of management thinking. Therefore, management must rationally identify the balance between the expected benefit and the expected cost of being more sustainable. Management needs to identify an equilibrium where the marginal benefits of increasing sustainability are equal to the marginal cost of sustainability. Lundgren (2011, p.74) pointed out three potential benefits and three potential costs involved with increasing corporate sustainability based on the work of Gray and

Shadbegian (1998), Blend and Van Ravenswaay (1999), Heinkel et al. (2001), Bolvig (2005), Godfrey (2005), Heal (2008), and Wang (2008). According to Lundgren (2011), the consumer pays a premium price as a reward for being more sustainable, which results in increased revenue and profit. From the employees' point of view, they feel a warm glow when working in a firm that has the reputation of being sustainable. The last benefit Lundgren (2011) pointed out is that increasing sustainability reduces capital costs by being less risky to the bank and other portfolio managers. On the other hand, the cost of sustainability involves an investment in a sustainability project, the cost of promoting sustainability, and the cost of crowding-out effects, which relates to the opportunity cost related to the investment, which cannot recover sustainability restriction.

Value creation through corporate sustainability depends on the business strategy to utilise competitive advantages relating to the firm's sustainability over its competitors. Therefore, the potential gain is subject to the current state of applying corporate sustainability to the industry. In a given industry, if the competitor complies heavily with sustainability guidelines beyond legal bindings while there is a point where the related cost exceeds the benefit, the decision not to make any further investment in sustainability may increase the firm's value. On the other hand, if a competitor has not yet utilised the full benefit of sustainability, industry leadership in sustainability can offer extensive positive outcomes regarding profitability, cost of capital, and shareholders' value. To test this relationship, this study formulated the following hypothesis:

H1: Corporate ESG (environmental, social, and governance) sustainability performance is significantly associated with share price, as sustainability performance carries value-relevant information for the investors.

H2: Environmental performance

According to Hussainey and Salama (2010), the corporate environmental performance makes investors more confident and less uncertain about predicting a firm's future earnings by analysing the relationship between environmental performance and earnings on the share price. According to them, higher environmental reporting is associated with a stock price that is more informative for future earnings. They claim that a higher environmental reputation enhances

the capability of the market to predict future earning changes, improve stakeholder relationships, reduce the cost of conflict, enhance the reputation and increase employee productivity, providing more relevant information to the investors. To test this claim and assess the value relevance of higher environmental performance, this study formulated the following hypothesis:

H2: Corporate environmental performance is significantly associated with share price, as environmental performance provides value-relevant information for investors.

H3: Social performance

According to Fombrun et al. (2000), a firm's social engagement can produce many benefits because of its responsible activities. Social engagement can help the firm develop strong community ties and be more socially integrated while building up the firm's reputation. Thus, social engagement can offer more favourable negotiation with suppliers and regulators, earn customer loyalty, and allow the firm to charge premium prices to reduce the cost of capital (Garcia-Castro et al., 2010). Social performance can also generate competitive advantages while mitigating the risk of reputational losses and enhancing investor confidence. To test this claim and assess the value relevance of a higher level of social performance, this study formulates the following hypothesis:

H3: Corporate social performance is significantly associated with share price, as social performance provides value-relevant information for the investor.

H4: Governance performance

Voluntary disclosure on environmental, social, and economic matters enhances transparency and facilitates more precise future earnings estimates. Sustainability disclosure can also indirectly affect stock prices by influencing the relevance of the primary accounting variable, as this disclosure offers further and complementary information. Sustainability performance contains information regarding the firm's future commitment and policy, together with past and present activities. As a result, sustainability reports imply different selections of financial

and other resources for future projects, policies, and initiatives. However, this sort of forward-looking information is generally not contained in the traditional financial statement; it can explain the importance of complementary information communicated by sustainability reports. Therefore, this study expects higher governance performance associated with a higher share price. Thus, this study formulated the following hypothesis:

H4: Corporate governance performance is significantly associated with share price, as governance performance provides value-relevant information for the investor.

H5: Firm size

Firm size is an important determinant of corporate sustainability (Kuzey & Uyar, 2017). Large firms are always under more public scrutiny (Lourenço & Branco, 2013; Kansal et al., 2014); therefore, they require more legitimacy (Kolk & Perego, 2010), while at the same time, they hold a higher amount of resources (Liu & Anbumozhi, 2009). Most prior studies referred to legitimacy theory (Kolk & Perego, 2010) to investigate firm size and sustainability. This study assumes that firm size is associated with share price based on the same theoretical ground. Thus, this study formulates the following hypothesis:

H5: Firm size significantly affects the sustainability–share price relationship, as firm size provides value-relevant information for the investor.

H6: Sustainability reputation

A firm's reputation is viewed as one of the most effective intangible resources that bring competitive advantages ahead of competitors (Robert & Dowling, 2002). A higher sustainability reputation helps the firm improve and maintain its relationship with external stakeholders, including customers, investors, banks, suppliers, and regulators. Schnitz and Epstein (2005, p. 329) claimed that sustainability reputation 'may facilitate complex, long-term stakeholder management which, in turn, ought to enhance the firm's ability to outperform its competitors, either by increasing revenue or by reducing expenses'. Sustainably reputed firms enjoy a lower cost of contracts with stakeholders, including the government, suppliers, social

representatives, unions, lenders, and customers (Liston-Hayes & Ceton, 2009). This study assumes the valuation for the sustainability reputation will be higher compared to the firm without a sustainability reputation. Under the signalling theory, firms included in the FTSE4Good Index (used as a proxy for the higher reputation of sustainable firms) will be tested to determine whether sustainability reputation provides any stock market benefit. Therefore, this study formulated the following hypotheses:

H6A: A large firm with a higher sustainability reputation is associated with a higher share price than a large firm with a lower sustainability performance.

H6B: The market undervalues the large firm with a lower sustainability performance when compared to the small firm with a lower sustainability performance.

H7: Industrial background

The industrial background has a long-standing relationship with corporate sustainability practices (Skouloudis et al., 2014). The sustainability practice of industrially sensitive firms can be discussed under the legitimacy theory (Legendre and Coderre, 2013; Burgwal and Vieira, 2014; Braam et al., 2016). Environmentally sensitive industries are likely to harm the planet more, and they are more likely to face strict regulations (Liu and Anbumozhi, 2009). At the same time, an environmentally sensitive firm must compensate for the environmental damage caused (Skouloudis et al., 2014). Some large firms have very high carbon footprints while having considerable environmental recovery budgets. These firms are likely to have more operational and environmental risks, for which the investors are likely to ask for additional risk premiums for their investment.

Therefore, it is essential to investigate the stock market response regarding the firms' environmental damage recovery performance. Thus, to determine whether operating in environmentally sensitive industries has any stock market implications, this study formulates the following hypotheses:

H7A: The market undervalues firms that operate in high-impact industries compared to firms in other industries.

H7B: The stock market undervalues firms with no sustainability reputation more severely than those with a sustainability reputation when both firms operate in environmentally sensitive industries.

H8: Age of Stock Market Listing of firms

Age is an essential determinant when picking shares (Borghesi et al., 2014). Borghesi et al. (2014) also claimed that comparatively young companies and young CEOs are more likely to invest in CSR and altruistic reasons. They also claimed that CSR spending may be driven by altruistic purposes and as part of a wider strategy to develop goodwill and legitimacy. Saeidi et al. (2015) claimed that age is a potential moderator of sustainability performance. Similar to Pelozo (2006), they claim that firms require a minimum level of assurance to invest in sustainability practices.

As sustainability practices affect the valuation process, young firms take a more integrated approach to ESG performance and financial performance, while some old firms are more reactive to ESG issues (Yang & Baasandorj, 2017). Therefore, this study sought to identify the impact of the age of stock market listings on the valuation process. Thus, to confirm whether the age of stock market listing has any association with the stock price, this study formulates the following hypothesis:

H8A: The firm's age of stock market listing is significantly associated with share price, as the firm's age provides value-relevant information for the investor.

H8B: The market share price is higher for young firms with a better sustainability reputation than other firms.

2.7. Summary

Considering the primary aim, this study extensively reviews the role of corporate sustainability in share price and firm value. This chapter carefully reviewed the existing literature relating to corporate environmental, social, and governance sustainability, as many similar terms are used in the literature to denote corporate sustainability. This study adopted multi-theoretical references following Gray et al. (2009), including stakeholder theory, agency theory, decision usefulness theory, legitimacy theory, and signalling theory. Using these theoretical references, a conceptual framework has been developed while formulating 11 hypotheses covering eight broad sustainability areas to assess the value relevance of corporate sustainability.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

3.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to choose the appropriate philosophical and methodological stance to collect and analyse the data. This chapter discusses the available methodological choices in designing the research and justifies the selected alternatives. This chapter describes the data sample and regression models. Finally, this chapter also discusses ethical issues when conducting this study and the limitations of the research methods.

3.2. Philosophical background

This research study involves social accounting projects (Gray, 2002) among the various schools of thought. Social accounting projects can be defined as forms of accounting that evolve based on the principles of democracy and accountability (Gray, 2002). This form of accounting brings to light a separate route that goes beyond the scope of financial or economic accounting (Gray, 2002). In practice, social accounting appears under various names, such as social responsibility accounting, social audit, corporate social reporting, environmental reporting, sustainability reporting, and stakeholder dialogue reporting (Gray, 2002). However, social accounting is not part of conventional accounting, while still struggling to find a place in the accounting literature where it should be addressed and analysed.

The social accounting project emphasises introducing and implementing accounting practices to reduce social inequalities (Gray, 2002). Thus, social accounting research argues against the role of current accounting while developing a new form of accounting practices, including a voluntary, regulatory, and protest-driven approach that empowers civil society (Gray, 2002). This study is a form of social accounting research exploring corporate sustainability practices in the UK. Corporate sustainability practices and performance are considered voluntary instruments that force firms to answer their stakeholders for any action that affects their lives (O'Dwyer, 2005).

Blaikie (2007) outlined a systematic procedure that involved developing new knowledge, philosophies, and theoretical ideas in social inquiries and described what constitutes social reality. Gill and Johnson (2010, p.24) described the philosophical strands as ‘philosophical commitment which is inevitably made in undertaking research always entails a commitment to the various knowledge-constituting assumptions about the nature of truth, human behaviour, representation, and accessibility of social reality’. Gill and Johnson (2010) also argued that the researcher’s philosophical position relating to ontology, epistemology, and axiology affects the methodological choices ultimately chosen to answer the research questions. Therefore, it is essential to outline the philosophical assumptions made when undertaking a particular research project.

3.3. The philosophical assumption underpinning this study

Research philosophy constitutes a set of beliefs and assumptions related to the research topics that define and identify the means of identifying, collecting, and analysing data (Brayman, 2012). However, selecting the appropriate philosophy is not automatic, but depends on the aim and objectives of the study (Goddard & Melville, 2004). The characteristics of the data set to be investigated in the research project are also primary variables for determining the appropriate philosophy (May, 2011). Usually, the philosophical stance of research offers validation and justification for the methodology used to reach the aims and objectives of the research work. There are no good or bad philosophies regarding merit, benefits, and characteristics; therefore, any particular research philosophy used would be based on its inherent benefits (Podsakoff et al., 2012). The researcher’s position on ontology, epistemology, and axiology has been stated in the following sections.

3.3.1. Ontological assumption

Ontology is a philosophical assumption that involves the reality of nature on what exists (Blaikie, 2007). However, the notion of reality is a complex phenomenon, as both objectivists and subjectivists possess two opposing views. The theory of subjectivism assumes that reality has no independent existence, but a figment of human imagination. According to Bryman

(2001), subjectivism (also called social constructivism, constructivism, or interpretivism) is an alternative ontological position where the meaning of social phenomena continuously changes with social interaction. Nothing is definitive regarding the researcher's position, as his position changes with circumstances where truth survives for a particular moment. Corporate entities are created by humans as a social organisation, while organisational culture is part of the entity that affects behaviours. However, the culture grows and evolves with organisational growth.

On the other hand, objectivism theory believes that reality has an independent existence in human observation. Bryman (2001) claimed that an organisation is a separate entity with its rules, regulations, human resources, procedures, hierarchy, and mission statement. Bryman (2001) also argued that a social organisation has its reality external to those within it and represents a social order. Therefore, objectivism relies on the thought that a social phenomenon is independent of social actors.

3.3.2. Epistemological assumption

Epistemology is a theory of knowledge concerned with the nature of knowledge and the way of knowing and learning about social reality. Alternatively, it can be defined as the study of criteria classified into what does and what does not constitute knowledge (Hallebone & Priest, 2009). There are two main perspectives of epistemology: positivism and interpretivism. Burrell and Morgan (1979, p. 5) defined positivism as 'epistemologies which seek to explain and predict what happens in the social world by searching for regularities and causal relationship between its constituent elements'. Subjective opinion is not considered here, as this philosophy usually deals with verifiable observation measurement of the relationship between those observations. Therefore, it is merely a more scientific research perspective, as there is no scope for inserting subjective opinions.

On the other hand, interpretivism opposes absolute facts while suggesting that the facts are individual perceptions rather than objective truths. According to Burrell and Morgan (1979, p. 5), this social reality is fundamentally relative; therefore, only the individual involved with the activities can understand the actual reality.

Thus, the conclusion is driven by the participant's interpretation; consequently, it is challenging to understand the meaning of individual interpretation. Research following this philosophy requires adequate subjective and specialist knowledge to realise the meaning and context of the subject.

3.3.3. Axiological assumption

Axiology is a branch of research philosophy that judges value (Hallebone & Priest, 2009). In simple terms, axiology relates to evaluating researchers' roles and personal values throughout the study (Wahyuni, 2012). Scholars (e.g., Heron, 1996; Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2009) argued that researchers' evaluation and judgement were affected by the researchers' value in the research process. Heron (1996) claimed that personal values are fundamentally non-negotiable and can affect the explanation of any event.

The researcher's value also affects the interpretation of the research results. Therefore, the contradiction caused by individual values cannot be debated. The researcher needs to be value free (Popper, 2018). According to Abdullah (2011), two available views are associated with science and value. The first view is that science is free from the value that complies with positivist ideology. The research study must be carried out free of values, while the researcher must be independent throughout the research and maintain objectivity (Nugrahanti, 2018). The second view is called the critical view, which assumes that science is not value free. Value-free science harms the survival of science and humans (Guba & Lincoln, 2005).

This research study investigates the value relevance of the sustainability performance of UK-listed firms. Therefore, in this study, firms are the social entity, while all stakeholders are part of the social actors. This study assumes that there is a fundamental truth that stays outside the social actor. Whether sustainability performance is value-relevant or not has an absolute answer, but has not yet been discovered. The research outcome relies solely on independent and external information related to individual perception. Therefore, this study assumes the objectivist philosophy as an ontological position, while positivist philosophy is an epistemological stance to identify observable relationships. The researcher's values can play an essential role in the research, particularly in interpreting results. This study is solely

quantitative and follows a positivist research philosophy with clear research objectives. The hypotheses will be tested based on the regression analysis; therefore, the researcher value would unlikely interfere with the research result, while the interpretation will be based on the hypothesis results.

3.4. Research design

Identifying the appropriate methodological position plays an essential role in the validity and reliability of the research outcomes. Generally, the research design is an extensive predetermined research plan that will guide the whole research process (Wilson, 2014). Research design includes research objectives, sampling, data collection, data transformation, data analysis techniques, and related research ethics to deal with (Saunders et al., 2016). Sekaran and Bougie (2016) describe research design as a blueprint for collecting, measuring, and analysing research data to answer the research questions. The methodological choices of this research design, including research approach, method, strategy, sample, and data analysis, are discussed in the following sections.

3.4.1. Research approach

Researchers classify the research approach broadly into two types: deductive and inductive (Hussey & Hussey, 1997; Perry, 2000; Cavaye, 1996). The deductive approach follows general to specific (Kothari, 2004), which deals with studies relating to conceptual and theoretical structures (Hussey & Hussey, 1997). According to Hussey and Hussey (1997), in the deductive approach, conceptual and theoretical structure development will be based on empirical observation, leading through the deduction of a specific observation from the general likelihood. The literature suggests that the deductive approach applies to examine issues under an established theory while predominantly following quantitative methods for data collection (Hussey & Hussey, 1997).

The literature suggests that an inductive research approach generally follows qualitative research methods (Ali & Birley, 1999). On the other hand, the inductive research approach is a research study that helps formulate a theory based on the observed empirical results (Hussey & Hussey, 1997). According to Kothari (2004), the inductive research approach follows developing theory based on the specific observed results that generalise the view.

The deductive approach has advantages, as it allows testing the previous research outcome, which may suffer from some limitations. The deductive research approach facilitates enlarging the scope of knowledge by setting up new hypotheses and measuring the relationships between the variables. The inductive research approach can help us understand how human beings describe and interpret their social existence and generalise undiscovered knowledge (Saunders et al., 2009).

3.4.2 Research methods

In social science research, two types of research methods are used: qualitative and quantitative. Some researchers use another form of research method: the mixed method, which is a combination of both qualitative and quantitative methods (Williams, 2007). Selecting the appropriate research method is one of the fundamental responsibilities that researchers need to perform. The appropriate method will be selected based on the research questions (Carter & Little, 2007) and objectives (Marshall, 1996).

Generally, quantitative research methods deal with quantitative data to generate statistical information that predicts, confirms, generates, validates, or develops findings and theories (Cresswell et al., 2003; Leedy & Ormrod, 2001). Qualitative research develops hypotheses and data analyses based on the research questions and objectives (Williams, 2007). The quantitative research method enables the researcher to interpret the findings and develop new knowledge on the topics using a statistical approach as part of the research design (Williams, 2007). Quantitative research can vary in nature, such as experimental research, correlational research, and survey research (Saunders et al., 2009).

The researcher often suggests using a mixed research method to understand the complexity of the subject matter while developing measurable variables to achieve objectivity and predictability (Cresswell et al., 2003). However, Greene and Caracelli (1997) warned against using mixed methods, as this is neither an automatic choice, nor is it good science to mix them. They also argued that the mixed method's effectiveness would predominantly depend on how and what is being mixed. If the researcher fails to comprehend this, the mixed method will yield nothing but keeping the qualitative and quantitative next to each other without attaining the objective of mixing.

This research investigates the value relevance of ESG sustainability performance on the market share price. This investigation interacts with variables such as the market value of the share, the book value of the share, the earnings per share, the environmental, social, and governance performance, the industrial background, the firm's sustainability reputation, and the age of the stock market listing, which are predominantly quantitative in nature. This investigation aims to ascertain the cause-and-effect relationship between dependent and independent variables through regression tests. Therefore, this study employed deductive and quantitative research methods to investigate the relationships among the variables.

3.5. Research data, sample size and selection

The sample is representative data that is analysed from the research population. This study focused on the statistical association between the market value of shares and corporate sustainability performance. Because of the quantitative nature of the study, it is important to determine the correct sample size to obtain reliable findings. This study used multiple regression analysis. The general rule of thumb for the minimum number of observations in regression analysis is no fewer than 50 (Wilson et al., 2007). This number will increase with an increasing number of independent variables.

Harris (1985) suggested two ways of determining the number of participants based on the predictor variables. One way is that the number of participants should exceed the number of predictor variables by at least 50 for five or fewer predictor variables. However, if the predictor variables are six or more, he suggested at least ten participants per predictor variable. Green

(1991) suggested a similar formula to determine sample size: $N > 50 + 8M$ (M is the number of independent variables) or $N > 104 + M$ (M is the number of independent variables).

To ensure the robustness of this research outcome, this study collected a sample of 1,210 companies between 2017 and 2020. Before commencing data collection, this study had to consider the sampling frame. Between 2017 and 2020, the total number of registered companies was 8,302, which consists of 2,035 registered companies in 2017, 2,170 registered companies in 2018, 2,106 registered companies in 2019, and 1,991 registered companies in 2020. All of the data collected are for the period between 2017 and 2020. This study used simple random sampling from companies listed on the London Stock Exchange (LSE). Therefore, the inclusion criteria are that the firm must be listed on the London Stock Exchange before 2017 or between 2017 and 2020. This study excluded those firms whose financial and sustainability data were missing or unavailable. This study also excluded all aim-listed companies.

This study collected cross-sectional data, as the panel data for all the sample companies were unavailable. For example, for each company, this study required ten different pieces of data such as the market value of a share, book value of a share, earnings per share, ESG score, environmental sustainability score, social sustainability score, governance sustainability score, market capitalisation, specific industry background, age of stock market listing, etc. For four-year panel data, 40 variables are required for one company, and missing one variable makes the remaining collected data irrelevant. Because of this limitation, this study collected cross-sectional data. The breakdown of the sample data is as follows:

Figure 6: Breakdown of sample based on FTSE constituent.

Figure 7: Breakdown of sample based on FTSE4Good membership.

The sample of 1,210 consists of 302 FTSE100 companies, 321 FTSE250 companies, and 587 companies classed as Small-cap. Although FTSE has index series of FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies called FTSE350, this study considers both index series separately, as noticeable differences exist in relation to size and sustainability practices between the FTSE100 sample group and the FTSE250 sample group.

Additionally, this study classified all the 1,210 companies per year into FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies. FTSE4Good companies in this sample were constituents of the FTSE4Good Index from 2017 to 2020. Out of the 1,210 companies, 478 companies were reported as FTSE4Good companies and 732 as non-FTSE4Good companies. On the other hand, NonFTSE4Good firms were never included in the FTSE4Good Index between 2017 and 2020. This study did not select the sample based on the FTSE4Good status but classified the data as FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good once all the data collection was complete.

3.5.1. Financial and other non-financial data

This study considered three financial variables to perform a regression analysis. These financial variables are the market value of the share, the book value of the share, and earnings per share. These data are available in many recognised financial databases. However, this study collected these data from the London Stock Exchange database. Other financial and non-financial information also requires the regression test, such as industrial background, total market capitalisation, and age of stock market listing. These data were also collected from the London Stock Exchange database.

3.5.2. Corporate sustainability data

This study required a sustainability performance score for each sample firm. This sustainability performance includes the ESG sustainability performance score, environmental sustainability performance score, social sustainability performance score, and governance sustainability performance score. All these sustainability performance scores were collected from the Thompson Reuters Refinitiv database. Before commencing data collection, this study considered other data sources for sustainability information, such as Bloomberg, Thompson Reuters and the FTSE Russell Group. One of the most significant limitations to overcome in collecting data is accessing the data sources, as Bloomberg is not a public domain. At the same time, the FTSE Russell Group requires an extended lead time to get the information from them.

However, the FTSE Russell Group only provides the ESG sustainability performance scores, not the individual environmental, social and governance scores. Therefore, corporate sustainability data were collected from the Thompson Reuters Refinitiv database.

Thompson Reuters formerly owned Refinitiv as part of its financial and risk business. It provides an extensive collection of the company's global ESG information, covering over 80% of the worldwide market capitalisation of over 630 individual ESG metrics. Refinitiv evaluates a company's sustainability performance based on the company's reported information. It evaluates ESG sustainability in each of three distinct sustainability pillars, environmental, social, and governance performance, focusing on ten dominant themes. These themes include emissions, environmental product innovation, human rights, corporate social behaviour, etc. Refinitiv also offers a combined ESG performance score, which is a discounted score evaluated based on the sustainability controversies that affect the firm. In the Refinitiv database, more than 12,000 public and private companies' sustainability data are available globally starting from 2002.

Refinitiv's ESG sustainability performance score is determined based on environmental and social sustainability, industry performance, and the country of origin for governance performance. The key performance indicators of the ESG sustainability score are as follows:

1. Unique ESG magnitude – Each ESG sustainability metric is evaluated on a scale from 0 to 10 for each industry. However, the magnitude of weighting can differ from industry to industry.
2. Transparency stimulation – A firm's sustainability disclosure is key to determining the sustainability performance score. The omission of material information negatively affects the sustainability performance score, while the nondisclosure of immaterial information may not affect the sustainability performance score.
3. ESG controversies overlay – Refinitiv verifies the firm's commitment and course of action over time. A firm's lack of action to fulfil commitment can significantly affect the ESG sustainability performance score. Refinitiv addresses the market cap bias by introducing severity weight, where controversies are adjusted with sustainability score.
4. Industry and country benchmark – Refinitiv's sustainability scores are calculated based on sector benchmarks and country benchmarks within the peer group.

- Percentile rank scoring methodology – Refinitiv’s sustainability score produces an ESG sustainability score on a scale between 0 and 100 scale for environmental, social, and governance sustainability scores, ESG score and combined sustainability score. There is no hidden layer in the calculation.

Figure 8: ESG Scoring mechanism – broad categories.

Refinitiv regularly updates its ESG sustainability database. This regular update could include the inclusion of a new company in the database, the publication of new financial reports, or any controversial events. However, ESG sustainability reports are changed once a year in accordance with the firm’s sustainability reports. However, in most exceptional cases, such as changes in sustainability reports or the company’s structure, Refinitiv updates the database.

Refinitiv’s ESG scores are considered definitive, except for the last five financial years. Thus, any ESG score before the last five financial years will remain unchanged. The ESG score can be changed in the last five financial years if the sustainability reports have undergone any changes or restatements.

Refinitiv’s sustainability scoring methodology maintains some key principles, such as transparency. Combined ESG scores are discounted forms of ESG scores after considering all news controversies affecting firms.

Refinitiv encapsulates over 630 company-level ESG metrics to calculate sustainability scores. Of these, 186 metrics are most relevant for each industry and play a pivotal part in assessing overall sustainability scoring systems. All these metrics are grouped into ten categories under environmental, social and governance sustainability. The final ESG score is the summary of the environmental, social, and governance pillars score derived from 630 sustainability metrics of ten ESG categories based on sustainability performance, commitment, and effectiveness. The overall ESG score is the sum of ten category scores, which eventually vary from industry to industry in relation to environmental and social sustainability pillars. At the same time, the category weight for governance sustainability stays constant for all industry types.

Category definitions are available in [Appendix F](#).

Figure 9: ESG scoring mechanism – scoring metrics distribution.

On the other hand, the combined ESG (ESGC) score is weighted by the ESG score and ESG controversies. The rationale for ESGC is to reflect a firm’s true sustainability performance after considering all negative media news. Any contemporary negative media news reflects on the very recent sustainability performance. Despite no controversies, the ESG and ESGC scores remained the same. Controversies are comprised primarily of 23 broad areas of ESG sustainability.

The ESGC score can be affected in the following year if the controversies have longer impacts or there is a new development of the topics such as lawsuits, fines, etc. The firm will be penalised for any related controversies with reduced ESGC scores and grading.

In addition to the sustainability performance score, this research also used the FTSE4Good Index listed firm to categorise the firm with a high sustainability reputation acknowledged by an independent assessor. Therefore, FTSE4Good Index membership is used as a proxy for sustainability reputation. FTSE4Good indexes are highly regarded sustainability indices that report a firm's sustainability performance worldwide. The FTSE4Good Index generally includes firms that perform exceptionally well, and better than other firms in several sustainability criteria. The sustainability criteria cover areas such as corporate governance, risk management, mitigation of climate changes, supply chain standards, labour market practice, and other industry-specific criteria, along with financial information. FTSE4Good sustainability information is evaluated and managed by the London Stock Exchange Group.

Additionally, the FTSE4Good Index updates its selection criteria. At the same time, the firm must continuously improve its sustainability performance and its long-term plan related to sustainability to stay on the index. The details of the FTSE4Good Index are stated below.

FTSE4Good Index series

The FTSE4Good Index is a leading sustainability index used as a sustainability benchmark around the world. The FTSE Russell Group introduced the FTSE4Good Index in 2001, and since then, it has encouraged firms to make positive changes regarding their environmental, social, and governance issues. The FTSE4Good Index assessed and evaluated the firms' sustainability behaviours based on 14 ESG themes. Their performance on these 14 ESG criteria determines whether these firms are to be included in the index series. ESG sustainability ratings are determined based on existing public data administered by an independent external expert group. FTSE Russell's ESG rating comprises 7,200 companies from 47 countries.

The ESG rating comprises three sustainability pillars, environmental, social, and governance, under which there are 14 themes built on over 300 distinct indicators used to assess each individual company's risk exposure.

Figure 10: FTSE4Good ESG rating score measurement.

Index Construction Process

The FTSE4Good Index series is developed in a three-step process. The first step involves selecting the constituent companies. The constituent companies were chosen based on the ESG rating score, which reflects strong sustainability risk management practices. The individual firm needs to have at least a 3.3 ESG rating score out of 5.0 to be included in the FTSE4Good Index series for the first time. An ESG rating score of 3.3 represents a very powerful handling of sustainability risks.

	Developed markets	Emerging markets
Companies newly included in the Index Series	ESG Rating of 3.3 or higher	ESG Rating of 2.9 or higher
Companies removed from the Index Series	ESG Rating lower than 2.9	ESG Rating of lower than 2.4

Figure 11: FTSE4Good inclusion and exclusion point table.

Step two involves excluding the FTSE4Good companies from the index series based on the firms' behaviour and controversies. When a firm is involved in serious sustainability controversies, it will not be included in the index series; also, if an existing constituent company is involved in serious controversies, it may be dropped from the index. The companies involved in manufacturing tobacco products, weapons, and coal extraction are not considered for the FTSE4Good Index.

Step three involves reviewing and publishing the FTSE4Good Index series regularly. The FTSE4Good Index series are reviewed in June and December each year. If a firm's ESG rating score drops below the minimum threshold, it has one year to improve its ESG rating before the company is removed from the index.

3.6. Data analysis

There are several ways to analyse quantitative data and find conclusions (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). This study set out the hypotheses in Section 2.6.2 in Chapter Two to achieve the research aim and objectives. This study also used descriptive analysis and inferential analysis to obtain findings. The descriptive analysis includes statistical mean, median, mode, skewness, and kurtosis. The inferential statistics are the main part of this study, which consists of multiple regression analysis. The details of the multiple regression model are explained in the following section.

3.6.1. Regression model

Value-relevance study has been used in this research to investigate the association between a firm's sustainable performance and value. A value-relevance study investigates the association between independent variables and the market price of a given company's share. Prior researchers have used different measures and models to assess value relevance. Following the previous research of Hassel et al. (2005), Moneva and Cuellar (2009), Schadewitz and Niskala (2010), and de Villiers et al. (2012), this study decided to use Ohlson's (1995) valuation model.

This model sufficiently addresses the aim and objectives of this study to assess the incremental value relevance of sustainability reporting and to evaluate whether the combination of financial information and sustainability information offers better market estimation than only financial information.

According to Ohlson (1995), the market value of the share is the product of book value, earnings, and other non-financial value-relevant information. According to Barth et al. (2001), the share price reflects the investors' collective view even when the share market is not fully efficient in implicating all available information in the valuation process. Thus, value relevance can be ascertained based on the equity market value and its changes (Barth, 2006). Generally, the value-relevance model needs a quantitative measure of firm value and follows either a level (price) or a change (return) specification (Barth, 2006). A level (price) specification was used for this study. Based on the above assumption, the fundamental valuation model derived by Ohlson (1995) is as follows:

$$MV_t = \alpha_0 + BV_t + \alpha_1 EPS_t + \alpha_2 vt$$

where

MV_t = market value of equity at time t,

BV_t = book value of equity at time t,

EPS_t = abnormal earning per share for a period t (calculated as the difference between net income at time t and the opening book value of equity multiplied by the required rate of return).

vt = other value-relevant information.

Hassel et al. (2005) claimed that sustainability information is categorised as non-financial value-relevant information. Following Hassel et al.'s (2005) model, this study assumes that corporate sustainability performance enhances the relevance of financial statements when combined. Calculating abnormal earnings in Ohlson's (1995) valuation model is impossible, as the required return rate is not available. Therefore, Hassel et al. (2005) restated the Ohlson (1995) model regarding cum-dividend market value, opening book value, earnings, and other

non-accounting value-relevant information. Thus, Hassel et al. (2005) modified the Ohlson (1995) valuation model as follows:

$$MV_t + DI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BV + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 V_t + \epsilon_t,$$

where

$MV_t + DI_t$ = cum-dividend adjusted market value

BV_t = opening book value

NI_t = current period net income

MV_t = market value of equity

DI_t = dividend declared in the current period

V_t = other value-relevant information

Hassel et al. (2005) deflated all variables in a regression equation with the opening book value to control size. This study followed de Klerk and de Villiers's (2012) natural log to remove size effects and satisfy the regression assumptions. To identify the association between accounting information and the market value of equity, this study restated the Hassel et al. (2005) model as follows:

$$\ln MV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BV + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 V_t + \epsilon_t \text{ - - - - - (Model 1)}$$

where

lnMV = natural log of the cum-dividend-adjusted market value of the share. *MV* is measured as the market value of the share three months after the closing day of the financial statements. The adjusted closing *MV* is taken after three months to allow the firm to prepare and publish financial statements and reflects the dividend on the share price.

BV_t = book value per share for company *i*. Book value is measured as the difference between total assets minus total liabilities divided by the total number of shares.

EPS = earnings per share of company i at the end of financial year t. Earnings per share are measured as earnings after interest and tax divided by the total number of equity shares. Current period net income.

To measure the value relevance of sustainability performance, a new variable called ESG is used as a proxy for non-accounting information and replaces the term V_t in Model 1. Thus, the following model is derived from Model 1:

$$\ln MV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BV + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 ESG + \epsilon_{i,t} \text{ - - - - - (Model 2)}$$

where

ESG is the corporate ESG sustainability performance score of company i at the end of the financial year t. It is a concrete variable, and the score can vary between 0 and 100. The ESG score is determined based on sustainability practices and performance on certain sustainability criteria.

ESG sustainability is a composite measure of corporate sustainability consisting of environmental, social and governance sustainability. To assess the value relevance of environmental, social, and governance sustainability, the ESG variable used in Model 2 has been replaced by three individual sustainability variables, Env, Soc, and Gov. Thus, the new regression model is derived as

$$\ln MV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BV + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 Env + \beta_4 Soc + \beta_5 Gov + \epsilon_{i,t} \text{ - - - - (Model 3)}$$

where

Env = corporate environmental performance score of company i at the end of financial year t. The environmental performance score is defined based on corporate environmental practices and performance. Environmental performance is a concrete variable; the score can vary between 0 and 100.

Soc = corporate social performance score of company i at the end of financial year t. Social performance is a concrete variable; the score can vary between 0 and 100. The social performance score is determined based on corporate social practices and performance.

Gov = corporate governance performance score of company *i* at the end of financial year *t*. The governance performance score is determined based on corporate governance practices and performance. Governance performance is a concrete variable; the score can vary between 0 and 100.

Firm size measured as log market capitalisation (LogMCAp) was used in the next regression model to identify the association between firm size and share price. Market capitalisation is used as a log value to eliminate the potential scaling problem. Therefore, the new regression model is presented as follows:

$$\ln MV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BV + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 ENV + \beta_4 SOC + \beta_5 GOV + \beta_6 \ln MCAp + \beta_7 REP + \beta_8 ES + \beta_9 AGE + \epsilon_{i,t} \text{ --- (Model 4)}$$

where

lnMCAp = natural log of market capitalisation. Market capitalisation is measured as the market value of a share multiplied by the total number of outstanding shares.

REP = the sustainability reputation of a firm at a given time. It is a binary variable valued at 1 when getting the reputation; otherwise, 0. FTSE4Good Index membership has been taken as a proxy for sustainability reputation. When a firm is included or stays as a member of the FTSE4Good Index, it is treated as having a sustainability reputation.

ES = an interaction variable of an environmentally sensitive industry background. *ES* is the binary variable that values 1 when a firm operates in environmentally sensitive industries; otherwise, 0. *Big* is also the binary variable with a value of 1 when the firm's market capitalisation is more than the median; otherwise, 0.

AGE = the number of years the firm is listed on the stock exchange. The age of the stock market listing counted as the year the financial data was collected, and the year the firm was first listed on the stock market.

To accommodate all the interaction variables of size, reputation, industry, and age, Regression Model 4 was further extended with several new binary interaction variables. The new variables are Rep_Big, NonRep_Big and NonREP_Small. Rep is a binary variable that assumes the value 1 if the firm is not included in the FTSE4Good Index and 0 otherwise. Similarly, size is also used as a dummy variable that assumes big firms when market capitalisation is higher than the median and small firms when market capitalisation is less than the median.

This study used four new binary interaction variables for the industrial background. The new variables are Rep_ES, NonRep_ES, ES_Big, and Industry_S. ES is a binary variable measured as 1 when a firm represents an environmentally sensitive industrial background. Environmentally sensitive industries include mining, oil and gas, tobacco, and chemical industries. Similarly, Industry_S are those firms that represent service-based operations. Therefore, Industry_S is measured as 1 when a firm represents a service firm.

In relation to age, this study included one interaction variable between age and sustainability reputation Rep_Y. Y represents a young firm. The young firm is those firms whose age at stock market listing is lower than the median age of the firm. Therefore, Y is measured as 1 when the firm is lower than the median age of the total sample firm; otherwise, 0.

Thus, the final regression model is as follows:

$$\ln MV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BV + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 ENV + \beta_4 SOC + \beta_5 GOV + \beta_6 \ln MCAP + \beta_7 AGE + \beta_8 Rep_Big + \beta_9 NonRep_Big + \beta_{10} NonRep_Small + \beta_{11} Rep_ES + \beta_{12} NonRep_ES + \beta_{13} ES_Big + \beta_{14} Ind_S + \beta_{15} Rep_Y + \epsilon_{i,t} \text{----- (Model 5)}$$

where

Rep_Big = Rep_Big is an interaction variable between sustainability reputation and firm size. Big is the binary value of 1 when a firm's market capitalisation is more than the median; otherwise, 0. Rep_Big are those firms included in the FTSE4Good Index with a market capitalisation of more than the median of the full sample; otherwise, 0.

NonRep_Big = NonRep_Big is also an interaction variable between sustainability reputation and firm size. Big is the binary value of 1 when a firm's market capitalisation is more than the median; otherwise, 0. NonRep_Big are those firms that are not

included in the FTSE4Good Index and, at the same time, have a market capitalisation of more than the median of the full sample, otherwise 0.

NonRep_Small = NonRep_Small is an interaction variable between sustainability reputation and firm size. Small is the binary value of 1 when the firm's market capitalisation is less than the median; otherwise, 0. NonRep_Small are those firms that are not included in the FTSE4Good Index and, at the same time, have a market capitalisation of less than the median of the full sample, otherwise 0.

Rep_ES = Rep_ES is an interaction variable between sustainability reputation and a firm's industrial background. ES is the binary value of 1 when a firm operates in environmentally sensitive industries; otherwise, 0. Rep_ES are those firms that are included in the FTSE4Good Index and, at the same time, operate in environmentally sensitive industries; otherwise, 0.

NonRep_ES = NonRep_ES is also an interaction variable between sustainability reputation and a firm's industrial background. ES is the binary value of 1 when a firm operates in environmentally sensitive industries; otherwise, 0. NonRep_ES are firms that are not included in the FTSE4Good Index and, at the same time, operate in environmentally sensitive industries; otherwise, 0.

ES_Big = ES_Big is also an interaction variable of industry background and firm size. ES is the binary variable that values 1 when a firm operates in environmentally sensitive industries; otherwise, 0. Big is also the binary variable with a value of 1 when the firm's market capitalisation is more than the median; otherwise, 0. Thus, ES_Big are firms that simultaneously operate in environmentally sensitive industries and have a market capitalisation of more than the median of the full sample.

Ind_S = Ind_S is a binary variable of a service firm measured as 1 when a firm operates in the service industry.

Rep_Y = Rep_Y is an interaction variable between a firm's sustainability reputation and the firm's age of stock market listing. A firm represents a reputed firm when it is part of the FTSE4Good Index, while at the same time, a firm is young when its age is lower than the median age of the firm. Therefore, Rep_Y is measured as 1 when a firm

is part of the FTSE4Good Index, and at the same time, its age is lower than the median age of listing; otherwise, 0.

3.6.2. Data scaling

This study used one dependent variable in the regression equation to achieve the research aim and objectives. Two main predictor variables are entirely financial: book value per share (BV) and earnings per share (EPS). This study used four sustainability performance scores: the ESG sustainability performance score (ESG), environmental sustainability performance score (Env), social performance score (Soc) and governance sustainability score (Gov). These sustainability variables are measured between 0 and 100 based on their particular sustainability practices and performance. Four interaction variables were used in the regression model. These variables are firm size, sustainability reputation, environmentally sensitive industrial background, and age of stock market listing. Size, reputation, and industrial background were broken down into six interaction variables. This study used two variables related to a firm's age. Therefore, this study used eight binary variables.

Age of stock market listing and market capitalisation are two continuous variables used in the regression equation. For eight binary variables, this study used 0 or 1 based on specific criteria (please see the definition of variables). However, the book value and earnings per share are financial measures available on companies' financial statements and other databases.

Variables, such as market value (MV) and market capitalisation (MCap), can vary widely; therefore, these variables dominate each other because of their extreme nature. From the beginning of the value-relevance studies, the researchers used actual market data for MV, BV, and EPS regression analysis. Hassel et al. (2005) first used scaling data in the regression analysis for MV, BV, and EPS. Hassel et al. (2005) used BV scaling for the MV, BV, and ESP values. They divided MV, BV, and EPS by opening the book value of the share for a particular company to control the size variance in the regression analysis. Following Hassel et al. (2005), many researchers used book value scaling to address the extreme value and transform the data for analysis. Later, de Klark and de Viliars (2012) used book value transformation and log transformation for data scaling. Until now, value-relevance studies have used three different forms of data transformation: original, BV-scaled, and log-transformed data.

This study considered all three forms of data transformation for the regression analysis, but found the natural log of MV and Mcap better suited to the regression equation. The binary data of 0 and 1 were used in the regression, as this does not require any transformation. On the other hand, original data for BV, EPS, ESG sustainability, environmental sustainability, social sustainability, and governance sustainability best match the regression requirements.

To test the appropriateness of the research data, this study analysed the data characteristics using the skewness and kurtosis of all three data sets. The table below shows the results of the skewness and kurtosis analysis.

	Original Data		Book value Transformation		Natural Log Transformation		Best Achieved Normality	
	Skewness	Kurtosis	Skewness	Kurtosis	Skewness	Kurtosis	Skewness	Kurtosis
MV	-2.31	5.33	8.3	14.12	-0.413	0.671	Natural Log	Natural Log

Table 1: Skewness and kurtosis test of MV.

Descriptive statistics of the original data show skewness for MV variables is -2.31, while the kurtosis reported for the same variables is 5.33. However, for the same variables, said skewness under book value transformation is 8.3, and kurtosis is 14.12. On the other hand, the reported skewness and kurtosis for MV are -0.413 and 0.671, respectively.

Hair et al. (2010) and Bryne (2010) claimed that data is considered normal if the skewness falls between -2 and +2 and the kurtosis between -7 and +7. Curran et al. (1996) recommended the same normality threshold for skewness and kurtosis in evaluating multivariate normality. Under the recommended rule of thumb, the natural log transformation of MV achieved the best-known normality of the data. Table 3 shows the data skewness and kurtosis of all the variables used in the regression analysis.

All Variables		
Variables	Skewness	Kurtosis
<i>InMV</i>	-0.413	0.671
<i>BV</i>	1.660	5.397
<i>EPS</i>	1.646	6.852
<i>ESG</i>	0.037	-0.881
<i>ENV</i>	0.284	-1.056
<i>SOC</i>	0.013	-0.874
<i>GOV</i>	-0.152	-1.018
<i>Rep_Big</i>	0.989	-1.023
<i>NonRep_Big</i>	1.515	0.295
<i>NonRep_Small</i>	0.381	-1.858
<i>Rep_ES</i>	0.723	2.339
<i>NonRep_ES</i>	1.096	4.598
<i>ES_Big</i>	1.370	7.123
<i>Ind_S</i>	0.949	-1.102
<i>Rep_Y</i>	1.451	0.106
<i>Age</i>	0.933	-0.299
<i>InMcap</i>	0.223	-0.105

Table 2: Skewness and kurtosis test results of all variables.

The results revealed that out of 16 predicting variables, 15 satisfy the recommended limit of skewness and kurtosis for the multivariate normality based on Hair et al.'s (2010) and Bryne's (2010) rules of thumb. Only ES_Big narrowly exceeds the limit by a fraction. Kline (1998) suggested that research data should be treated as expected if the skewness is below 3 and the kurtosis value is below 10. Therefore, the dataset achieved essential normality.

3.6.3. Assumptions of regression analysis

It is essential to ensure that the regression data satisfy the five assumptions. This section will discuss five main regression assumptions that need to be satisfied. The assumptions are as follows:

- normality
- linearity
- independent error terms
- constant error variance/ homoscedasticity/ no heteroscedasticity

- no multicollinearity

3.6.3.1. Normality of data

Normal distribution of research data is one of the first criteria regression data needs to meet in order to maximise the reliability of regression results (Camron & Windmeijer, 1997). Research data that cannot satisfy the normality test, such as highly skewed, kurtotic, or outliers, can mislead the relationship between variables. Data normality can be ensured using a few tests and techniques. Histograms, Q-Q plots, skewness, and kurtosis are visual techniques, while Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk are the inferential tests of data normality (Osborne, 2001). The outlier of the data can be identified through histograms or visual inspections. Removal of the outlier minimises the probability of Type I and Type II errors and maximises estimate accuracy (Osborne, 2001). If the normality of data is not maintained, then the standard error will be affected. Normal data distribution is not an issue if the sample size is large enough because of the central limit theorem.

To assess the normality of the research data, the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, Shapiro–Wilk test, and the skewness and kurtosis tests were conducted.

Tests of Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BV	0.246	1210	0.079	0.518	1210	0.106
EPS	0.255	1210	0.073	0.519	1210	0.091
ESG	0.046	1210	0.459	0.982	1210	0.325
ENV	0.078	1210	0.051	0.952	1210	0.073
SOC	0.055	1210	0.069	0.982	1210	0.087
GOV	0.063	1210	0.210	0.970	1210	0.160
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction						

Table 3: Results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests.

All Variables		
Variables	Skewness	Kurtosis
<i>InMV</i>	-0.413	0.671
<i>BV</i>	1.660	5.397
<i>EPS</i>	1.646	6.852
<i>ESG</i>	0.037	-0.881
<i>ENV</i>	0.284	-1.056
<i>SOC</i>	0.013	-0.874
<i>GOV</i>	-0.152	-1.018
<i>Rep_Big</i>	0.989	-1.023
<i>NonRep_Big</i>	1.515	0.295
<i>NonRep_Small</i>	0.381	-1.858
<i>Rep_ES</i>	0.723	2.339
<i>NonRep_ES</i>	1.096	4.598
<i>ES_Big</i>	1.370	7.123
<i>Ind_S</i>	0.949	-1.102
<i>Rep_Y</i>	1.451	0.106
<i>Age</i>	0.933	-0.299
<i>InMcap</i>	0.223	-0.105

Table 4: Skewness and kurtosis of all variables.

The Kolmogorov–Smirnov tests and Shapiro–Wilk tests confirmed the data normality for BV, EPS, ESG, Soc, and Gov variables as $p < 0.05$. However, the skewness and kurtosis confirmed the normality of all the variables used in the regression. ES_Big marginally exceeds the acceptable limit of normal skewness and kurtosis of 2 and 7, respectively, but it can still be used as the skewness does not exceed 10 (Windmeijer, 1997). Therefore, all the variables used in the regression analysis satisfied the data goodness of fit and normality assumption.

3.6.3.2. Assumption of a linear relationship

The value-relevance study was developed based on the linear relationship between dependent and independent variables (Ohlson, 1995). A linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables is essential to accurately estimate the association using multiple regression. There is a non-linear relationship on many occasions in social science research, but it is essential to assess non-linearity (Osborne, 2001). A non-linear relationship between independent and dependent variables produces an incorrect estimation, ultimately increasing the chance of making Type I and Type II errors. Three methods have been suggested by Cohen

and Cohen (1983) and Berry and Fieldman (1985) to detect non-linearity. First, they recommended using existing theories and previous research within the current analysis. This method has not been fully verified, as some previous researchers might have overlooked the linearity in their research work. The second method they suggested was to assess the standardised residual plot as a function of the predicted value. They also suggested a third method of routinely running regression analysis with curvilinear components using squared and cubic terms (Goldfeld & Quandt, 1976).

This research involved a natural log of the market value of the share (dependent variable), the book value of the share, earnings per share, combined ESG sustainability performance, environmental performance, social performance, and governance performance as independent variables. Value-relevance studies have been conducted using Ohlson's (1995) methods many times in previous research (e.g., Baboukardos & Rimmel, 2016; de Klerk & de Villiers, 2012). This study mainly followed de Klerk and de Villiers (2012), who used natural log transformation for the market value per share. Therefore, this research followed the first methods, Cohen and Cohen (1983) and Berry and Fieldman (1985), to address linearity issues.

As Cohen and Cohen (1983) and Berry and Fieldman (1985) suggested, a standardised residual plot is depicted below as a predictive value and P-P function.

Figure 12: Histogram of lnMV (dependent variable).

Figure 13: P-P plot of regression standardized residual of lnMV (dependent variable).

Figure 14: Scatterplot of regression standardized residual of lnMV (dependent variable).

The probability plot shows that the cumulative value follows a straight line and goes upward towards the right-hand side. The scatter plot shows that the standardised residual values are evenly spread from the central line. The P-P and scatter plot of residual values confirm the linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

3.6.3.3. Constant error variance/homoscedasticity/no heteroscedasticity

Constant error variance, commonly known as homoscedasticity, is treated as one of the main assumptions of regression analysis. Homoscedasticity assumes that the error variances are constantly or evenly spread across all independent variable levels (Draper et al., 1966). According to Berry and Feldman (1985), heteroscedasticity can temper the significance test, eventually increasing the possibility of a Type I error. Heteroscedasticity can be identified visually using P-P and scatterplots (Hoaglin & Welsch, 1978). Inferentially, it can be identified using analysis of variance (ANOVA), the Goldfeldt–Quant test, and the Breusch–Pagan test. This research used a P-P plot and analysis of variance (ANOVA) as measures to identify heteroscedasticity.

Figures 13 and 14, the P-P plot and scatterplot, confirm that standardised residuals are evenly scattered across the 0 horizontal lines. Heteroscedasticity exists only when the residual values are not spread relatively evenly. Heteroscedasticity can assume many shapes, such as a bow tie or fan shape (Osborne, 2001). Only more formal tests such as Goldfeldt–Quant, Breusch–Pagan, or ANOVA are recommended when the standard residual deviates from the normal shape.

As a formal heteroscedasticity test, the Goldfeldt–Quant test is useful when error terms decrease or constantly increase as the value of the dependent variable increases, like a fan shape. At the same time, the Breusch–Pagan test is useful for detecting heteroscedasticity when there is a small variance at the centre of the observation and a larger variance at the extreme of the observation in the bow tie shape plot (Berry & Freedman, 1985).

ANOVA is used to test the null hypothesis that the dependent and independent variables taken from them have similar means and variances (Hoaglin & Welsch, 1978). ANOVA is used to compare two sample means involving whether the error terms of their predictor variable differ significantly from each other (Tabachnick et al., 2001). The significance level would indicate

whether the variance is homoscedastic (if significance < 0.01) or heteroscedastic (if significance > 0.01) (Draper et al., 1966; Hoaglin & Welsh, 1978).

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
5	Regression	1144.168	15	76.278	71.323	<.001
	Residual	1276.944	1194	1.069		
	Total	2421.112	1209			
Dependent Variable	InMV					
Predictors	(Constant), BV, EPS, ENV, SOC, GOV, InMCAP, AGE, Rep_Big, NonRep_Big, NonRep_Small, Rep_ES, NonRep_ES, ES_Big, Ind_S, Rep_Y.					

Table 5: ANOVA Table.

From the ANOVA table, the sum of the regression square is 1144.168, and the residual square sum is 1276.944. With 15 degrees of freedom, the F-statistics (value) is 71.323. The significance test shows a value $P > 0.001$, which is less than 0.01. Therefore, there are no significant differences between the error variance of the dependent variable and the independent variables.

3.6.3.4. Independent error terms/no autocorrelation

Under autocorrelation between independent variables, the explanatory power of each predictor variable is at risk because of unexplained error variance. Under this circumstance, there is an increasing risk of making Type II errors of failing to reject the incorrect null hypothesis (Draper et al., 1966; Kenney & Keeping, 1962). The basic Ohlson (1995) model was modified and used by Hassel et al. (2005), and de Klerk and de Villiers (2012) acknowledged it as robust. However, the Durbin–Watson test was employed in this research to test the independence of error terms.

Model Summary	
Model	Durbin-Watson
5	1.164
Dependent Variable	InMV
Predictors	(Constant), BV, EPS, ENV, SOC, GOV, InMCAP, AGE, Rep_Big, NonRep_Big, NonRep_Small, Rep_ES, NonRep_ES, ES_Big, Ind_S, Rep_Y

Table 6: Results of the Durbin-Watson test.

The Durbin–Watson test analyses the independence of error terms by correlating the error terms with an autoregressive model. The Durbin–Watson test produces a value (D-score) between zero and four; zero indicates a cluster of error terms (positive autocorrelation), while a value close to 4 indicates error terms alternate (shifting between positive and negative correlation) (Neter et al., 1996). D-score close to 2 indicates perfect independence of error terms, while a d-score between 1.5 and 2.5 suggests strong independence. The reported D-score of 1.164 suggests a relatively strong independence of the error terms. This statistical assessment and confirmation increased the robustness of the validity of the test results.

3.6.3.5. No multicollinearity

Research studies often face the problem of multicollinearity, resulting in the combined prediction of dependent variables (Nimon et al., 2010). Collinearity or multicollinearity can be defined as the non-zero correlation between two variables (Thompson, 2006). The most common way of detecting multicollinearity is the value of pair-wise correlation, R-square value (Gujarati & Porter, 2008), variance influence factor (VIF), and tolerance limit (TOL) (Kutner et al., 2004; Marquardt, 1970). This study has used TOL and VIF as a measure to detect multicollinearity.

Collinearity Statistics		
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
<i>BV</i>	0.888	1.126
<i>EPS</i>	0.877	1.140
<i>ESG</i>	0.011	9.985
<i>ENV</i>	0.096	1.403
<i>SOC</i>	0.054	0.461
<i>GOV</i>	0.072	3.839
<i>InMcap</i>	0.254	3.945
<i>Rep</i>	0.308	3.243
<i>ES</i>	0.022	4.315
<i>Age</i>	0.976	1.024
<i>Rep_Big</i>	0.238	4.204
<i>NonRep_Big</i>	0.440	2.272
<i>Rep_ES</i>	0.040	5.203
<i>NonRep_ES</i>	0.031	2.441
<i>ES_Big</i>	0.111	0.985
<i>Ind_S</i>	0.777	1.287
<i>Rep_Y</i>	0.857	1.167

Table 7: Results of collinearity statistics.

The table presents the TOL and VIF analysis results for all the predicting variables. According to Gujarati and Porter (2008), a VIF value of less than 5 strongly suggests no multicollinearity, whereas a value between 5 and 10 suggests no severe multicollinearity. Out of the 17 independent variables used in this analysis, 15 indicated no serious multicollinearity. ESG and Rep_ES have VIF values of 9.985 and 5.203, respectively, indicating no serious multicollinearity.

This study has tested five assumptions of multiple regression: normality, linearity, independent error terms, homoscedasticity, and no multi-correlation. Statistical assessments and relevant visual displays confirmed the validity of the research data to perform the regression analysis.

3.7. Ethical consideration

Research ethics refers to the moral principles that instruct the researcher as to how the research work should be carried out. According to Saunders et al. (2016), research ethics are behavioural standards that govern how the researcher should deal with the parties directly or indirectly involved in the research. This research involves secondary data analysis, while there is no interaction with the primary data. The financial, non-financial, and sustainability data collected for the study are available in the public domain. Therefore, some of the ethical principles do not apply to this study. However, the actual data sources have been acknowledged, while safe storage of the collected data has been maintained. The data are only collected for research purposes, and only those collected can be used to answer the research questions.

3.8. Summary

This chapter provides the philosophical stance and methodological choice in compliance with the research aim and objectives. Considering the nature of the research questions, available data, and the existing literature, this study adopted a positivist–objective philosophical research continuum. As an objective study with a clear theoretical backup, this research follows a deductive approach with quantitative research methods. It concentrated entirely on quantitative research methods based on secondary data. This study adopted the Ohlson (1995) valuation model as an analysis tool to test the regression analysis.

The key objectives of this chapter were to achieve theoretical and methodological understandings relevant to this study and select the appropriate methodological design, including areas such as research philosophy, research design, approach, strategy, methods, data analysis tools and techniques to answer the research questions. This study used a natural log to control the size variance for market value data to ensure the normality of data to validate the test results.

This chapter's first section described the justification for using natural log scaling. This chapter also involved all aspects of data validation and analysis. This study ensured that the research data satisfy all the validation criteria, as the process of meeting multiple regression assumptions, data normality, linearity, independence of error terms, homoscedasticity, and multicollinearity was tested using relevant statistical tests. This study employed more than one detection tool for each of these checks. The following chapter discusses how these methodological choices were implemented to meet the research objectives.

Chapter Four: Data Analysis and Results

4.1. Introduction

This chapter describes the data analysis of various regression models developed in Chapter 3 and gives details of descriptive statistics and inferential statistics, such as regression analysis and hypothesis testing, to answer the research questions. The descriptive statistics provide a general overview of the data characteristics and compare the outcome of full sample groups, FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, with FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good sample groups. Regarding regression analysis, the first three regression models were employed on the full sample and inter-sample groups, which facilitated comparison between the regression results of each cluster of samples.

To compare and contrast the results, the full sample was classified twice, once based on the sustainability status, the FTSE4Good sample group and the NonFTSE4Good sample group. The other classifications are based on the Stock Market Index constituency as the FTSE100 sample group, the FTSE250 sample group, and the Small-cap sample group. Therefore, this chapter will examine the descriptive statistics, regression results of all five regression models, and the results of all hypotheses.

4.2. Descriptive analysis of variables

The following tables contain basic descriptive information about all discrete variables. MV was used as the dependent variable in the regression analysis, while the others were used as independent variables. The value of MV, BV, and EPS is presented on a pence scale (1/100 pound), age as year, and MCap as £Million. The tables below depict sets of descriptive statistics for each full sample group: FTSE100, FTSE250, Small-cap sample groups, and FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good sample groups.

<i>Full Sample</i>	<i>MV</i>	<i>BV</i>	<i>EPS</i>	<i>ESG</i>	<i>CESG</i>	<i>ENV</i>	<i>SOC</i>	<i>GOV</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Mkt. Cap (M)</i>
Mean	828.93	3.92	0.39	49.50	46.98	40.96	51.87	52.57	25.63	7249.46
Standard Error	35.11	0.18	0.04	0.60	0.55	0.78	0.64	0.69	0.61	570.61
Median	354.47	2.05	0.19	50.24	47.00	38.00	53.00	53.50	18.00	1276.00
Standard Deviation	1221.19	6.39	1.50	20.87	19.04	27.02	22.10	23.93	21.36	19848.81
Minimum	0.615	-6.07	-15.64	2.9	3	0	1	3	1	12
Maximum	11174.59	133.38	18.30	95.06	94.00	97.00	97.00	99.00	81.00	167761.00
Count	1210	1210	1210	1210	1210	1210	1210	1210	1210	1210

Table 8: Descriptive statistics results of the full sample.

<i>FTSE100</i>	<i>MV</i>	<i>BV</i>	<i>EPS</i>	<i>ESG</i>	<i>CESG</i>	<i>ENV</i>	<i>SOC</i>	<i>GOV</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Mkt. Cap (M)</i>
Mean	1573.84	5.55	0.95	68.47	61.02	63.28	69.08	69.61	31.06	24858.14
Standard Error	99.31	0.32	0.11	0.95	0.92	1.36	1.06	1.09	1.24	1956.40
Median	900.67	4.15	0.50	72.40	61.00	70.00	73.00	73.00	25.50	9764.00
Standard Deviation	1725.78	5.64	1.86	16.51	15.96	23.58	18.44	18.89	21.59	33998.58
Minimum	27.93	-6.07	-5.20	17.04	17.00	7.00	13.00	16.00	1.00	339.00
Maximum	11174.59	29.73	18.30	95.06	94.00	95.00	99.00	97.00	81.00	167761.00
Count	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302

Table 9: Descriptive statistics results of the FTSE100 sample group.

<i>FTSE250</i>	<i>MV</i>	<i>BV</i>	<i>EPS</i>	<i>ESG</i>	<i>CESG</i>	<i>ENV</i>	<i>SOC</i>	<i>GOV</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Mkt. Cap (M)</i>
Mean	714.93	4.48	0.31	48.64	47.95	39.52	52.53	51.22	29.98	1916.53
Standard Error	49.44	0.34	0.06	0.95	0.95	1.42	1.00	1.32	1.33	64.65
Median	383.01	2.29	0.19	50.34	49.00	38.00	53.00	53.00	24.00	1630.00
Standard Deviation	885.74	6.04	1.11	17.09	16.96	25.51	17.93	23.68	23.89	1158.27
Minimum	32.71	-0.57	-8.85	11.14	11.00	0.00	13.00	4.00	1.00	155.00
Maximum	8653.84	39.60	6.08	85.16	85.00	97.00	94.00	94.00	77.00	5509.00
Count	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321

Table 10: Descriptive statistics results of the FTSE250 sample group.

<i>Small Cap</i>	<i>MV</i>	<i>BV</i>	<i>EPS</i>	<i>ESG</i>	<i>CESG</i>	<i>ENV</i>	<i>SOC</i>	<i>GOV</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Mkt. Cap (M)</i>
Mean	508.02	2.77	0.16	40.21	39.24	30.27	42.38	44.81	20.45	1106.44
Standard Error	35.08	0.28	0.06	0.75	0.71	0.92	0.82	0.92	0.76	94.00
Median	219.75	1.38	0.10	38.97	38.00	27.00	41.00	43.00	16.00	476.00
Standard Deviation	849.87	6.72	1.42	18.08	17.27	22.21	19.91	22.34	18.39	2277.39
Minimum	0.62	-3.28	-15.64	2.90	3.00	0.00	1.00	3.00	1.00	12.00
Maximum	6588.11	133.38	16.45	91.02	91.00	96.00	97.00	97.00	81.00	16989.00
Count	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587

Table 11: Descriptive statistics results of the Small-cap sample group.

<i>FTSE4Good</i>	<i>MV</i>	<i>BV</i>	<i>EPS</i>	<i>ESG</i>	<i>CESG</i>	<i>ENV</i>	<i>SOC</i>	<i>GOV</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Mkt. Cap (M)</i>
Mean	1063.16	4.84	0.64	63.86	59.04	58.18	65.86	63.89	30.47	13122.41
Standard Error	65.98	0.27	0.08	0.74	0.70	1.11	0.81	0.86	1.04	1119.34
Median	462.80	3.47	0.32	64.51	58.00	62.50	67.00	66.00	24.00	4669.00
Standard Deviation	1442.58	5.95	1.67	16.12	15.22	24.33	17.80	18.70	22.63	24472.40
Minimum	8.30	-1.37	-13.20	11.14	11.00	0.00	11.00	6.00	1.00	58.00
Maximum	11174.59	39.60	18.30	95.06	94.00	97.00	97.00	97.00	81.00	162755.00
Count	478	478	478	478	478	478	478	478	478	478

Table 12: Descriptive statistics results of the FTSE4Good sample group.

<i>NonFTSE4Good</i>	<i>MV</i>	<i>BV</i>	<i>EPS</i>	<i>ESG</i>	<i>CESG</i>	<i>ENV</i>	<i>SOC</i>	<i>GOV</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Mkt. Cap (M)</i>
Mean	675.97	3.31	0.23	40.12	39.11	29.72	42.73	45.17	22.40	3414.39
Standard Error	37.86	0.24	0.05	0.67	0.63	0.83	0.73	0.89	0.74	552.58
Median	294.18	1.66	0.12	37.80	37.00	26.00	40.00	43.00	16.00	817.50
Standard Deviation	1024.30	6.59	1.36	18.11	17.08	22.38	19.74	24.09	19.95	14950.37
Minimum	0.62	-6.07	-15.64	2.90	3.00	0.00	1.00	3.00	1.00	12.00
Maximum	8653.84	133.38	16.45	91.02	91.00	96.00	97.00	99.00	81.00	167761.00
Count	732	732	732	732	732	732	732	732	732	732

Table 13: Descriptive statistics results of the NonFTSE4Good companies.

The average market value (MV) per share is reported at 828.93 pence for the full sample of 1210 companies. However, for FTSE100, the average share price is 1573.84, and for FTSE250 companies, the average price per share is 714.93, and for Small-cap companies, the average share price is 508.02 per share. In contrast, the average share price for FTSE4Good companies is 1063.16, while it is 675.93 per share for NonFTSE4Good companies. The average share price for the FTSE100 companies is 89% higher compared to the full sample, while it is 120% higher compared to the FTSE250 companies and three times higher compared to the average share price for Small-cap companies. On the other hand, the statistical mean of the share price

for FTSE4Good companies is 57% higher compared to the average share price of NonFTSE4Good companies. Therefore, the average share price is dominated by FTSE100 companies over the other shareholder groups, which is confirmed by the mean and median of the share price.

The mean BV per share is 3.92, 5.55, 4.48, and 2.77 for the full sample, FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies. The book value for FTSE100 companies is 1.41 times higher than the full sample and 1.24 times higher than FTSE250, and almost twice as high compared to Small-cap companies. The book value indicates that for each share of FTSE100, companies hold 1.24 times more assets than FTSE250 companies and twice as many assets compared to Small-cap companies. On the other hand, the mean BV for FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies are 4.84 and 3.31, respectively. Therefore, the book value indicates that each FTSE4Good company's share holds 28% more assets than the NonFTSE4Good company's share.

The mean EPS per share is 0.39, 0.95, 0.31, and 0.16 for the full sample, FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies. The book value for FTSE100 companies is 2.43 times higher than the full sample, 3.6 times higher than FTSE250, and 5.93 times higher compared to Small-cap companies. The earnings per share indicate that each share of FTSE100 companies earns 3.60 times more profit than FTSE250 companies and 5.93 times more profits compared to Small-cap companies. On the other hand, the mean EPS for FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies are 0.64 and 0.23, respectively. Therefore, the book value indicates that each FTSE4Good company's share earns 2.78 times more profit than the NonFTSE4Good company's share.

BV and EPS are the main drivers of MV. In considering the strength of the BV and EPS, FTSE100 companies hold a powerful position compared to FTSE250 and Small-cap companies. At the same time, FTSE4Good companies are far ahead compared to NonFTSE4Good companies in relation to BV and EPS.

In terms of ESG sustainability for all sample groups, the descriptive statistics show ESG, Env, Soc, and Gov performance scores. The reported ESG sustainability performance scores are 49.50, 68.47, 48.64 and 40.21 for the full sample, FTSE100 companies and FTSE250 companies and Small-cap companies, respectively. On average, the FTSE100 companies got

much stronger sustainability performance scores compared to the other sample groups. The ESG score for FTSE100 companies is 1.4 times higher than FTSE250 companies and 1.7 times higher than Small-cap companies. As a result, the FTSE4Good Index is dominated by FTSE100 companies. However, the mean of the combined ESG, which is actually the adjusted ESG score, is reported to be 61.02, significantly lower than the current ESG score. Any deficit in implementing the previous year's commitment can affect the combined ESG score in the current year. Thus, FTSE100 companies are often awarded lower combined ESG (CESG) scores for failure to keep the ESG promise in the previous year, but revealed in the current year. The CESG score for other sample groups is 46.98, 47.95, and 39.34 for the full sample, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, respectively. Each sample group experienced decreased CESG compared to the current year's ESG score. The CESG score is 10.88% lower for FTSE100 companies, 1.41% lower for FTSE250 companies, and 2.53% lower for Small-cap companies, compared to the original ESG score.

Like FTSE100 firms, FTSE4Good firms are more likely to miss their ESG promises more often than NonFTSE4Good firms. On the other hand, the ESG score is reported to be 63.68 and 40.12 for FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies, respectively, while the CESG score is 59.04 and 39.04 for FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good companies, respectively. Because of the higher ESG score of FTSE4Good companies, their combined ESG was reduced significantly compared to NonFTSE4Good firms.

The reported mean of the Env sustainability performance score is 40.96, 63.28, 39.52, and 30.27 for the full sample, FTSE100 companies and FTSE250 companies and Small-cap companies, respectively. On average, FTSE100 companies got much stronger Env sustainability performance scores compared to the other sample groups. The Env score for FTSE100 companies is 1.6 times higher than FTSE250 companies and 2.09 times higher than Small-cap companies. At the same time, the Env score for FTSE4Good companies is 58.18, while the mean Env score for NonFTSE4Good companies is 29.72. Therefore, the mean Env score for FTSE4Good companies was 1.95 times higher than the NonFTSE4Good companies. However, FTSE100 companies, among all other sample groups, hold the strongest foothold in environmental practice and performance.

The reported mean Soc sustainability performance score is 51.87 for the full sample, 69.61 for FTSE100 companies, 52.53 for FTSE250 companies, and 42.38 for Small-cap companies. On average, FTSE100 companies had much stronger Soc sustainability performance scores compared to the other sample groups. The Soc performance score for FTSE100 companies is 1.32 times higher than FTSE250 companies and 1.64 times higher than Small-cap companies. At the same time, the Soc score for FTSE4Good companies is 65.86, while the mean Soc score for NonFTSE4Good companies is 42.73. Therefore, the mean Soc score for FTSE4Good companies was 1.54 times higher than for NonFTSE4Good companies. However, FTSE100 companies, among all other sample groups, hold the strongest foothold in social sustainability practice and performance.

The reported mean of the Gov sustainability performance score is 52.57 for the full sample, 69.61 for FTSE100 companies, 51.22 for FTSE250 companies, and 44.81 for Small-cap companies. Again, FTSE100 companies got much stronger Gov sustainability performance scores compared to the other sample groups. The Gov performance score for FTSE100 companies is 1.34 times higher than FTSE250 companies and 1.54 times higher than Small-cap companies. At the same time, the Gov score for FTSE4Good companies is 63.89, while the mean Gov score for NonFTSE4Good companies is 45.17. Therefore, the mean Gov score for FTSE4Good companies was 1.41 times higher than the NonFTSE4Good companies. However, FTSE100 companies, among all other sample groups, hold the strongest foothold in governance sustainability practice and performance.

Age revealed that the bigger the firm size, the higher the age. The average age of the sample firms is reported to be 25.63 years for the full sample, 31.06 for FTSE100 companies, 29.98 for FTSE250 companies, and 20.45 for Small-cap companies. This is probably because a firm requires time to grow, so on average FTSE100 constituents were aged 31.56, while Small-cap companies were on average only 20.45 years old. FTSE100 companies have been trading on the stock market for almost 1.58 years, and 11.11 years more than FTSE250 companies and Small-cap companies. At the same time, FTSE4Good firms are 30.47 years old, while NonFTSE4Good firms are aged only 22.49. Therefore, FTSE4Good companies have been trading in the stock market for almost 8.07 years longer than NonFTSE4Good firms. FTSE4Good firms are older because FTSE100 firms dominate FTSE4Good Index constituents.

Firm size is one of the strongest determinants of a firm's sustainability practices. The mean market capitalisation (MCap) for the full sample is 7249.46 (£m) compared to 24858.14 for FTSE100 firms, 1916.53 for FTSE250, and 1106.44 for Small-cap firms. Therefore, every FTSE100 firm is around 12 times larger than FTSE250 firms and 22 times larger than Small-cap companies. On the other hand, the statistical mean of MCap for the FTSE4Good firm is 13122.41, compared to 3414.39 for the NonFTSE4Good index. Based on the mean, each of the FTSE4Good companies is, on average, 3.84 times larger than the NonFTSE4Good companies.

Descriptive Statistics							
Variables	Mean	Standard Error	Median	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Count
<i>InMV</i>	5.87	0.04	5.87	1.42	-0.49	9.32	1210
<i>BV</i>	3.92	0.18	2.05	6.39	-6.07	133.38	1210
<i>EPS</i>	0.39	0.04	0.19	1.50	-15.64	18.30	1210
<i>ESG</i>	49.50	0.60	50.24	20.87	2.90	95.06	1210
<i>ENV</i>	40.96	0.78	38.00	27.02	0.00	97.00	1210
<i>SOC</i>	51.87	0.64	53.00	22.10	1.00	97.00	1210
<i>GOV</i>	52.57	0.69	53.50	23.93	3.00	99.00	1210
<i>Rep_Big</i>	0.28	0.01	0.00	0.45	0.00	1.00	1210
<i>NonRep_Big</i>	0.20	0.01	0.00	0.40	0.00	1.00	1210
<i>NonRep_Small</i>	0.41	0.01	0.00	0.49	0.00	1.00	1210
<i>Rep_ES</i>	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.20	0.00	1.00	1210
<i>NonRep_ES</i>	0.08	0.01	0.00	0.27	0.00	1.00	1210
<i>ES_Big</i>	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.21	0.00	1.00	1210
<i>Ind_S</i>	0.29	0.01	0.00	0.45	0.00	1.00	1210
<i>Rep_Y</i>	0.21	0.01	0.00	0.41	0.00	1.00	1210
<i>Age</i>	25.63	0.61	18.00	21.36	0.00	81.00	1210
<i>InMkt. Cap (M)</i>	7.29	0.05	7.15	1.76	2.48	12.03	1210

Table 14: Descriptive statistics of all variables for the full sample.

Table 6 shows the mean statistics for all the variables with appropriate transformation. The total number of samples used in this study was 1,210. Among the variables, only *InMV* and *InMCap* are shown with the natural log value, while *Rep_Big*, *NonRep_Big*, *NonRep_Small*, *Rep_ES*, *NonRep_ES*, *ES_Big*, *Industry_S*, and *Rep_Y* are all binary variables used as a dummy. Four sustainability variables, *ESG*, *Env*, *Soc*, and *Gov*, are discrete variables, and their value is presented in their original form.

4.4. Regression results

This study investigated whether corporate ESG sustainability performance is value-relevant to the investor. Following Hassel et al. (2005) and de Klerk and de Villiar (2012), this study analysed how ESG performance relates to the market share price. A positive association was expected between market share price and financial and non-financial information based on

Ohlson's (1995) valuation model. ESG sustainability, environmental, governance, and social performance were used as proxies of non-financial information. In addition, this study further explores ESG sustainability by analysing the sustainability reputation, firm size, industrial background, and age of firms listed on the stock exchange using an extensive 1,210 samples.

Regression Models 1, 2, and 3 were used for the full sample, FTSE100 sample group, FTSE250 group, Small-cap sample group, and all the sample groups. These models were also applied to FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies to compare and contrast the regression results. Regression Models 4, 5, and 6 were only used for the full sample. The regression results of all regression models are presented in table 15, 16 and 17. Please note *** represent results are significant at 0.01 significance level and ** represent results are significant at 0.05 level.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
	Standardized Coefficient				
	Beta	Beta	Beta	Beta	Beta
Intercept	5.440***	4.889***	4.847***	2.873***	2.770***
BV	0.391***	0.365***	0.369***	0.337***	0.331***
EPS	0.244***	0.227***	0.229***	0.156***	0.137***
ESG		0.173***			
ENV			-0.012	-0.109***	-0.115***
SOC			0.107***	0.059**	0.058
GOV			0.085***	0.035	0.053**
lnMcap				0.529***	0.515***
Rep				0.044**	
ES				-0.125***	
Rep_Big					0.028**
NonRep_Big					-0.048
NonRep_Small					0.075**
Rep_ES					-0.010**
NonRep_ES					-0.187***
ES_Big					0.060
Ind_S					0.002
Age				-0.065***	-0.064***
Rep_Y					0.527***
R Square	0.248	0.277	0.296	0.456	0.476
Adjusted R Square	0.247	0.275	0.293	0.452	0.471
F	198.956	153.739	91.842	111.850	71.323
No. of Observations	1210	1210	1210	1210	1210

Table 15: Regression results of Models 1 to 5 for the full sample.

	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	Standardized Coefficient								
	Beta								
	FTSE100	FTSE250	Small Cap	FTSE100	FTSE250	Small Cap	FTSE100	FTSE250	Small Cap
Intercept	6.159***	5.535***	5.124***	6.685***	5.930***	4.710***	6.401***	5.979***	4.728***
BV	0.334***	0.522***	0.325***	0.356***	0.514***	0.310***	0.405***	0.533***	0.309***
EPS	0.317***	0.188***	0.151***	0.318***	0.183***	0.152***	0.321***	0.177***	0.151***
ESG				0.111**	-0.126***	0.135***			
ENV							-0.294***	-0.105**	0.062
SOC							0.023	0.142***	0.086
GOV							0.116	-0.075**	0.007
R Square	0.294	0.348	0.130	0.306	0.363	0.148	0.337	0.389	0.150
Adjusted R Square	0.290	0.343	0.127	0.299	0.357	0.144	0.326	0.379	0.142
F	62.364	84.687	43.762	43.822	60.292	33.881	30.089	40.092	20.457
No. of Observations	302	321	587	302	321	587	302	321	587

Table 16: Regression Results 1 to 3 for FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies.

	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	Standardized Coefficient					
	Beta	Beta	Beta	Beta	Beta	Beta
	FTSE4G	NonFTSE4G	FTSE4G	NonFTSE4G	FTSE4G	NonFTSE4G
Intercept	5.551***	5.367***	5.238***	4.799***	5.031***	4.819***
BV	0.459***	0.349***	0.449***	0.333***	0.473***	0.333***
EPS	0.233***	0.223***	0.229***	0.217***	0.229***	0.218***
ESG			0.0613**	0.184***		
ENV					0.079***	0.025
SOC					0.078	0.099***
GOV					0.081**	0.078***
R Square	0.329	0.185	0.333	0.218	0.341	0.214
Adjusted R Square	0.326	0.183	0.329	0.215	0.334	0.208
F	116.530	82.740	78.803	67.828	48.848	39.475
No. of Observations	478	732	478	732	478	732

Table 17: Regression Results 1 to 3 for FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good companies.

4.4.1. Regression Model 1

Table 15 presents the regression output, which estimates the association between the market share price and the financial variables before adding any non-financial information. As expected, the coefficient estimate for the book value of common equity share (BV) and the earnings per share (EPS) are both positive and statistically significant for the full sample,

FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, FTSE4Good, and NonFTSE4Good companies. The intercepts are 5.440 for the full sample, 5.551 for FTSE4Good companies, 5.367 for NonFTSE4Good companies, 6.159 for FTSE100, 5.535 for FTSE250, and 5.124 for Small-cap companies, with a P-value <0.01 on all six occasions.

The R^2 is 0.248 for the full sample, 0.329 for FTSE4Good companies, 0.185 for NonFTSE4Good companies, 0.294 for FTSE100, 0.348 for FTSE250, and 0.130 for Small-cap companies. However, the adjusted R^2 is slightly lower than the R^2 . The adjusted R^2 for all sample groups are 0.247 for full sample, 0.326 for FTSE4G, 0.183 for NonFTSE4G, 0.29 for FTSE100, 0.343 for FTSE250 and 0.127 for Small-cap companies. The adjusted R^2 revealed that around 24.7% of the variation in the market value of the common equity share could be explained by the two independent variables, BV, and EPS, for the full sample. However, the adjusted R^2 for FTSE4Good companies is 0.326, while for the NonFTSE4Good companies, it is 0.183, which are significantly different from each other. The adjusted R^2 revealed that 32.6% of the stock price variation could be explained by book value and earnings for FTSE4Good companies, while only 18.3% for the NonFTSE4Good companies.

The adjusted R^2 varies considerably among the sample groups, indicating that each group possesses its characteristics to determine the market share price. Similarly, the adjusted R^2 for FTSE100 companies is 0.294, FTSE250 companies are 0.348, and Small-cap companies are 0.130, which are again significantly different from one group to another. This adjusted R^2 shows that the common equity share price for Small-cap companies in the stock market is more diversified than any other sample groups. On the other hand, the share price for the FTSE250 companies was more centralised on BV and EPS compared to the other sample groups.

4.4.2. Regression Model 2

The ESG sustainability performance variable is added in Model 2 as non-financial information to predict the share price. In Regression Model 2, the coefficient estimate for ESG sustainability performance for the full sample is 0.173; however, the P-value <0.01 significance level. The intercept for the regression equation is 4.889, with a P-value <0.01. The coefficient estimate for the BV is 0.365 and the P-value < 0.01, while the coefficient estimate for EPS is

0.227 with the P-value < 0.01 . The R^2 and adjusted R^2 for the full sample were 0.277 and 0.275, respectively. From Regression Model 1 to Model 2, predicting variable ESG makes changes to adjusted R^2 , which increased 0.028 (0.275-0.247). Thus, the new ESG performance variable makes significant changes and provides further information to the shareholders and market participants for the full sample.

However, in Model 2, the intercept of FTSE4Good companies for the equation is 5.238 and reported a P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient estimate for the BV is 0.449, with the P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient estimate for EPS is 0.229, and the P-value < 0.01 . However, the coefficient for ESG is 0.061, while the P-value is < 0.05 . Thus, the ESG sustainability performance for FTSE4Good is positively and significantly related to the equity share price. At the same time, the intercept of NonFTSE4Good companies for the equation is 4.799 and reported the P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient estimate for the BV is 0.333, with the P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient estimate for EPS is 0.217, and the P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient for ESG is 0.184, while the P-value is < 0.01 . Thus, the ESG sustainability performance for NonFTSE4Good is positively and significantly related to the equity share price.

The coefficient estimate for ESG sustainability for NonFTSE4Good companies is 0.122 higher than the coefficient estimate for FTSE4Good companies, which indicates that ESG sustainability performance is even more relevant for those firms that are not members of prestigious FTSE4Good companies. The R^2 for the FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies are 0.333 and 0.218, respectively, and the adjusted R^2 are 0.329 and 0.215, respectively. From Regression Model 1 to Model 2, the adjusted R^2 increased only 0.004 (0.333-0.4329) for FTSE4Good companies and 0.033 (0.218-0.185) for NonFTSE4Good companies. Therefore, the newly added ESG sustainability variable has significantly impacted the prediction of the share price for both FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good companies. Thus, ESG performance information provides value-relevant information to the stock market participant.

Additionally, for FTSE100 companies in Model 2, the intercept for the equation is 6.685, and the P <0.01 . The coefficient for the BV is 0.356, and the P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient for EPS is 0.318, with the P-value < 0.01 . However, the coefficient for ESG is 0.111, with a P-value < 0.05 . The coefficient and P-value advocate a positive and significant relationship

between ESG sustainability performance and the common equity share price for FTSE100 companies. The R^2 and adjusted R^2 for the FTSE100 companies are 0.306 and 0.299, respectively. From Regression Model 1 to Model 2, the adjusted R^2 increased by 0.012 (0.306-0.294). Regarding FTSE100 companies, the newly added ESG sustainability variable remarkably predicted the share price. Thus, the ESG performance information carries truly value-relevant information to the stock market participant.

On the other hand, for FTSE250 companies in Model 2, the intercept for the equation is 5.930, and the $P < 0.01$. The coefficient for the BV is 0.514, and the P -value < 0.01 . The coefficient for EPS is 0.183, with the P -value < 0.01 . However, the coefficient for ESG is -0.126, with a P -value < 0.01 . The coefficient estimate and P -value advocate a negative and significant relationship between ESG sustainability performance and the common equity share price for FTSE250 companies. The R^2 and adjusted R^2 for the FTSE250 companies are 0.363 and 0.357, respectively. From Regression Model 1 to Model 2, the adjusted R^2 increased by 0.014 (0.357-0.343). Therefore, the newly added ESG sustainability variable remarkably predicts the share price. Thus, the ESG performance information carries truly value-relevant information to the stock market participant for FTSE250 companies.

Additionally, for the Small-cap companies in Model 2, the intercept for the equation is 4.710, and the $P < 0.01$. The coefficient for the BV is 0.310, and the P -value < 0.01 . The coefficient for EPS is 0.152, with the P -value < 0.01 . However, the coefficient for ESG is 0.135, with a P -value < 0.01 . The coefficient estimate and P -value advocate a positive and significant relationship between ESG sustainability performance and the common equity share price for Small-cap companies. The R^2 and adjusted R^2 for the Small-cap companies are 0.148 and 0.144, respectively. From Regression Model 1 to Model 2, the adjusted R^2 increased to 0.017 (0.144-0.127). Therefore, the newly added ESG sustainability variable significantly differs in predicting share price. Thus, the ESG sustainability performance carries truly value-relevant information to the stock market participants for Small-cap companies.

4.4.3. Regression Model 3

In Regression Model 3, the ESG sustainability performance variable has been replaced by each element of ESG sustainability, including environmental, social, and governance performance, to assess the value relevance of each sustainability element and relative importance. ESG performance is the combined environmental, social, and governance performance, and the information users could prefer individual components rather than the combined performance.

4.4.3.1. Environmental performance

For the full sample in Regression Model 3, the intercept of the regression equation reported 4.847 with a P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient estimate of BV is 0.369, and the P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient for EPS is 0.229, and the P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient for environmental sustainability performance Env is -0.012, and the reported P-value < 0.01 . Thus, for the full sample, environmental sustainability performance negatively impacts stock price value. The R^2 and adjusted R^2 for the full sample were 0.296 and 0.293, respectively. From Regression Model 2 to Model 3, the adjusted R^2 increased only to 0.010 (0.293-0.283). Thus, the incremental R^2 indicates that individual environmental, social and governance sustainability performance is more value-relevant than the ESG performance for the full sample.

This study also applied Regression Model 3 for all sample groups. The intercepts of Regression Equation 3 for the FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies are 5.031 and 4.819, respectively, and in both cases, the reported P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient estimate for the BV for both FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies are 0.473 and 0.333, respectively, with a reported P-value < 0.01 . Similarly, the coefficient estimates for EPS for both FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies are 0.299 and 0.218, with a reported P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient estimates for environmental sustainability performance are 0.079 and 0.025 for FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies, respectively. However, the coefficient estimate is only statistically significant for FTSE4Good companies. Therefore, environmental sustainability is significantly and positively associated with the share prices for FTSE4Good companies, but no significant association exists for NonFTSE4Good companies.

On the other hand, for the FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, the intercepts of Regression model 3 are 6.401, 5.979, and 4.728, respectively, with reported P- values <0.01 for all three occasions. The coefficients for BV are 0.405, 0.533, and 0.309, respectively, for the FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, and in every case, the reported P-value <0.01. The coefficient estimates for EPS are 0.321, 0.177, and 0.151 for the FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, with reported P-value <0.01 for all three occasions. The coefficient estimates for environmental sustainability performance are -0.294 for FTSE4100 companies, -0.105 for FTSE250 companies, and 0.062 for Small-cap companies. The P-value associated with Env is >0.01 for FTSE100 and >0.05 for FTSE250 companies, and the addition of environmental performance increases R^2 , which indicates the relevance of environmental performance to the investors. However, the P-value <0.05 for Small-cap companies. Thus, the negative coefficient estimates confirm the negative association between environmental performance and share price, meaning additional environmental expenditure reduces the firm value. This view is consistent with the cost-concerned school of thought. However, there is no evidence that Small-cap companies are negatively or positively affected by environmental sustainability.

The regression results show that environmental sustainability is either negatively associated or has no association with the share price. However, the negative effects are stronger for FTSE100 companies compared to FTSE250 companies. These negative effects are not significantly visible for Small-cap companies. On the other hand, the negative impacts for FTSE4Good companies are lower compared to FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies. At the same time, no significant relationship was found between Env and share price for NonFTSE4Good companies.

4.4.3.2. Social performance

As part of assessing the value relevance of the elements of sustainability, this study used the social sustainability score as a proxy for non-financial information in Regression Model 3. The regression coefficient for the social performance Soc is 0.107. The coefficient estimate indicates social performance positively impacts the share price. This view of positive influence is consistent with the theory, as social spending gives shareholders and investors a signal.

However, the P-value indicates that the relationship between social performance and stock price is significant at a 1% significance level.

This study also investigated the role of social sustainability performance on the share price for all individual sample groups. The incremental adjusted R^2 in Regression Model 3 indicates the additional value relevance of the individual elements of sustainability over the combined corporate sustainability performance. For the FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good companies, the regression coefficients for social performance are 0.078 and 0.099, which indicates that social performance positively influences share price. This view of positive influence is consistent with the theory, as social spending gives shareholders and investors a signal. However, the P-value < 0.01 is only for NonFTSE4Good companies, which indicates that the relationship between social performance and stock price is statistically significant for NonFTSE4Good companies. The positive coefficient estimates indicate that the firm that takes care of other social elements, maintains responsible behaviour, and acts for social well-being is likely to get an extra premium for its share trading from the stock market.

However, for FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, the regression coefficient estimates for social sustainability performance are 0.023, 0.142, and 0.086, respectively. The only occasion where the corresponding P-value is significant at 1% or even at a 5% significance level is for FTSE250 companies. Thus, the relationship between Soc and market share price is not significant for FTSE100 and Small-cap companies. However, the positive regression coefficient indicates a positive association between social performance and stock prices from the research data.

From the regression results, this study found a significant and positive association between social performance and stock price for the full sample and FTSE250 and NonFTSE4Good companies. Still, no evidence has been found for their relationship with FTSE100, Small-cap, and FTSE4Good companies. Unlike environmental performance, social performance did not generate a negative association for any sample group. For FTSE250 and NonFTSE4Good companies, investors appreciate the social engagement and spending, and as a result, they are willing to pay an additional price for the company's share. This scenario is only valid for the FTSE250 and NonFTSE4Good companies, but not for the FTSE100, Small-cap, and FTSE4Good companies.

4.4.3.4. Governance performance

In Regression Model 3, governance performance is used as a proxy of non-financial information alongside the other two elements of corporate sustainability. The regression result showed that the coefficient for Gov is 0.085 with a P-value < 0.01 . The coefficient and the P-value jointly indicate a positive and significant relationship between governance performance and stock prices. In theory, better sustainability performance should follow a higher stock price. The regression result indicates that the better the governance sustainability performance, the higher the share price. Therefore, the investor appreciates betterment in governance.

This study also tried to investigate the association of governance sustainability performance with market share price for all sample groups. For both FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good companies, the coefficient estimates of GOV are 0.081 and 0.078, respectively. The coefficient estimates of FTSE4Good sample companies are significant at a 5% significance level, and NonFTSE4Good companies are significant at a 1% level. Therefore, the regression coefficient indicates a positive and significant association between governance performance and the dependent variables for FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good companies, and the stock price for FTSE100&250 companies.

In addition, the coefficient estimates of GOV are 0.116, -0.075, and 0.007 for FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, respectively. However, the only occasion in which the P-value is < 0.05 is for the FTSE250 sample group. Based on the research data, the GOV variable is not statistically significantly associated with share price for both FTSE100 and Small-cap companies. However, both sample groups have positive coefficient estimates. This positive coefficient indicates whether the GOV variable is positively associated with the share price or has no significant impact on the share price. On the other hand, the GOV variable is negatively and significantly associated with FTSE250 companies.

Corporate governance is a very extensive topic that includes many elements. One of the reasons for the negative relationship is the existence of institutional investors who held 81% of the listed company share in 2017 (Office for National Statistics, 2018) and dominated the stock prices (Budsaratragoon & Jitmaneeoj, 2021). An institutional investor might not be very interested in additional spending on governance, as they have their representative on the board

and can also avail themselves of undisclosed insider information when needed. Thus, the negative relationship between governance performance and stock prices is not surprising.

4.4.4. Regression Model 4

In Regression Model 4, four control variables were introduced with Model 3. These new variables are: firm size in the form of the natural log of market capitalisation (lnMcap), reputation, environmentally sensitive industry background (ES), and age of the stock market listing (Age).

In Regression Model 4, the intercept of the regression equation is reported as 2.873, and the P-value is <0.01 . The coefficient estimates for BV is 0.337 and for EPS is 0.156, with a P-value <0.01 on both occasions.

Significant changes have been noticed in the association between environmental performance and share prices. The regression coefficient for ENV is reported as -0.109, which is significantly higher than the coefficient of -0.012 in Model 3. The reported P-value is still significant for the coefficient in model 4, which is still <0.01 . Thus, the environmental performance variable has a much stronger negative association with share price in Model 4 than in Model 3. This coefficient and the P-value indicate that the new independent control variable carries further information for the investor. It pushes the existing association between the independent and dependent variables.

Significant changes have also been noticed in social performance and share price associations. The regression coefficient for social performance was reported as 0.059, which is significantly lower than the coefficient of 0.107 in Model 3. The P-value for the coefficient in Model 4 is <0.05 , while the P-value was <0.01 in Model 3. Thus, the SOC variable has a much less strong positive association with the share price in Model 4 than in Model 3.

Similar to social performance, significant changes have been noticed in the association between governance performance and share prices. The regression coefficient for GOV is reported as 0.035, which is significantly lower than the coefficient of 0.085 in Model 3. The P-value for the coefficient in Model 4 is >0.05 , while the P-value was <0.01 in Model 4. Thus, the governance performance is no longer statistically significant and has a positive association with share price in Model 4.

The new variable $\ln\text{MCap}$ is the first control variable used in Regression Equation 4. The coefficient estimate for $\ln\text{Mcap}$ reported 0.529 with a $P\text{-value} > 0.001$. Based on the coefficient estimate and the $P\text{-value}$, this new variable is positively and significantly associated with the share price. The larger the company size, the higher the share price. The reason for this association could be that large companies have more diversified and less volatile operations, which tend to be more attractive to shareholders.

The second control variable used in Regression model 4 is sustainability reputation. For sustainability reputation, this study used FTSE4Good Index membership as a proxy and assumed that firms that are members of the prestigious FTSE4Good Index have a good reputation regarding sustainability. The coefficient estimate for the reputation was reported to be 0.044 with a $P\text{-value}$ of < 0.05 . Based on the coefficient estimate and the $P\text{-value}$, this new variable is positively and significantly associated with the share price. A sustainability reputation helps the firm get a premium share price. At the same time, the FTSE4Good Index maintains very rigorous inclusion and exclusion criteria. When a firm is included in the FTSE4Good Index membership, it maintains a very good track record of managing all sustainability risks, which makes the firm's share more attractive to the market.

The third control variable added to the regression equation is the environmentally sensitive industrial background (ES). Firms are categorised under this class when they belong to the mining, oil and gas, tobacco, and chemical industries. In Regression Equation 4, the coefficient estimate for the variable ES is -0.125 with a $P\text{-value} < 0.01$. Based on the coefficient estimate and the $P\text{-value}$, this new variable is negatively and significantly associated with the share price. Thus, shareholders dislike firms operating in environmentally sensitive industries. Shareholders offer a lower price for shares in firms that operate in the mining, oil and gas, tobacco, and chemical industries. As these industries cause enormous harm to the environment, investors and shareholders penalise these firms by offering less value for their shares.

The fourth control variable added with Regression Equation 4 is the age of the stock market listing. The age of the stock market listing is measured by the number of years the company has been trading since the firm was listed in the main market. In Regression Equation 4, the coefficient estimate for the Age is -0.065 with a $P\text{-value} < 0.01$. Based on the coefficient

estimate and the P-value, this new variable is negatively and significantly associated with the share price. The longer the company trades in the stock market, the lower the share price. Therefore, the regression result suggests that the number of years a firm trades in the stock market is negatively associated with the share price. This regression result indicates that newly registered firms are more market-driven and serious about sustainability issues.

The reported R^2 and adjusted R^2 in Regression Equation 4 were 0.456 and 0.452, respectively. The adjusted R^2 is 0.159 higher (0.452-0.293) compared to the R^2 in Regression Equation 3. These four control variables shifted the R^2 and adjusted R^2 to a greater extent. Therefore, the adjusted R^2 is 35.17% higher than the adjusted R^2 in Model 3. The incremental R^2 indicates the additional value relevance of these control variables. Thus, Regression Model 4 can explain the variability of market share prices up to 45.2% by using the traditional financial measures of book value, EPS, and corporate sustainability information. From Regression Model 3 to Regression Model 4, the firm size, reputation, industry background, and age variables brought the additional explanatory power of 15.9% of the market price fluctuation.

4.4.7. Regression Model 5

Regression Model 5 is the final regression model for this study. This final model added several new interaction variables related to firm size, reputation, high-impact industry background, and age. A firm's market capitalisation measures company size. When the firm's market capitalisation is higher than the median, it is classified as a large firm, and when the firm's market capitalisation is less than the median, it is ranked as a small firm.

In Regression Model 5, this study introduced three more predicting binary variables to assess the value relevance of a firm's reputation and size. This study used FTSE4Good membership as a proxy for a firm's sustainability reputation. It is important to know whether a sustainability reputation carries any relevant information and creates any stock market benefit for the company. Regression Model 5 accounts for how investors and shareholders have treated sustainability reputation. A comparison was made between companies of a similar size with a sustainability reputation and without a reputation. This study further classified non-reputed companies into non-reputed large companies and non-reputed small companies.

Table 15 presents the regression results for Model 5. The intercept for regression was 2.770, while it was 2.873 in Model 4. The intercept is statistically significant at a 1% significance level, as the P-value is $P < 0.01$. The coefficient estimate for BV is almost similar to the value of Model 4. In Regression Equation 5, the reported coefficient estimate is 0.331, while it is 0.337 in Regression Equation 4. The coefficient estimates are statistically significant on both occasions, as the $P\text{-value} < 0.01$. The coefficient estimate for EPS changes slightly from Model 4 to Model 5. The reported coefficient for EPS in Model 5 is 0.137, while it was 0.156 in Model 4. Once again, the coefficient estimate for environmental sustainability performance is significantly and negatively associated with share price, similar to Regression Model 4. The coefficient estimates for environmental sustainability performance are -0.115 and -0.109 for Regression Model 5 and Model 4, respectively.

However, the coefficient estimates are statistically significant on both occasions, even after the new variable of environmentally sensitive industries is added to the regression equation. Therefore, the addition of all interaction variables does not bring any changes to the value relevance of environmental sustainability performance.

The coefficient estimate for social sustainability performance remained almost unchanged from Regression Model 4 to Model 5. The coefficient estimates are 0.058 in Model 5 and 0.059 in Model 4; however, the P-value is significant at the 5% significance level in both cases. Thus, adding all interaction variables does not change the value relevance of environmental sustainability performance as an independent variable. Therefore, social sustainability performance is valuable and relevant information for prospective and existing investors.

However, a significant change was noticed in the statistical significance of coefficient estimates in governance sustainability performance. The reported coefficient estimate was 0.053 in Model 5, while the coefficient estimates were 0.035 in Model 4. The coefficient estimate was not significant in Model 4, but it was significant in Model 5 as the $P < 0.01$. Therefore, the magnitude of the impacts of governance performance increased by 0.018 for each reporting unit of higher governance performance. Thus, adding all interaction variables changed the value relevance of governance sustainability performance. Therefore, governance sustainability performance carries value-relevant information to prospective and existing investors.

The regression coefficient for Rep_Big is positive (0.028), and this coefficient is statistically significant at a 5% significance level. Therefore, the coefficient estimate and the P-value indicate that large companies with a good reputation for sustainability enjoy a significant premium price for their shares when traded on the stock market. This is an incentive for companies to be more sustainable and secure a good reputation for sustainability by being more sustainable.

The coefficient estimate for NonRep_big is -0.048. However, the regression coefficient estimates are not statistically significant, as the P-value is above acceptable. Thus, although there is a negative relationship between the large company not being sustainable and its market share price, from the data, it cannot be concluded that large companies are being punished for not having a good reputation for sustainability.

Table 15 also presents the regression summary statistics results from Regression Model 5. According to the results in the table, the coefficient estimates for the interaction terms company size (market capitalisation) and non-reputed small companies are positive (0.075), and the result is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The results indicate that sustainability reputation is not a problem in the stock market for small companies. Small companies are less visible to the media and the public, whereas large companies are always under extreme media scrutiny. Thus, potential investors and shareholders do not punish smaller companies for not being highly sustainable. Compared to large companies, both reputed and non-reputed, small companies enjoy better stock market prices and higher value.

Among three different groups in terms of sustainability reputation and size, Rep_Big companies, NonRep_Big companies, and NonRep_Small companies, positive and significant associations exist for Rep_Big companies and NonRep_Small companies. The coefficient estimate is negative for NonRep_Big companies but not statistically significant. This result indicates that investors overvalue the share for reputed companies and non-reputed small companies; however, this overvaluation does not exist for the same size of companies that do not have sustainability reputations. The comparison revealed a real stock market reward for FTSE4Good membership and/or sustainability reputation. The sustainability reputation enjoys a higher market share price than the company that has a lower sustainability reputation. Thus, the reputation of having higher sustainability performance creates value for large companies.

On the other hand, large companies have more negative coefficient estimates than less sustainable performance companies. In contrast, small companies have statistically significant positive coefficient estimates, but the association with market share price for large companies with no sustainability reputation is statistically insignificant. Therefore, there is statistical evidence from the data that the stock market treats non-reputed large companies and non-reputed small companies differently. The coefficient estimates for NonRep_Big and NonRep_Small follow two directions.

Regression Model 5 also accommodated three interaction variables related to environmentally sensitive or high-impact companies (ES) on the market share price. This study has used three interaction terms: reputation, firm size, and industrial background to assess the possible impacts of sustainability on the share price for environmentally highly impacted firms. The first interaction term used is Rep_ES companies, the second interaction term used is NonRep_ES, and the third interaction term used in the regression model is ES_Big. All three different interaction terms compare the sustainability impacts on share price between reputed companies and non-reputed companies and between large and small companies. This study also used an industrial binary dummy of service industries to see how sustainability performance impacts share prices for the companies that operate in the service industry.

Table 15 presents the results, showing that the coefficient estimate for Rep_ES is -0.010; this coefficient estimates that the environmentally sensitive industrial background is negatively associated with the market share price for reputed companies. The P-value suggests ($P < 0.05$) that the relationship between the interaction terms Rep_ES and market share price is statistically significant. Based on this result, even a highly sustainable firm offered a lower market share price than the other firms in environmentally sensitive industries.

However, the investors and the shareholders have higher expectations from these companies not to damage the environment, natural resources, and the planet. Some of the largest companies listed on the London Stock Exchange have the world's highest carbon footprint. When considering their overall environmental impacts, the negative coefficient estimates are not unjustified from the shareholders' and investors' points of view. When a firm is a member of the prestigious FTSE4Good sustainability index, it has a good track record of its environmental and sustainability effects. However, investors and shareholders expect no

further damage to the planet's natural resources; thus, investors offer lower share prices for them, considering their potential harm whenever the firm operates in environmentally sensitive industries.

In Regression Equation 5, the second interaction term used in the model is NonRep_ES, when a firm does not have a sustainability reputation but operates in environmentally sensitive industries. These firms are categorised as less focused on sustainability as they work in industries with a high environmental impact. The coefficient estimate for NonRep_ES is -0.187, which is significant at the 1% significance level. Thus, non-reputed companies operating in environmentally sensitive industries are negatively associated with market share price, and the relationship is statistically significant.

However, to assess the stock market effects for large companies operating in environmentally sensitive industries, this study used the interaction terms Big_ES for the companies with a market capitalisation larger than the median and working in high-impact industries. The coefficient estimate for Big_ES is 0.060, and the value is not statistically significant at the 1% or 5% significance level. The regression result suggests that larger companies enjoy higher stock market prices than smaller companies. Large companies enjoy higher prices, probably because of their relative importance of size, availability of liquid assets, and capability to restore the environmental damage they caused. However, on the other two occasions for Rep_ES and NonRep_ES, the stock market effects were negative.

In Regression Equation 5, another dummy variable was used in the model for companies operating in service industries. According to the theory, service companies are less likely to cause environmental damage. From the regression analysis, the coefficient estimate was 0.002. However, this value is not statistically significant at a 1% or 5% significance level, as $P > 0.05$. So service companies, at least, are not negatively associated with the market share price. The reason could be the less physical substance of their presence.

The service industry in the UK is dominated by financial services, and it is critical to see which industry firms make the most of the investment. Service has a very small positive coefficient estimate, but is not statistically significant. From the regression results, services firms do not differ from other industrial backgrounds regarding stock market price. Theoretically, service

companies should have a lower environmental footprint, but technically, they can have higher environmental impacts through their investment.

The regression result differences between Rep_ES and NonRep_ES are that the magnitude of the negative impact for NonRep_ES is 1.87 times higher than that of Rep_ES. Reputed companies are more sustainable than others, while their size and market capitalisation are larger. Based on the theory, a more sustainable company should have a less negative impact on their share price, and the regression result follows the theory. Investors offer lower prices whenever companies operate in industries with a high environmental impact, but they care about the firm's sustainability status. However, whenever the investor considers the firm to be a member of the FTSE4Good Index but operates in industries with a high environmental impact, they offer a slightly higher price because a sustainability reputation helps to ease off some of the negative impact industries hold.

Because of general perceptions and expectations, the strategic direction is unlikely to be reconciled between sustainability reputation and companies operating in high-impact industries. As a member of society, the investor expects no further damage to the environment in the first place. At the same time, the sustainable firm operates in high-impact industries, does environmental damage, and then tries to compensate through its environmental spending. Thus, a sustainability reputation can minimise the environmental damage and negative impacts of operating in high-impact industries. However, because of this unlikely combination, these companies suffer more in stock market price than non-FTSE4Good companies operating in industries with a high environmental impact.

In Regression Equation 5, no noticeable changes were noticed for the variable Age. The coefficient estimate for the variable Age is -0.064 with a P-value < 0.01. Based on the coefficient estimate and the P-value, this variable is negatively and significantly associated with the share price. Therefore, the regression results suggest that the firm's length of stock market trading is negatively associated with the share price. The longer the company trades in the stock market, the lower the share price. This regression result indicates that newly registered firms are more market-driven and serious about sustainability issues.

The last added variable in Regression Equation 5 is Rep_Y to assess the stock market impacts of young firms with a reputation for sustainability. The coefficient estimate for the variable Rep_Y is 0.527 with a P-value<0.01. Based on the coefficient estimate and the P-value, this variable is positively and significantly associated with the share price. Therefore, the regression result suggests that young sustainable firms enjoy better share prices than old and non-sustainable firms.

The R² and adjusted R² for Regression Model 5 are 0.473 and 0.466, respectively. Therefore, the R² in Model 5 is 3.73% higher than the R² in model 4. At the same time, the adjusted R² is 3.09% higher than the adjusted R² in Model 4. The incremental R² indicates the incremental value relevance of new variables added in Regression Equation 5. Thus, Regression Model 5 can explain the variability of market share price up to 46.6% by using book value, EPS, and corporate sustainability information. From Regression Model 4 to Regression Model 5, all interaction variables brought the additional explanatory power of 3.09% of the market price fluctuation.

4.5. Hypothesis results

This study set nine alternative hypotheses to achieve the research aim and objectives. However, only Hypotheses 1, 2, 3, and 4 applied to all the sample groups, including FTSE100 companies, FTSE250 companies, and Small-cap companies. At the same time, these hypotheses were also applied to FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies. The table below presents each alternative hypothesis and the test result at a 95% confidence level.

Serial Hypothesis	<i>Alternative Hypothesis</i>	<i>Status</i>
<i>H1</i>	<i>Corporate ESG sustainability (environmental, social, and governance) performance is significantly associated with share price, as sustainability performance carries value-relevant information for investors.</i>	<i>Accepted</i>

H2	<i>Corporate environmental performance is significantly associated with share price, as environmental performance provides value-relevant information for investors.</i>	Accepted
H3	<i>Corporate social performance is significantly associated with share price, as social performance provides value-relevant information for investors.</i>	Accepted
H4	<i>Corporate governance performance is significantly associated with share price, as governance performance provides value-relevant information for investors.</i>	Accepted
H5	<i>Firm size significantly affects the sustainability–share price relationship, as firm size provides value-relevant information for the investor.</i>	Accepted
H6A	<i>A large firm with a higher sustainability reputation is associated with a higher share price compared to a large firm with a lower sustainability performance.</i>	Accepted
H6B	<i>The market undervalues the large firm with lower sustainability performance when compared with the small firm with a similar level of sustainability performance.</i>	Rejected
H7A	<i>The market undervalues firms that operate in high-impact industries when compared with firms from other industries.</i>	Accepted
H7B	<i>The stock market undervalues firms with no sustainability reputation more severely compared to those firms that have a reputation for sustainability when both firms operate in environmentally sensitive industries.</i>	Accepted

<i>H8A</i>	<i>A firm's age of stock market listing is significantly associated with share price, as the firm's age provides value-relevant information for the investor.</i>	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>H8B</i>	<i>The market share price is higher for young firms having a better sustainability reputation compared to other firms.</i>	<i>Accepted</i>

Table 18: Result of Hypotheses

Hypothesis Result – H1

ESG sustainability performance to stock price – positively and significantly associated

The first hypothesis was designed to assess the relationship between ESG sustainability performance and share price in the stock market. In Regression Model 2, the ESG sustainability performance score was added to the existing independent variables of BV and EPS. From the regression result in Table 15, the coefficient estimate for ESG sustainability performance was reported as 0.173. The coefficient estimate is statistically significant, with a 99% confidence level. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

ESG to stock price for FTSE4Good – positively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess the relationship between ESG sustainability performance and market share price for the FTSE4Good companies. The regression results presented in Table 17 show that the reported coefficient estimate is 0.061, and this coefficient is statistically significant at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, there is a positive and significant association between ESG sustainability performance and market share price for FTSE4Good companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

ESG to stock price for NonFTSE4Good – Positively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess the relationship between ESG sustainability performance and market share price for the FTSE4Good companies. The regression results presented in Table 17 show that the reported coefficient estimate is 0.184, and this coefficient is statistically significant at a 99% confidence level. Therefore, there is a positive and significant association between ESG sustainability performance and market share price for NonFTSE4Good companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

ESG to stock price for FTSE100 companies – positively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess the relationship between ESG performance and market share price for the FTSE100 companies. From the regression results using Regression Model 2, the reported coefficient estimate is 0.111, and this coefficient is statistically significant at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, a positive and significant relationship exists between ESG sustainability performance and the market share price for FTSE100 companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

ESG to stock price for FTSE250 companies – negatively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess the relationship between ESG performance and market share price for the FTSE250 companies. From the regression results using Regression Model 2, the reported coefficient estimate is -0.126, and this coefficient is statistically significant with a 99% confidence level. Therefore, a negative and significant relationship exists between ESG sustainability performance and market share price for FTSE250 companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

ESG to stock price for Small-cap companies – positively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess the relationship between ESG performance and market share price for Small-cap companies. From the regression results using Regression Model 2, the reported coefficient estimate is 0.135, and this coefficient is statistically significant at a 99% confidence level. Therefore, a positive and significant relationship exists between ESG sustainability performance and the market share price for FTSE100 companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Hypothesis Result – H2

Environmental performance to stock price – significantly and negatively associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess the relationship between environmental performance and market share price. Using Regression Model 5, the reported coefficient estimate for environmental performance was -0.115, and this coefficient was statistically significant at a 99% confidence level. Therefore, a significant relationship exists between environmental performance and market share price. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Environmental performance to stock price for FTSE4Good companies – significantly and positively associated

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis on whether there is any relationship between environmental performance and market share price for FTSE4Good companies. Using Regression Model 3, the reported coefficient estimate for environmental performance for FTSE4Good companies is 0.079, and this coefficient is statistically significant with a 99% confidence level. Therefore, a positive and significant relationship exists between environmental performance and market share price for FTSE4Good companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Environmental performance to stock price for NonFTSE4Good – no significant association

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis on whether there is any relationship between environmental performance and market share price for NonFTSE4Good companies. Using Regression Model 3, the reported coefficient estimate for environmental performance for FTSE4Good companies is 0.025, and this coefficient is not statistically significant at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, no significant relationship exists between environmental performance and market share price for NonFTSE4Good companies. Thus, the null hypothesis is retained due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically insignificant.

Environmental performance to stock price for FTSE100 companies – significantly but negatively associated

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis on whether there is any relationship between environmental performance and market share price for FTSE100 companies. The reported coefficient estimate for environmental performance for FTSE100 companies is -0.294, and this coefficient is statistically significant at a 99% confidence level. Therefore, a negative and significant relationship exists between environmental performance and market share price for FTSE100 companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Environmental performance to stock price for FTSE250 companies – significantly but negatively associated

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis on whether there is any relationship between environmental performance and market share price for FTSE250 companies. Using Regression Model 3, the reported coefficient estimate for environmental performance for FTSE250 companies is -0.105, and this coefficient is statistically significant at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, a negative and significant relationship exists between environmental performance and market share price for FTSE250 companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Environmental performance to stock price for Small-cap companies – no significant association

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis on whether there is any relationship between environmental performance and market share price for Small-cap companies. Using Regression Model 3, the reported coefficient estimate for environmental performance for Small-cap companies is 0.062, and this coefficient is statistically significant with a 95% confidence level. Therefore, no significant relationship exists between environmental performance and market share price for Small-cap companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was retained because the alternative hypothesis was statistically significant.

Hypothesis Result – H3

Social performance to stock price – positively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess the relationship between social performance and the market share price as part of the combined ESG score. In Regression Model 3, environmental, social and governance performance scores are used as a proxy of ESG sustainability performance. The final regression model, Model 5, was used to assess the value relevance of social performance. The reported coefficient estimate is 0.058, which is statistically significant with a 95% confidence level. Therefore, a positive and significant relationship exists between social performance and market share price. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Social performance to stock price for FTSE4Good – no significant association

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis of whether there is any relationship between social performance and market share price for FTSE4Good companies. The reported coefficient estimate for social performance for FTSE4Good companies is 0.078, and this coefficient is statistically insignificant at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, there is no

evidence of any statistically significant relationship between social performance and market share price for FTSE4Good companies. Thus, the null hypothesis is retained due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically insignificant.

Social performance to stock price for NonFTSE4Good – positively and significantly associated

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis of whether there is any relationship between social performance and market share price for NonFTSE4Good companies. Using the results of Regression Model 3, the reported coefficient estimate for social performance for NonFTSE4Good companies is 0.099, and this coefficient is statistically significant with a 99% confidence level. Therefore, a positive and significant relationship exists between social performance and market share price for NonFTSE4Good companies. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Social performance to stock price for FTSE100 companies – no significant association

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis of whether there is any relationship between social performance and market share price for FTSE100 companies. Using the results of Regression Model 3, the reported coefficient estimate for social performance for FTSE100 companies is 0.023, and this coefficient is not statistically significant at the 95% confidence level. Therefore, no significant relationship exists between social performance and market share price for FTSE100 companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was retained because the alternative hypothesis was statistically insignificant.

Social performance to stock price for FTSE250 companies – positively and significantly associated

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis of whether there is any relationship between social performance and market share price for FTSE250 companies. Using the results

of Regression Model 3, the reported coefficient estimate for social performance for FTSE250 companies is 0.142, and this coefficient is statistically significant with a 99% confidence level. Therefore, a positive and significant relationship exists between social performance and market share price for FTSE250 companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Social performance to stock price for Small-cap companies – no significant association

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis of whether there is any relationship between social performance and market share price for Small-cap companies. Using the results of Regression Model 3, the reported coefficient estimate for social performance for Small-cap companies is 0.086, and this coefficient is statistically insignificant at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, no significant relationship was found between social performance and market share price for Small-cap companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was retained because the alternative hypothesis was statistically significant.

Hypothesis Result – H4

Governance performance to stock price – positively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess the relationship between governance performance and the combined ESG score with the market share price. In Regression Model 3, environmental, social, and governance performance scores are used as a proxy for ESG performance. However, the final regression equation, Model 5, was used to test this hypothesis. The reported coefficient estimate for governance performance is 0.053, and this coefficient is statistically significant with a 95% confidence level. Therefore, a positive and significant relationship exists between governance performance and market share price. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Governance performance to stock price for FTSE4Good companies – positively and significantly associated

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis of whether there is any relationship between governance performance and market share price for FTSE4Good companies. Using the results of Regression Equation 3, the reported coefficient estimate for governance performance for FTSE4Good companies is 0.081, and this coefficient is statistically significant at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, a statistically significant relationship exists between governance performance and market share price for FTSE4Good companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Governance performance stock price for NonFTSE4Good companies – positively and significantly associated

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis of whether there is any relationship between governance performance and market share price for NonFTSE4Good companies. Using the results of Regression Equation 3, the reported coefficient estimate for governance performance for NonFTSE4Good companies is 0.078, and this coefficient is statistically significant at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, there is evidence of a statistically significant relationship between governance performance and market share price for NonFTSE4Good companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Governance performance to stock price for FTSE100 companies – no significant association

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis of whether there is any relationship between governance performance and market share price for FTSE100 companies. Using the results of Regression Equation 3, the reported coefficient estimate for governance performance for FTSE100 companies is 0.116, and this coefficient is statistically not significant at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, there is no evidence of any statistically significant relationship

between governance performance and market share price for FTSE100 companies. Thus, the null hypothesis is retained due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically insignificant.

Governance performance to stock price for FTSE250 companies – negatively but significantly associated

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis of whether there is any relationship between governance performance and market share price for FTSE250 companies. Using the results of Regression Equation 3, the reported coefficient estimate for governance performance for FTSE250 companies is -0.075, and this coefficient is statistically significant with a 95% confidence level. Therefore, there is evidence of a statistically significant relationship between governance performance and market share price for FTSE250 companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected because the alternative hypothesis is statistically insignificant.

Governance performance to stock price for Small-cap companies – no significant association

Regression Model 3 was used to test this hypothesis of whether there is any relationship between governance performance and market share price for Small-cap companies. Using the results of Regression Equation 3, the reported coefficient estimate for governance performance for Small-cap companies is 0.007, and this coefficient is statistically not significant at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, there is no evidence of any statistically significant relationship between governance performance and market share price for Small-cap companies. Thus, the null hypothesis is retained due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically insignificant.

Hypothesis Result – H5

Firm size to share price – positively and significantly associated

This study tested the hypothesis of the impact of firm size on share price using Regression Model 4. From the regression result of Model 4, the reported coefficient estimate for $\ln\text{Mcap}$ is 0.515, and this coefficient is not statistically significant at the 99% confidence level. Therefore, there is strong evidence of a statistically significant relationship between firm size and market share price for the full sample. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Hypothesis Result – H6

Sustainability reputation for a large firm to stock price – positively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess whether the stock market incentivises a higher sustainability reputation for a large firm than a low-sustainability firm of the same size. For this purpose, FTSE4Good Index membership is used as a proxy for a higher sustainability reputation. Those firms that are not members of the FTSE4Good Index are treated as having a lower sustainability reputation. To test this hypothesis, Regression Model 5 was used. The coefficient estimate for Rep_Big is 0.028, which is statistically significant with a 95% confidence level. Therefore, a large firm with a higher sustainability reputation gets a larger premium value for its share in the stock market than a firm with a lower sustainability reputation of the same size. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Large firm without sustainability reputation to a stock price – negatively but not significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess whether the stock market penalises a larger firm without a sustainability reputation compared to a smaller firm without a sustainability reputation. For this purpose, FTSE4Good Index membership is used as a proxy for a higher sustainability reputation. Those firms that are not members of the FTSE4Good Index are treated as having a

lower sustainability reputation. This hypothesis compares stock market returns between larger and smaller firms that are not part of the FTSE4Good Index. To test the hypothesis, Regression Model 5 was used. The coefficient estimate for NonRep_Big is -0.048, and this coefficient estimate is not statistically significant at the 95% confidence level.

At the same time, the coefficient estimate for NonRep_Small is 0.075, which is statistically significant, with a 95% confidence level. However, NonRep_big firms have a negative coefficient that indicates the investors' willingness to penalise the company by paying less for the shares of those large companies that fail to create a higher sustainability reputation. At the same time, NonRep_Small firms have positive coefficient estimates, which indicates the investors' unwillingness to penalise the firms' lower level sustainability.

Therefore, evidence suggests that large firms with lower sustainability reputations get lower stock prices from the data compared to smaller firms without a sustainability reputation. Thus, the null hypothesis is retained due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically insignificant.

Hypothesis Result – H7

Environmentally sensitive firm to share price – negatively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess how the stock market reacts to companies operating in environmentally sensitive industries. This hypothesis was mainly built to see how investors react to stock pricing for firms that operate in environmentally sensitive industries. To test the hypothesis, Regression Model 4 was used. The coefficient estimate for ES is -0.125, and this coefficient estimate is statistically significant at a 99% confidence level. The coefficient estimate is negatively associated with the share price. Investors underprice the share value of companies operating in environmentally sensitive industries. The negative impacts of operating in environmentally sensitive sectors offset the positive effects of higher corporate sustainability on stock prices. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Non-sustainable firms operating in environmentally sensitive industries to share price – negatively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess how the stock market reacts to companies without sustainability reputations and also operating within environmentally sensitive industries. To test this hypothesis, Regression Model 5 was used. The coefficient estimate for NonRep_ES is -0.187, and this coefficient estimate is statistically significant, with a 99% confidence level. The coefficient estimate is negatively associated with the share price. The negative impacts for environmentally sensitive industries are significantly higher for a firm without a sustainability reputation than for a firm with a sustainability reputation. Therefore, investors underprice the value of the share for those companies without a sustainability reputation that operates in environmentally sensitive environments. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

The large firm operating within environmentally sensitive industries to share price – no significant association

This hypothesis was designed to assess how stock market impacts are managed by companies operating within environmentally sensitive industries. To test this hypothesis, a dummy interaction variable of Big_ES was used, and Regression Model 5 was used. The coefficient estimate for Big_ES is 0.060, and this coefficient estimate is not statistically significant at the 95% confidence level. The coefficient estimate is positively associated with the share price, although the coefficient estimate is positively correlated with the share price. Still, from the data, the evidence is not strong enough to conclude that the negative environmental impacts on share price are managed better by a large corporation. Thus, the null hypothesis is retained due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically insignificant.

Hypothesis Result – H8

Age to share price – negatively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess how stock prices differ with the age variation of a stock market listing. The coefficient estimate for age is -0.064, which is statistically significant at a 99% confidence level. Moreover, the coefficient estimate is negatively associated with the share price, indicating investors' unwillingness to pay a lower price for the share of old companies. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

Young firm with sustainability reputation to share price – positively and significantly associated

This hypothesis was designed to assess how the stock price differs with the varying age of stock market listings for firms with sustainability reputations. The coefficient estimate for Rep_Y is 0.527, which is statistically significant at the 99% confidence level. Moreover, the coefficient estimate is positively associated with the share price, indicating that investors pay a premium price for the shares of young firms with a sustainability reputation. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected due to the alternative hypothesis being statistically significant.

4.6. Sensitivity Analysis

A sensitivity analysis was undertaken on the regression models to establish the reliability of the model and results. In sensitivity analysis, the dependent variable lnMV has been replaced by lnMCap. Market capitalisation is measured as the total number of outstanding shares multiplied by each share's market value. As market capitalisation is a big sum, this study used natural log (ln) to control the size. All five regression models have been tested using lnMCap as dependent variables. The regression results are presented below:

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5		Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
	Standardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient								
	Beta	Beta	Beta	Beta	Beta		Beta	Beta	Beta	Beta	Beta
Intercept	6.994***	4.591***	4.638***	4.717***	4.983***	Intercept	5.440***	4.889***	4.847***	2.873***	2.770***
BV	0.384***	0.296***	0.085***	0.092***	0.042***	BV	0.391***	0.365***	0.369***	0.337***	0.331***
EPS	0.209***	0.147***	0.142***	0.137***	0.062***	EPS	0.244***	0.227***	0.229***	0.156***	0.137***
ESG		0.605***				ESG		0.173***			
ENV			-0.107**	-0.136***	-0.146***	ENV			-0.012	-0.109***	-0.115***
SOC			0.179***	0.2404***	0.298***	SOC			0.107***	0.059**	0.058**
GOV			0.029	0.037	0.147***	GOV			0.085***	0.035	0.053**
Size				0.381***	0.323***	InMcap				0.529***	0.515***
Rep				0.089***		Rep				0.044**	
ES				-0.053**		ES				-0.125***	
Rep_Big					0.595***	Rep_Big					0.028**
NonRep_Big					0.436	NonRep_Big					-0.048
NonRep_Small					0.121***	NonRep_Small					0.075**
Rep_ES					-0.097	Rep_ES					-0.010**
NonRep_ES					-0.025***	NonRep_ES					-0.187***
ES_Big					0.16**	ES_Big					0.060
Ind_S					0.031	Ind_S					0.002
Age				-0.043***	-0.026***	Age				-0.065***	-0.064***
Rep_Y					0.391***	Rep_Y					0.527***
R Square	0.092	0.445	0.456	0.466	0.530	R Square	0.248	0.277	0.296	0.456	0.476
Adjusted R Square	0.190	0.344	0.453	0.462	0.527	Adjusted R Square	0.247	0.275	0.293	0.452	0.471
F	61.407	322.923	168.174	116.375	215.844	F	198.956	153.739	91.842	111.850	71.323
No. of Observations	1210	1210	1210	1210	1210	No. of Observations	1210	1210	1210	1210	1210

Dependent Variable : InMcap

Dependent Variable: InMV

Table 18: Regression results dependent variables InMcap vs InMV.

Under the new dependent variable InMcap, all regression outputs showed similar results to the previous regression output using InMV as dependent variables. ESG sustainability performance is significantly associated with a market capitalisation as well as the market value of the share. In regression models 1 to 3, the only time the regression results significantly changed for governance performance. The coefficient estimate for GOV was statistically significant in previous regression, but it's not statistically significant on this occasion. However, in the final model, the coefficient estimate became statistically significant again. Environmental performance is negative and social performance is positively associated with market capitalisation, which is same as before, but the coefficient changed.

Some changes have been noticed for the R^2 and the adjusted R^2 . In regression model 5, the moderating variable Rep_ES is not significantly associated with market capitalisation any more, and this variable was statistically significant in the original regression at a 95% confidence level. On the other hand, ES_Big is significant at a 95% confidence level which was not statistically significant in the original regression. The adjusted R^2 increased under the new regression to 0.527, originally reported to 0.471. Therefore, sensitivity analysis confirms the authenticity of the original regression results, as not many major changes were noticed.

4.7. Robustness Check

To check the robustness of the regression results, this study used R essentials robust regression. Robust regression is an alternative to ordinary least squares (OLS) regression. Robust regression is designed to deal with the issues with outliers. It minimises the effects of outliers and results in a more precise standard error. Table 20 presents coefficient estimates of regression model 5 using both OLS regression and robust regression. Robust regression also produced similar coefficient estimates for all variables. Robust regression produces a negative coefficient for ENV, Rep_ES and NonRep_ES, which are also negative under OLS regression. Therefore, robust regression results confirm no heteroscedastic issues of data.

	Model 5	Model 5
	Standardized Coefficient Beta	Standardized Coefficient Beta
	OLS	R Essentials
Intercept	2.770	3.048
BV	0.331	0.311
EPS	0.137	0.138
ENV	-0.115	-0.108
SOC	0.058	0.054
GOV	0.053	0.053
InMcap	0.515	0.456
Rep_Big	0.028	0.026
NonRep_Big	0.048	0.054
NonRep_Small	0.075	0.082
Rep_ES	-0.010	-0.021
NonRep_ES	-0.187	-0.155
ES_Big	0.060	0.064
Ind_S	0.002	0.003
Age	-0.064	-0.59
Rep_Y	0.527	0.545
No. of Observations	1210	1210

Table 19: Comparison of Regression coefficient OLS vs R essentials.

To ensure further robustness of the results, this study considers the possibility of endogeneity and exogeneity, omitted variable bias and reverse causality. Few studies (such as Li et al., 2018; Haryono et al., 2016; Attig et al., 2013; El Ghoul et al., 2011) have discussed endogeneity and exogeneity, omitted variable bias and reverse causality in their CSR and sustainability research. El Ghoul et al. (2011) investigated how corporate social responsibility affected the cost of equity finance by using panel data between 1992 to 2007 and identified that firm-level

corporate governance might have potential impacts both in cost of capital and CSR performance. On the other hand, Attig et al. (2013) investigated the impacts of CSR on credit rating using panel data between 1991 to 2010 and used financial performance as a potential endogenous variable. They argued financial performance could have impacted both CSR and credit rating. They have also used industry average CSR and firm-level initial value of CSR score as first-stage instruments to apply an instrumental variable technique. Li et al. (2018) investigated the impact of ESG disclosure on firm value focusing on CEO power. They followed Attig et al. (2013) model to address the omitted variables bias, endogeneity and exogeneity issues. Therefore, the literature followed the internal valuation technique. Li et al. (2018) used Tobin's Q as a proxy of firm value.

This study used market-based accounting valuation technique using Ohlson (1995) model following Hassel et al. (2005), Xu et al. (2007), Jifri and Citron (2009), Schadewitz and Niskala (2010), Berthelot et al. (2012), Laurenco et al. (2012), de Klerk and de Villiers (2012), Semenova and Hassel (2015), Lee et al. (2015), Mervelskemper and Streit (2017). This study used the market value of equity shares as dependent variables, while book value, earnings and sustainability performance score were the main independent variables. Unlike many other studies, this study used an actual sustainability score rather than a dummy score for sustainability disclosure. As part of the sustainability performance, this study runs the regression using environmental, social and governance sustainability performance scores instead of one sustainability score. The sustainability score is derived from ten sustainability matrices under environmental, social and governance pillars. Each of these sustainability matrices is independent and not dependent on the market value.

Attig et al. (2013) used financial performance as a potential endogenous variable in their internal valuation model. The model used in this study already comprises financial performance, which includes book value and earnings per share as independent variables. As Ohlson's (1995) model used a balance sheet approach to stock valuation, these two financial variables also comprise several other financial variables such as assets, liabilities, floating assets, leverage, earnings, price earning, profitability etc. Therefore, book value and earnings are independent of each sustainability pillar which is supported by most value relevance studies using Ohlson's (1995) model.

Additionally, Attig et al. (2013) used industry average CSR score and firm-level initial CSR score as instruments to use the instrumental variable technique on their 20 years of panel data. This study used environmentally sensitive industrial background and service industry as control variables while also using sustainability reputation as control variables for highly sustainable firms. This study only used data between 2017 and 2020; only four years did not make significant changes in the firm's sustainability performance. Therefore, the firm-level initial sustainability score is not applicable to use as an instrument for this study as each sustainability performance is independent. Additionally, based on the model and variables used in this study is free from endogeneity and exogeneity issues, while no instruments affect both dependent and independent variables. As a result, reverse casualty does not affect this regression results.

4.8. Summary

Sixteen independent variables were used in five regression models to analyse the direct and indirect impacts of corporate sustainability performance on the share price. This study tested 11 hypotheses covering eight broad areas that directly or indirectly affect the dependent variables. Eleven of these 12 hypotheses were accepted at a 99% or 95% confidence level, while one was rejected. The regression results and hypotheses suggest the effectiveness of the sustainability performance varies from firm to firm based on their relative size, industry background, reputation, and even on their age of listing. Therefore, there is no universal way to generalise the effectiveness of ESG sustainability across all firms.

Chapter Five: Discussions of the Findings

5.1. Introduction

This research aims to assess the value relevance of ESG sustainability performance for listed companies in the UK. The previous literature has revealed mixed and inconclusive results for the value relevance of sustainability performance. Thus, this study was motivated to collect sample data and then categorise them into several sub-samples. Companies from each sample had similar characteristics, such as similar sustainability performance and firm size. Thus, more than one distinct sample group has facilitated comparison while helping to conclude whether value relevance differs based on the characteristics of firms.

The literature suggests mixed and inconclusive results regarding the association between sustainability performance and share price (e.g., Baboukardos & Rimmel, 2016; Mervelskemper & Streit, 2017; Hassel et al., 2005). For the intended purpose, actual ESG sustainability performance information has been used, rather than only the binary variable for sustainability reporting. This study employed the widely used Ohlson (1995) model to run a regression to link non-financial and financial information with the share price. Corporate sustainability performance is used as a proxy for non-financial information. This study used ESG sustainability performance and individual environmental, social, and governance performance scores in the regression equation. This study has further extended the regression model to identify the effect of firm size, sustainability reputation, industry background and age of stock market listing on the sustainability firm value relationship.

Some previous studies have used the Dow Jones Sustainability Index (DJSI) to investigate the value relevance of being a DJSI member. From the extensive literature review, only a few studies have been found in which two groups of samples have been tested side by side to assess the sustainability value relevance. This study put FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies side by side to compare and contrast the sustainability performance and share price to conclude the ongoing debate of stock market effects. In addition, this study also compares and contrasts the value relevance of FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies.

To achieve the research objectives outlined in Chapter One, quantitative data were collected and analysed to test the hypotheses. The findings of the analysis are summarised, discussed, and evaluated in this chapter.

5.2. ESG performance

5.2.1. Summary of the findings

This study aims to assess the value relevance of ESG sustainability performance for UK-listed companies. Using Ohlson's (1995) regression model, this study found a significant relationship between ESG sustainability performance and market share price for the full sample. Additionally, this study also found a significant positive association for sub-sample FTSE100, Small-cap companies, FTSE4Good companies, and NonFTSE4Good companies. However, this study found a significant negative relationship between market share price and ESG sustainability performance for FTSE250 companies.

Thus, the results of this regression test suggest mixed findings, including positive associations and negative associations between market share price and ESG sustainability performance.

5.2.2. Discussions and evaluation of the findings

The full sample of this study comprises several distinct groups, each of which has homogeneous characteristics. The results found a negative association between market share price and ESG sustainability for FTSE250 companies and a positive association between market share price and ESG sustainability performance for FTSE100, Small-cap companies, FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies.

Previous studies support all possible types of associations between variables, including positive association, negative association, and no significant association between dependent and independent variables. The literature review indicates that initial studies have mostly shown negative or no association (see Margolis et al., 2009; Hassel et al., 2005). On the other hand, most recent studies incrementally support value creation theory (e.g., Budsaratagoon & Jitmaneeroj, 2021; Ahmed et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2015; Kaspereit & Lopatta, 2016). The positive association between market share price and ESG sustainability performance revealed the positive valuation for the share for FTSE100, Small-cap companies, FTSE4Good

companies, and NonFTSE4Good companies. Some recent studies (Budsaratragoon & Jitmaneeroj, 2021; Ahmed et al., 2019) have supported these findings. This positive stock valuation can be explained and understood through the context of stakeholder theory.

Incremental ESG sustainability performance can generate financial benefits by improving its relationship with internal and external stakeholders (Angelo & Irene, 2016). The stakeholder group considers incremental sustainability performance to be a reliable indication of implementing the environmental, social, and governance needs of the firm (Lys et al., 2015). As sustainability performance enhances the corporate reputation, it helps the company achieve an additional price for the share in the stock market. This positive synergic effect of corporate sustainability on share price indicates that a comprehensive and complete approach to sustainable business practices can improve stakeholder behaviour regarding environmental, social, and governance matters (Budsaratragoon & Jitmaneeroj, 2021). The positive association between share price and ESG sustainability can help corporate managers decide whether to incorporate sustainability practices. If yes, then to what extent should the firm adopt sustainability practices to maximise the positive gain in the stock market?

From a positive valuation perspective, corporate sustainability is viewed as a long-term risk-mitigating strategy embedded within the long-term goal (Fatemi et al., 2015). As a long-term strategy, implementing a sustainable approach costs resources immediately or in the short term to ensure favourable HR policy, good working conditions, and environmental safety. In the long term, these firms get two-fold benefits; first of all, they mitigate the related risk if, for any reason, government regulation changes (Fatemi et al., 2015). A higher sustainable firm will be in an excellent position to capitalise on regulation changes instantly. Second, they get the first-mover advantages while other firms struggle to implement the essential criteria through which firms can add additional value to their current existence (Fatemi et al., 2015).

Empirical evidence shows the short-term versus the long-term impact on the sustainability performance of a corporation. In the short term, establishing a sustainability approach within the corporate structure and behavioural practices requires considerable cost. A significant initial investment can negatively impact cash inflow and profitability (Bachoo et al., 2013). This downward pressure can negatively impact stock prices and company valuations (Fatemi et al., 2015). This could be the reason why in this study, sustainability performance has adverse

effects on the FTSE250 companies. Barnett (2007) revealed that a firm requires significant time to gain the capability to influence a wider stakeholder group. Therefore, there could be a time lag between the sustainability investment and the financial gain derived from sustainability. Barnett and Salomon (2011) suggest a U-shaped relationship between corporate social performance (CSP) and financial performance. Their finding also suggests that firms with low CSP perform better financially (measured by return on assets and net income) than those with moderate CSP; however, the highest CSP firm has the most successful financial performance.

This study aims to assess how stock prices fluctuate because of ESG sustainability performance. In this study, FTSE100 companies had the highest level of ESG sustainability performance. The average market capital for FTSE100 index companies is 12 times as high as the FTSE250 companies. From the analysis of this study, sustainability performance has a strong significant positive association with market share price for FTSE100, Small-cap and FTSE4Good companies, which supports the view of Ahmed et al. (2019). This finding revealed that strong sustainability performance creates value for the companies.

The results also suggest there is a strong significant negative association between sustainability performance and market share price. This finding indicates that sustainability performance diminishes the value of the FTSE250 companies. On the other hand, the FTSE250 companies have lower sustainability performance than FTSE100 companies but have much better sustainability records compared to Small-cap companies. To explain the sustainability impacts on the share price for FTSE250 companies, our finding supports Barnett and Salomon's (2011) U-Shape financial performance structure. The highest level of ESG sustainability performance creates additional stock market value, while companies performing at a lower level of ESG sustainability lose value in the stock market. This study analysed a sample group with the lowest level of sustainability performance and found positive stock market returns suggested by Barnett and Salomon (2011). However, among the sub-sample group, Small-cap companies reported the lowest sustainability performance.

Additionally, higher sustainability performance can reduce environmental, social, and governance risks and improve long-term reputation. In contrast, any incremental pressure on sustainability issues from governments, regulators, and pressure groups can be easily mitigated

(Fatemi et al., 2015). The linear information dynamics are not apparent in FTSE250 companies; in some cases, current expenditure signals future earnings while suppressing profitability (Lys et al., 2015). In the same way, if the firm is in a steady state in terms of profitability and market share price, the current constant state could result from past ESG sustainability activities. Corporate sustainability is a long-term and continuous journey; it cannot be achieved by setting up a one-time goal. Thus, current sustainability performance cannot be seen as value-enhancing in the present, but it pays off in the future (Lys et al., 2015).

5.2.3. Practical implications of the findings to the stakeholders

The overall findings of this study relating to ESG sustainability have several practical and managerial implications. Regression results revealed a significant positive association between market share price and ESG sustainability performance for FTSE100 and Small-cap companies. This study found a significant negative relationship between share price and ESG sustainability performance for FTSE250 companies. For FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, the ESG sustainability performance score provides further relevant information to the shareholder and investors in addition to the information provided by book value and earnings. Thus, these findings can help shareholders and investors better assess the share price using the ESG sustainability performance score and the book value and earnings per share. Using the ESG sustainability score, investors, shareholders, investment agents, broker houses, and investment intermediaries can now have a more precise and authentic stock valuation for the companies listed on the London Stock Exchange (O'Dwyer & Owen, 2005; Searcy & Elkhawas, 2012).

Corporate managers can use corporate sustainability performance and reports as a tool to minimise the information gap between the inside and the outside stakeholders (Martínez-Ferrero et al., 2016). These information gaps, called information asymmetry, deter investors from making the right investment decisions. On the other hand, corporate managers can use these research findings at a more advanced level, as ESG sustainability performance provides additional information to the market participants relating to the companies. ESG sustainability practices, performance, activities, and reporting can ensure the free flow of relevant information towards outside stakeholders (Healy & Palepu, 2001). Therefore, using ESG

sustainability activities, a corporate manager can reduce the information asymmetry between the corporation and outside stakeholders and reduce related costs arising from information asymmetry (Cho et al., 2013). Capital market inefficiencies can be minimised if information asymmetry is reduced, which can result in adverse selection and moral hazards.

From the overall value relevance of ESG sustainability information, this research has also found two opposing characteristics of ESG sustainability performance that have significant practical value in use. Results reported that better sustainability performance is positively associated with market share price for FTSE100 companies and Small-cap companies, while negatively associated with market share price for FTSE250 companies. To the best of my knowledge, this is one of the few studies that put more than two sample results side by side and compared them. The results revealed that ESG sustainability performance could not be used for every listed firm's value maximisation objectives. This finding has managerial implications, as ESG is not a tailor-made value maximisation tool for every market participant. ESG sustainability performance can help only the FTSE4Good companies to maximise the share price on the stock exchange.

On the other hand, ESG sustainability performance diminishes the firm's value for FTSE250 companies in the short run. Therefore, the decision-maker should not emphasise ESG sustainability investment to maximise firm value for FTSE250 companies in the short run. The literature suggests that sustainability investment generates positive stock market benefits in the long run (Mervelskemper & Streit, 2017), but it only creates additional costs in the short run. Thus, the corporation should only allocate funds to implement sustainability practices if it can continue these investments until it reaches the point where sustainability performance is rewarded (Budsaratagoon & Jitmaneroj, 2021). It is imperative to consider the initial negative impacts of sustainability investments and practices, whether a firm can afford to be sustainable, whether they can benefit from corporate sustainability, and whether they have enough resources to ensure sustainability. These results claimed that only the larger companies could enjoy the fruit of ESG sustainability as they have available resources and can ensure continuous investment in sustainability projects. Sustainability is not an automatic choice for every firm in the value-creating process.

The results revealed that the higher the sustainability performance, the lower the sustainability risk (Albuquerque et al., 2018). Environmental, social, and governance risks are a significant part of a firm's operational risk, as higher performance ensures greater transparency (Albuquerque et al., 2018). These findings have managerial and practical implications for corporate strategy. Previous research has suggested ESG sustainability performance as an operational risk management tool that can have significant impacts on the overall capital structure of a firm in regards to the cost of equity and cost of debt (see, for example, Albuquerque et al., 2018; Cai et al., 2016). Therefore, a firm can use better sustainability performance to signal lower overall risk through the mediating role of the capital structure to the stakeholders (Lys et al., 2015).

This risk mitigation perspective significantly impacts the cost of capital and debt (Ahmed et al., 2019; Cheng et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2015). A firm performing highly on ESG sustainability can collect equity finance at a lower price for two specific reasons. First, a lower risk profile requires a lower risk premium, and second, higher sustainability performance reduces information asymmetry, thus minimising agency cost (Ferris et al., 2017; Ng & Rezaee, 2015). Therefore, higher sustainability performance can ensure a lower cost of equity and lower cost of debt as the firm's ESG risks are widely spread. In addition, higher sustainability performance can put a finance manager in a stronger position to negotiate the interest rate when a firm decide to borrow.

The findings on ESG sustainability also have an important practical use for credit scoring agents and lenders. Traditionally, sustainability performance has not been integrated with financial and operational measures in relation to the firm's creditworthiness. Lenders can have different lending strategies, and some firms follow an aggressive lending strategy because of the higher interest rate. In recent days, corporate sustainability has attracted considerable consideration from every aspect of society, mainly because of climate change and climate-related risks. As better sustainability performance lowers the environmental, social, and governance risks, this matter should be integrated with a corporate credit score that reflects the actual risk, ensuring better ranking and more efficient resource allocation (Ye & Zhang, 2011).

On the other hand, some social and ethical investment funds prefer investing in low-risk, society-friendly companies (Borghesi et al., 2014). Following socially and environmentally responsible investment principles, the total investment fund expanded from USD \$13.3tn in 2012 to 21.4 tn in 2014 (Global Sustainable Investment Alliance, 2014). In that case, it will definitely be a considerable positive step for sustainable firms to be able to access a wide range of funds at a lower cost in a more objective way. If the sustainability risk-adjusted creditworthiness evaluation process is implemented, both the bank and social and ethical lenders quickly assess which firm meets the criteria in compliance with their lending strategy. If this creditworthiness evaluation process is implemented, society- and environment-friendly firms will benefit through a lower interest rate as they have high initial sustainability practice implementation costs (Heinkel et al., 2011). Therefore, ESG risk-adjusted credit scoring systems and performance measures could foster sustainable development among all stakeholders.

This study found that ESG sustainability performance is value-relevant to investors. It provides additional information to the market participant that is effective and useful for a more precise stock valuation. This finding carries practical use for regulators and the capital market. Sustainability reporting is still voluntary and primarily unregulated, although some reporting guidelines, such as the GRI reporting framework, have been developed in recent years (Plumlee et al., 2015). In the last two decades, the overall attitude towards ethical, social, and environmentally friendly business practices has grown significantly because of increasing global warming, social inequality, and unsafe working conditions in third-world countries (Albuquerque et al., 2018).

To improve information flow and transparency, regulators should make it compulsory to report sustainability activities. This study revealed that all levels of sustainability performance (lower or higher) carry relevant information for investors and shareholders. Still, not every listed company on the London Stock Exchange reports sustainability performance. Therefore, regulators can make sustainability performance reporting mandatory to supply more relevant information for decision usefulness. At the same time, the sustainability performance-adjusted capital market index for all the listed companies on the London Stock Exchange can satisfy the investors' sustainability information needs and foster sustainable development to meet global challenges such as global warming, climate change, and gender inequality.

5.3. Environmental performance

5.3.1. Summary of the findings

The regression results revealed that environmental performance is significantly and positively associated with share price for FTSE4Good firms while significantly and negatively associated with the full sample, FTSE100, and FTSE250 companies. At the same time, no significant association was found between Small-cap companies and NonFTSE4Good companies.

5.3.2. Discussions and evaluation of the findings

This study investigated the valuation effects of corporate environmental performance as part of firms' overall ESG sustainability performance. Using Ohlson (1995), this study aimed to identify the impacts of sustainability performance on market share price through regression analysis. The results suggest environmental performance is positively and significantly associated with the market share price for FTSE4Good companies while negatively and significantly associated with the share price for the full sample, FTSE100, and FTSE250 companies. Thus, their environmental performance has positive valuation impacts on the FTSE4Good companies while negatively impacting the overall corporate value for the FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies. Therefore, their environmental performance has incremental explanatory power to explain the share price variation for FTSE4Good and FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies.

Results suggest a negative association between environmental performance and market share price for FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies, which indicates investors and shareholders do not value higher environmental performance. This argument was first revealed by Hassel et al. (2005) after investigating Swedish firms. The fundamentals of this argument were that it follows the cost-centred view that higher environmental performance is costly for the corporation, thus adversely affecting profitability, and so does firm value. Hassel et al. (2005) were one of the first studies to investigate environmental performance and its valuation effect. They have also suggested three reasons why better environmental performance diminishes a firm's value.

Hassel et al. (2005) first stated that investors perceived environmental reporting as a whitewashing tool for window-dressing financial performance. Second, investors perceive that environmental activities are performed at the expense of their profit, which investors oppose, as an expected reduction of profit does not reduce the risk. Third, the market focuses on the short term; investors do not consider long-term environmental information when making an investment decision.

Thus, investors are unlikely to reward better environmental performance of companies that do not belong to the prestigious sustainability index or have a widely accepted sustainability reputation. However, at the same time, better environmental performance is highly appreciated by investors in FTSE4Good companies. In terms of firm size and floating cash, FTSE4Good companies possess a stronger position and can raise additional funds when needed compared to their counterpart FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies. Ye and Zhang (2011) found that the sum of the funds invested for environmental and ethical betterment does not seem large enough to benefit from high environmental performance. Their initial investigation resulted in a negative relationship between environmental performance and firm value.

Environmental performance works as a subordinate or even a supplement to financial information when corporations make buying decisions (Budsaratragoon & Jitmaneeroj, 2021). This study revealed that large corporations are penalised severely by investors for not having good sustainability practices, while investors punish small corporations with the same sustainability and environmental status less severely. The coefficient of negative environmental effects for the FTSE100 companies is three times higher compared to the FTSE250 companies. The bigger the size of the firm, the bigger the negative impact.

Some studies have been conducted very specifically to assess the value relevance of those issues, such as pollution control information, toxic metal emissions, and adoption of global environmental standards; in most of the cases, mixed results were found. Some of the recent studies were conducted across countries and legislative regimes, but ended up with mixed findings. Our study found both positive and negative associations between environmental performance and market share prices. Our findings suggest that different corporations have different stock market implications for similar environmental sustainability performance.

However, environmental performance is value-relevant to investors (Chen et al., 2015; Eccles et al., 2014). Following agency theory, environmental performance conveys signals to the investor regarding the company and works as a valuation tool (Lys et al., 2015). Environmental performance was perceived as a positive catalyst for the listed companies in the FTSE4Good Index while negatively fuelling the firms' value for FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies.

5.3.3. Practical implications of the findings to the stakeholders

Environmental issues affect every living being and habitat on Earth. At the same time, environmental issues are the biggest and most expensive challenge to ensure sustainable development without compromising the well-being of our future generation (Barter & Bebbington, 2009). The findings on environmental performance have several managerial and practical implications. This study found a significant positive association between market share price and environmental performance for FTSE4Good companies. At the same time, a significant negative relationship was found between market share price and environmental performance for FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies.

Similar to the combined ESG performance, environmental performance carries value-relevant information for the capital market participants. Therefore, environmental performance can facilitate a more precise and authentic stock valuation for firms, investors, shareholders, lenders, and banks (Braam et al., 2016). This study suggests that corporate environmental performance provides extra information to information users, and management should use environmental performance reporting to reduce information asymmetry between insiders and outsiders. Environmental performance reporting will help the firm to reduce costs related to information asymmetry, while investors and shareholders can avoid adverse selection (Cho et al., 2013). Therefore, the firm can enjoy a lower cost of equity and a lower cost of debt through better managing environmental activities (Ahmed et al., 2019; El Ghoul et al., 2011).

Environmental risks are the most significant part of the ESG risk, as they cause two-fold damage, one for the environment and its inhabitants, and the other for the business and its reputation (Sharfman & Fernando, 2008). Issues like the carbon footprint are always at the top of the government's priority to control because of the increasingly severe and frequent natural calamities causing enormous damage. The extent of reputational risk is greater for

environmental issues because of growing media attention and changes in individual perception in the last two decades (Islam & Deegan, 2010). The magnitude of the adverse effects of environmental issues is significantly higher than the positive effects. Therefore, managing environmental risk should always be the top priority of corporate managers. Environmental risk can be mitigated and managed through better environmental performance (Banerjee & Linstead, 2009).

Although ESG reporting is still voluntary, delivering better environmental performance is a demand from environmental stakeholders, and it is no longer an optional choice (Blowfield & Murray, 2014). If environmental issues are not managed properly they can have catastrophic effects and cost a significant amount of money (such as BP's Gulf of Mexico oil spill), probably much more than regular environmental safety measures would have cost.

Environmental protection is urgent but requires significant cash outlay and regular maintenance (Sharfman & Fernando, 2008). The results suggest that the shareholders of the FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies treat environmental spending as a cost that consequently diminishes a firm's value. However, the results of the environmental performance of FTSE4Good companies proved that consistent, regular, and better environmental performance management enhances a firm's value. Thus, the management of FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies can learn from FTSE4Good companies, since FTSE4Good companies are consistently turning environmental costs into added value for the firms.

Environmental protection is now discussed at every global leaders' summit. Many countries, including the EU, have declared a climate emergency and set a target to meet net-zero carbon by 2050. The UK government has banned the sale of new diesel cars by 2030 (*The Guardian*, 2021), which signals how seriously the government treats environmental issues. Rather than reacting to the government declaration, industry representatives and associations can set up proactive work plans to tackle stricter government environmental protection measures. Environmental performance can be used as a means for industry representatives to lobby with regulators and government agencies.

Environmental performance can be used as an effective tool to enhance a corporate reputation as a green company (Heinkel et al., 2011). A corporate reputation as a green company helps the firm create a positive image among the stakeholders, while putting them in a strong position

for any corporate negotiation. Barnett and Salomon (2011) found that green companies have a higher Tobin's q ratio (market-to-book value of share) than neutral companies. Therefore, environmental performance can enhance a firm's worth if it manages it consistently and reasonably.

5.4. Social performance

5.4.1. Summary of the findings

As part of overall ESG sustainability, this study investigated the valuation effects of corporate social performance and whether it is significant to investors. Through regression analysis using Ohlson (1995), this study aimed to identify sustainability and social performance impacts on market share prices. The results suggest that social performance is positively and significantly associated with the market share price for the full sample. This relationship also exists positively and significantly for FTSE250 companies. However, no significant relationship has been identified for the case of FTSE100 companies and Small-cap companies.

Similarly, social performance was positively and significantly associated with NonFTSE4Good companies but not with FTSE4Good companies. Therefore, social performance has the incremental explanatory power of the share price variation for FTSE250 companies. Thus, enhanced social performance has positive valuation effects for the FTSE250, but no evidence was found that social performance has any valuation effects on the corporation or the share price for FTSE100 and Small-cap companies.

5.4.2. Discussion and evaluation of the findings

As a business operates within society, any corporate activities detrimental to society will be punished somehow (Godfrey et al., 2009). At the same time, dealing with stakeholders and implementing corporate social strategies in a financially rewarding manner is a major challenge. Social activity receives less attention than environmental activities, especially when these are predominantly adverse or detrimental. Bad performance (below-average performance) carries a higher magnitude of negative valuation effect than the magnitude of good performance on positive valuation effect. Previous studies have suggested mixed results

regarding the relationship between social performance and corporate financial performance (Margolis et al., 2009; Garcia-Castro et al., 2010; Husted & Salazar, 2006).

Some early research, such as Brammer et al. (2006), reported a negative association between social performance and financial performance. One of the reasons could be a time lag between CSR spending and implementation and financial rewards (Budsaratragoon & Jitmaneeroj, 2021). Therefore, the earliest research on sustainability or CSR performance found negative stock market returns and financial performance. An initial investment in sustainability results in reduced profitability, while the firm could not reduce its cost of capital. Similar to the results for FTSE100 and Small-cap companies, Humphrey et al. (2010) found no significant differences in stock market returns for UK firms.

One of the very early studies (McGuire et al., 1988) stated that the risk mitigation effect of CSR was solely firm-specific, and CSR policies were unlikely to reduce a company's vulnerability to systematic risk. However, in recent times, Ahmed et al.'s (2019) findings support the findings of this study that investors in the UK pay more attention to CSR and consider corporate social practice as a risk mitigation factor. Sharfman and Fernando (2008) and El Ghouli et al. (2010) reported that high levels of CSR firms enjoy a lower cost of capital. Therefore, higher social performance eventually reduces the borrowing costs for the firm. Thus, CSR performance is perceived as having a lower systematic risk, which, in turn, could affect valuation through lower discount rates and the cost of capital (Sun et al., 2010; El Ghouli et al., 2011).

This study investigated the valuation effects of social performance, especially stock valuation through market share price. A large part of the previous literature analysed the relationship between CSR performance and a firm's financial performance, while only a few looked at the valuation effects. Similar to the research findings of this study, Guenter et al. (2011) reported that eco-efficient US firms have a higher Tobin's q ratio than eco-inefficient firms. Tobin's q ratio is calculated as the market value of total assets divided by the book value of total assets. However, Fernando et al. (2010) found that both green and toxic firms have a lower Tobin's q ratio than environmentally neutral firms. This research result revealed that social performance carries valuable information to the investors, and investors' willingness to pay an extra price for the equity share of higher social performing FTSE100&250 firms.

Spending on corporate social and CSR strategies is similar to investing in intangibles (Fombrun, 2005), creating long-term benefits. Thus, investing in CSR signals future earnings (Lys et al. 2015). The fact that corporate social performance has no significant impact on the share price for FTSE100 and Small-cap companies could be because management prefers to prioritise environmental issues, as environmental wrongdoing has a severe negative impact on both the planet and corporate stock price. The magnitude of environmental investment is relatively larger; therefore, FTSE250 companies would rather focus on social spending than environmental issues, as they have less floating cash, available resources, media scrutiny, and environmental footprints. Therefore, relatively smaller firms tend to focus on social performance, as placing equal priority to other sustainability elements may not always be possible.

5.4.3. Practical implications of the findings

The findings relating to the effect of social sustainability performance on share prices have several strategic and practical implications for management. The results revealed that social performance is significantly associated with share price for FTSE250 companies and the full sample. Still, there is no significant relationship between social sustainability performance and share price for FTSE100 and Small-cap companies. Based on these findings, the management would choose which elements of ESG sustainability they should emphasise to maximise share price. Clearly, the social sustainability performance of FTSE250 companies can help maximise their shareholders' value. On the other hand, better environmental performance enhances the share price of FTSE4Good companies. Although in ESG sustainability practice, environmental, social, and governance elements are equally essential to ensure sustainable development, the management of FTSE250 companies should emphasise the social aspects to maximise the firm value.

Social sustainability performance is regarded as value-relevant to investors and shareholders. Using social sustainability information, investors can more precisely value the share price in addition to the valuation effort using book value and earnings. At the same time, by supplying social sustainability information, the firm can minimise information asymmetry and agency differences (Martínez-Ferrero et al., 2016). At the same time, outstanding social sustainability

performance can signal the increased capacity of potential investors to obtain revenue-generating opportunities and minimise the chance of future fines and lawsuits (Lys et al., 2015). The management of FTSE250 companies can also use social sustainability performance as a mechanism to reduce social and political risk (Gramlich & Finster, 2013) while building a social sustainability reputation, which will eventually get paid through higher customer loyalty and lower discounting rates in stock valuation (Malik, 2014).

5.5. Governance performance

5.5.1. Summary of the findings

Overall, governance sustainability performance is significantly associated with the full sample's share price. However, considering all the sub-samples, no significant association was found for FTSE100 companies and Small-cap companies, but there is a significant negative association between share price for FTSE250 companies. In addition, the share price is positively and significantly associated with both FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies.

5.5.2. Discussions and evaluation of the findings

Corporate governance is an extensive part of modern business that includes many aspects of corporate issues. Ownership structure, board characteristics, corporate accountability, integrity and ethical behaviour, disclosure and transparency are the broad areas that belong to corporate governance. The regression results of the research suggest that a significant association exists between governance performance and market share price for the full sample, FTSE4Good companies and FTSE250 companies. However, there is a significant negative association between share price and governance performance for FTSE250 companies.

On the other hand, no significant association was found between governance performance and share price for FTSE100 and Small-cap companies. This regression result supports Talal and Mostafa (2014), who found no statistically significant effect of the principle of corporate governance on the share price of firms listed on the Amman Stock Exchange. Talal and Mostafa (2014) investigated three aspects of corporate governance and their subsequent effect on share

prices. These three principles of corporate governance were the equal treatment of shareholders, the responsibilities of the board of directors, and the existence of an effective corporate governance framework. The findings of this study differed from some of the recent research (e.g., Al-Kassar & Al-Nidawiy, 2014; Amran et al., 2014); however, most research studies examined just part of corporate governance, such as audit committees, board diversity, women on the board, and internal control systems.

Listed companies manage to be more actively involved with fulfilling regulations, implementing good practices, and reporting actions and outcomes to cope with stakeholder pressure. In this study, the hypotheses were tested using an overall governance performance score and positive valuation effects on the share price were found for the full sample, which indicates that shareholders do appreciate best governance practices.

This study found a significant negative association between governance performance and share price for FTSE250 companies. One of the reasons could be ownership structure. Ownership structure has significant effects on the shape of corporate governance as well as overall sustainability. As part of corporate governance, Uwuigbe (2013) found a negative association between a firm's share price and ownership structure, and a positive relationship between share price and audit committee. One of the reasons for this negative relationship is called concentrated ownership or institutional shareholding. In the UK, 81% of market capital is controlled by institutional investors (Office for National Statistics, 2018). Amran and Haniffa (2011) revealed in their research that concentrated ownership, holding 20% or more voting rights, impedes implementing best governance practices, as they already have access to the information they need. They consider additional best practice guidance and reporting unnecessary and a waste of money. Any additional expenditure to promote the best governance practice is treated as a cost rather than an investment. At the same time, dispersed ownership demands a reduction in information asymmetry through best governance practices and reporting (Amran et al., 2014). The regression result suggests governance performance is negatively associated with market share price, which means that the better the governance performance, the lower the share price.

The regression revealed that no significant relationship exists between governance performance and share price for FTSE100 and Small-cap companies. This study focused on UK companies listed on the London Stock Exchange. The UK is the fifth-largest economy globally, while the LSE is one of the most developed stock markets associated with an overall robust governance regime for listed companies. Kolk and Perego (2010) reported that when a firm operates with a strong stakeholder orientation and strong governance enforcement, it is likely to have fewer impacts on its governance activities because of the overall high governance standard for the whole system. They also concluded that firms operating with greater stakeholder orientation but weaker governance are more likely to attach assurance statements to their sustainability reports.

The other explanation for the negative association and non-association with governance performance could be the short-term perspective of the initial investment. As mentioned previously, sustainability generates long-term benefits, while any investment diminishes its value in the short run (Budsaratragoon & Jitmaneroj, 2021). Consequently, any sustainability or governance expenditure triggers a negative stock market reaction. Like ESG sustainability, governance performance could follow the same U-shaped relationship between corporate social performance (CSP) and financial performance that Barnett and Salomon (2011) suggested. Barnett and Salomon's (2011) findings suggested that firms that perform low in sustainability show better performance financially (measured by return on asset and net income) than those with a moderate governance performance level.

5.5.3. Practical implications of the findings

Similar to environmental and social performance, governance performance plays an equally significant role in affecting the share price for the overall sample, particularly for FTSE4Good companies. As the regression results suggest, governance performance does not equally value relevance for each company. Management needs to develop a long-term strategy to create positive value for the firm. However, short-term cash outlay may cause some negative impacts on the share price, as happened for FTSE250 companies. It strengthens the protection of shareholders' and stakeholders' rights. Therefore, if a firm prioritises ESG sustainability activities, governance issues should also deal with environmental and social issues.

Based on the results, governance performance provided meaningful decision-useful information to the investors. In addition, to bring about the ESG synergic effect, the firm should focus on each element of ESG sustainability. Governance performance could affect environmental and social performance, negatively impacting share prices. Good governance can still reduce agency conflicts and information asymmetry and increase overall ESG sustainability for the firm.

5.6. Corporate size effects on sustainability and share price

5.6.1. Summary of the findings

The regression results revealed that firm size has a significant positive association with the market share price. However, descriptive statistics reported that the FTSE100 companies are several times bigger than other forms of sample groups, and there is a strong connection between a firm's sustainability performance and firm's financial performance. Big companies are more likely to negatively impact share prices if they do not have outstanding sustainability performance and reputation. On the other hand, relatively small firms face lower negative impacts on the share price for their lower sustainability performance.

5.6.2. Discussions and evaluation of the findings

In this study, firm size emerged as one of the essential elements that had visible impacts on investors' decision making. As mentioned earlier, the average size of the FTSE100 company is almost several times as large as the FTSE250 sample companies. Eventually, only larger companies adopt the approach to be regarded as the most sustainable companies. Firm size significantly impacts adoption and the extent of sustainability performance. Firm size possesses higher corporate visibility and causes more significant impacts on Earth. Higher visibility and effects are most likely to create more extensive stakeholder scrutiny and pressure (Fortanier et al., 2011; Gallo & Jones-Christensen, 2011).

This study revealed that firm size measured by market capitalisation is significantly and positively associated with market share price. Thus, the higher the firm size, the greater the share price. To facilitate the comparison between the large companies, this study classified firm size into two categories of large companies, Rep_Big, those companies that are large in size and also hold a sustainability reputation, and NonRep_Big, which are large but do not hold such a sustainability reputation. The regression result suggests that Rep_Big companies are significantly and positively associated with share price. At the same time, a NonRep_Big company's share price is negatively associated with corporate size.

However, the negative association is not statistically significant at the 5% significance level. Thus, investors will punish ebig companies if they do not have sustainability practices in place. At the same time, this study also ran a regression to assess the firm size effects of small companies on their share price. Thus, this study used a binary variable, NonRep_Small; these companies have less than the median market capitalisation but do not hold a sustainability reputation.

The regression result revealed that smaller firm size positively impacts share price and is also statistically significant. Both NonRep_Big and NonRep_Small companies do not hold a sustainability reputation, but only NonRep_Big companies have negative impacts on their market share price because of their corporate visibility and relative effects on the environment and society. Media exposures are always higher for large corporations, and so does corporate reputational risk (Li et al., 2017) because of bad publicity. At the same time, when the business is involved in a supply chain business-to-business, it is less likely to have reputational risk because of its less interaction with consumers (Li et al., 2017). On the other hand, the interaction between businesses and consumers always puts extra pressure on them to be more sustainable (Groves et al., 2011). Another critical factor is brand visibility; large corporations are likely to have better and more established brand visibility in society (Nikolaeva & Bicho, 2011). Therefore, poor sustainability performance can lead to significant pressure on management and downward pressure on stock prices.

5.6.3. Practical implications of the findings to the stakeholders

The literature shows that firm size is one of the main determinants of sustainability behaviour and performance (Kuzer and Uyar, 2017). Because of corporate visibility, large companies are always under the radar of the media and society (Islam & Deegan, 2010). Therefore, a big company's sustainability performance strongly affects the share price. These results revealed that big companies' share prices suffer significantly if their sustainability performance is not up to the top tier.

The findings have several managerial implications for the companies. The board must take care of sustainability; otherwise, the shareholders will lose their investment. Corporate sustainability practice is an essential element for big and visible companies. If the firm maintains outstanding sustainability performance, it will help to push the corporate value up, but if the firm does not have sustainability performance up to the desired level, then the share price will suffer heavily (Gallo and Jones-Christensen, 2011).

On the other hand, small companies have less severe impacts on share prices because of their substandard sustainability performance. Therefore, similar sustainability performance has different impacts on big and small companies. This variation arises because of varying levels of stakeholders' expectations, corporate visibility, and media attention (Groves et al., 2011). The literature also suggests that when a firm deals with end-user or direct consumers, it can have higher stakeholder expectations and bigger brand visibility. Therefore, the corporate manager of big companies and those companies that directly interact with consumers and end customers must consider keeping up their outstanding sustainability performance; otherwise, the share price will suffer in the capital market. Corporate sustainability is a must-needed corporate element whose presence makes little positive difference in stock price, but its absence makes significant changes in the negative direction for big companies (Li et al., 2017). Therefore, management should always focus on corporate sustainability to keep up with the long-term positive stock valuation effects.

Sustainability performance is treated as a current signal for future growth prospects (Ahmed et al., 2019). If a firm cannot ensure an outstanding sustainability practice within the organisation, it will never culminate in share price and the firm value. The firm must ensure higher sustainability performance to avail the best stock market benefit (Barnett & Salomon, 2011)

and to ensure a positive stock price effect of sustainability effects. However, at the same time, growing smaller companies should also emphasise sustainability performance, although they have less severe negative impacts on the share price for their substandard sustainability performance.

5.7. Sustainability reputation

5.7.1. Summary of the findings

The regression results revealed that sustainability reputation is significantly and positively associated with the market share price. At the same time, the market share price of a large firm suffers to a greater extent if they do not have as good a sustainability reputation compare to small firm.

5.7.2. Discussions and evaluation of the findings

Reputation has emerged as one of the very effective intangible assets for modern corporations, as it provides sustainable competitive advantages (Robert & Dowling, 2002). There is a difference in the market valuation of firms with or without a sustainability reputation. Corporate reputation allows firms to communicate with broad stakeholders regarding product quality, commitments, and the capability to create value. The regression results suggest that sustainability reputation is significantly and positively associated with the market share price. Building a sustainability reputation is hard; only the very best company belongs to those levels. Membership in sustainability indices, such as the Dow Jones Sustainability Index (DJSI), has proved valuable to investors. Companies with a higher sustainability reputation are likely to have better relationships with stakeholders, such as customers, investors, bankers, and competitors (Claudia et al., 2015). Schnitz and Epstein (2005, p.329) summarise the benefits of corporate sustainability as ‘may facilitate complex, long-term stakeholder management which, in turn, ought to enhance a firm’s ability to outperform against its competitors, either by increasing revenues or reducing costs’.

In contrast, a firm of the same size without a sustainability reputation has a negative regression coefficient, meaning its share is sold at a lower price than it should be. A sustainability reputation offers better access to finance and attracts investors (Lopez et al., 2007). FTSE4Good Index membership is a benchmark of corporate sustainability in the UK that can help track performance compared to its competitors. Submission to the sustainability index helps improve internal reporting processes and innovation (Searcy & Elkhawas, 2012).

Scarlet and Kelly (2010) noted that when a firm fills out application for membership of sustainability indices (such as DJSI and FTSE4Good), it helps the firm identify improvement areas. The DJSI website (DJSI, 2011) claims the feedback report they provide to the individual firm is beneficial, as ‘Companies often use the feedback report from the SAM Corporate Sustainability Assessment to identify gaps and initiate improvements in their business practices, and a company’s relative ranking in the relevant DJSI industry sector allows it to effectively compare its sustainability performance with that of its main competitors.’ Although sustainable benefits are hard to quantify, reputational benefits are frequently cited in the corporate sustainability literature (Weber, 2008; Kolk, 2010). Surroca et al. (2010) noted that their investment in sustainability leads to differences in a firm’s performance because of the difficulty of replicating the reputational value in the short term. Thus, sustainability performance and reputation positively affect employee motivation, commitment, and loyalty to the firm (Brammer et al., 2007). Therefore, companies can save a large part of the recruitment and training costs and increase productivity (Vitaliano, 2010).

Companies with a better sustainability reputation enjoy reduced implicit and explicit costs of the contract with wider stakeholders, including government, suppliers, and community representatives (Liston-Hayes & Ceton, 2009). Therefore, investment in sustainability practices builds the reputation of best corporate behaviour and sends positive signals to investors and other stakeholders. In addition to sustainable investment, FTSE4Good companies gain the reputation of being an industry leader in some critical strategic areas, such as financial, environmental, social, and governance issues (Robinson et al., 2011). The analysis of this research suggests that a sustainability reputation has significant value relevance to investors as the traditional financial information has limited capacity to forecast future risks and prospects, as all the data are related to the past.

In recent years, corporate competitiveness mainly depends on knowledge-based intangible resources that are not present in traditional financial statements. The demand for sustainability reporting and indices increases over time, as it stays unreported in the financial statement. Thus, the value relevance of financial statement information declines over time due to the increasing importance of intangible assets in the value creation process (Lourenço, 2014).

A sustainability reputation leads a company to lower economic uncertainty and better predictable earnings, consequently reducing investors' risk. Sustainability practices offer better marketability, making such firms more attractive to investors over firms with a lower sustainability performance (Malik, 2014). It helps to anticipate future earnings changes and reduces the variability in cash flow (Hussainey & Salama, 2010). Thus, sustainability reputation now significantly enhances firm's value through its impacts on a firm's risk profile, including but not limited to regulatory, litigatory, supply chain, product, technological, environmental, and physical risks (Starks, 2009).

5.7.3. Practical implication of the findings

The results suggest that corporate sustainability reputation is positively and significantly associated with the share price. Corporate sustainability reputation involves higher sustainability performance over a long period of time, which ensures lower sustainability risk, lower uncertainty, lower cost of capital, lower cost of debt, and a strong bargaining position (Malik, 2014). Corporate sustainability practice is a long-term journey that requires consistent planning, constant effort, regular investment, and gradual performance improvement. Building a sustainable reputation requires long-term time plans and cannot be developed quickly (Lourenço et al., 2014). Conversely, a single accident or negative publicity can soon ruin a firm's sustainability reputation.

Findings on corporate sustainability reputation have important practical and managerial implications. Inclusion in leading sustainability indices, such as DJSI and the FTSE4Good Index, signifies prestige and is the result of long-term sustainability practices (Lourenço et al., 2014). This shows that a sustainability reputation adds additional value for the corporation. Investors and shareholders are willing to offer additional share premiums when they buy the

share and are willing to accept less return from their investment. Corporate sustainability benefits surpass initial investment and time expenditure (Lundgren, 2011). Once the sustainability practice project is initiated, the board should continue investing and gradually improve its performance to develop a long-term sustainability reputation and enjoy the additional share premium for sustainability.

Sustainability practices and firm size are interrelated. Outstanding sustainability performance helps achieve the best possible stock price in the capital market while lowering the cost of capital and borrowing and keeping the corporate risk profile low. Therefore, the best sustainability performance always offers the best benefit from sustainability (Barnett & Salomon, 2011).

Sustainability leadership can have the power to change the external perception of reputation, help the firm generate extra cash flow, and signal long-term prospects to the investors (Hussainey & Salama, 2010). On the other hand, corporate size helps a firm achieve the highest sustainability recognition and reputation through gradual and constant investment, policy implementation, and brand visibility. Therefore, the management and the board of directors of the listed companies should emphasise building a sustainability reputation to get the best possible value for their share from the capital market, as they already have a strong presence in society and brand visibility.

5.8. Industry background and its effect on sustainability and share price

5.8.1. Summary of the findings

The regression results of this study found that an environmentally sensitive industrial background is significantly and negatively associated with the share price. At the same time, the negative impacts of operating in sensitive industries are higher for companies with no sustainability reputations. Lower sustainability companies have a heavier negative impact on their share prices when operating in environmentally sensitive industries.

On the other hand, there is no statistical evidence that the service industry background is either negatively or positively associated with the share price. Large companies mitigate their negative impacts on share prices through environmental recovery, but this relationship is not statistically significant.

5.8.2. Discussions and evaluation of the findings

Based on the regression results of this study, an industrial background with a harmful environmental impact has a significant negative impact on the market share. Industrial affiliation and the firm's sustainability performance can be explained through legitimacy theory (Legendre & Coderre, 2013; Burgwal & Vieira, 2014; Braam et al., 2016). Industrial affiliation is strongly linked to the disclosure of sustainability information through reporting (Skouloudis et al., 2014). At the same time, management is motivated to report this information as it is likely to harm the environment; as a result, the firm is expected to face stricter regulation (Liu & Anbumozhi, 2009). Therefore, it is in the firm's interest to disclose their sustainability information to attract a positive impression from stakeholders. Burgwal and Vieira (2014) suggested that environmentally sensitive companies disclose sustainability reports to ease stakeholder pressure and protect themselves from regulators' tougher restrictions. Despite having a higher sustainability performance and disclosing all the necessary information to the stakeholders, these firms still cannot prevent negative impacts on their stock prices because of their industrial background.

Stakeholders have higher expectations of a better sustainability-performing company. Therefore, higher sustainability-performing companies get a higher stock price than lower-performance companies (Braam et al., 2016). Likewise, firms operating in environmentally high-impact industries are likely to have bigger environmental impacts. Thus, higher sustainability performance creates higher stakeholder expectations; however, when the same firm operates in environmentally sensitive industries, it demoralises the stakeholders' expectations. Therefore, the negative impact of operating in high-impact industries reduces the positive effects of a better sustainability reputation. This negative impact is higher for non-reputed firms compared to reputed firms, as the reputed firm has better sustainability practices in place. This study suggests that the negative effect on the share price for operating in

environmentally high-impact industries for non-reputed firms is almost twice as high as for reputed firms. The regression results show that higher sustainability performance and operating in environmentally sensitive sectors conflict with each other.

Corporate sustainability is an effective mechanism for putting things right for the business, environment, and society. The bigger the operation, the higher the environmental impact, and the bigger the sustainability investment required to ensure sustainability. At the same time, operations in environmentally highly impacted industries such as mining, oil and gas, energy, construction, and tobacco are obstacles to achieving sustainability (Braam et al., 2016). As a result of increased fear and uncertainty and the related risk of extensive operations, non-reputed companies suffer the most comprehensive stock price devaluation because of their large operations in high-impact industries.

As mentioned earlier, reputed companies are at least twice as large on average as non-reputed companies. Because of their relatively small size, non-reputed companies are likely to have a smaller environmental footprint and require lower environmental recovery costs and sustainability investments. This in turn results in severe negative impacts on the share price. On the other hand, reputed companies have less severe negative impacts on their share prices despite operating in environmentally high-impact industries.

This study tested separate regression to check whether large companies operate in environmentally high-impact industries differently from smaller ones. The regression result revealed that large companies manage the impact of industrial background better to ease the adverse effects than smaller companies. Large companies are likely to have more floating cash and available resources for environmental recovery and sustainability investment, which eventually offer competitive advantages over smaller companies (Legendre & Coderre, 2013). Therefore, through sound environmental strategies using available resources, large corporations reduce the negative impacts of operating in environmentally high-impact industries.

5.8.3. Practical implications of the findings

Operation in high-impact sectors is one of the biggest challenges on the way to achieving corporate sustainability. An environmentally sensitive industrial background is negatively and significantly associated with its share price. Investors expect to pay less when they offer to buy a share of a company that operates in the oil and gas, tobacco, mining, and construction industries. Tobacco and alcohol cause many health hazards; therefore, these companies will never be sustainable for society, as their products cause enormous damage.

Corporate managers and boards of directors should consider several practical implications of these research findings. Operation in high-impact industries requires a higher cost of capital (El Ghouli et al., 2011); therefore, raising further capital and access to additional finance is expensive. At the same time, these firms are unlikely to generate a sustainability reputation and benefit from being sustainable. In addition, these firms are likely to face frequent and tough policy changes, and they are always at higher political and environmental risk (Sharfman & Fernando, 2008). Therefore, management should consider diversifying part of their operations out of the high-impact industries to balance the whole business portfolio and overall group risk profile.

On the other hand, investors, investment banks, lenders, investment consortiums, and other firms should reconsider before making any further investment decisions for businesses that operate in environmentally highly impacted industries. Additional investments can further damage their existing sustainability reputation, resulting in the devaluation of their shares. At the same time, the overall riskiness of the whole business portfolio will be increased, while brand loyalty can be affected.

The negative impacts of operating in industries with a high environmental impact are more severe than the positive stock market impacts of being sustainable. The negative effects are less severe for firms that have a sustainability reputation, possibly because of a lower environmental footprint, smaller brand visibility, and lower customer interaction. As far as the firm value and share price are concerned, investors should prioritise smaller firms rather than large firms if they need to choose high-impact industries to ensure higher investment gain. However, further investment in environmentally high-impact industries ultimately threatens sustainable development.

Although the association is not statistically significant, large firms that operate in high-impact industries can positively turn share prices through additional sustainability efforts and recovery agendas. Therefore, management should continue consistent and further sustainability recovery efforts to ease the negative impacts on the capital market and possibly gain a positive value-relevance effect.

5.9. Age of firm's stock market listing

5.9.1 Summary of the findings

The firm's age is negatively and significantly associated with the share price. Young firms enjoy a stock market premium compared to firms listed some time ago. The research results also revealed that comparatively newer firms perform better in the sustainability index.

5.9.2. Discussions and evaluation of the findings

The stock market listing requires maintaining specific procedures to ensure high-quality shares are traded in the stock market and uphold the reputation of the stock exchange. Age is one of the determinants of stock price, particularly for the initial public offering (IPO) price. Prior literature suggests investment in IPOs is not a wise decision, as the firm underperforms for at least the first three years compared to older firms. Therefore, investing in a newer firm is not an attractive decision. The research results disagreed with this argument and found that relatively young companies in the stock market attract higher share prices than older firms.

However, a company can be formed many years before it is listed in the share market. Moore (2019) claimed that the age effect is real for most firms, but the best performers are those above the median in age but not in the oldest quartile; he classed these as adult firms rather than seniors. Borghesi et al. (2014) claimed that female CEOs, younger CEOs, and managers tend to invest more in sustainability because of their altruistic approach. On the other hand, adult companies are more reluctant to change, while discouraging deviation from the initial working principles. Young companies can enjoy better share prices because of their willingness to accept changes, realise the business need, and be open to the newly available technology that can keep the cost low and ensure faster process delivery.

5.9.3. Practical implications of the findings to the stakeholders

The research findings about the age at stock market listing have some practical and managerial implications that can make some degree of difference in decision making. Investors, investment banks, lenders, investment consortiums, and stockbrokers can consider these findings before making investment decisions for the business, which can be classified as either an adult or a new company. Old companies generally possess bigger operations, more extensive experience, the finest technical know-how, a diversified risk portfolio, and balanced internal control systems. All of these issues make them attractive to investors, rather than investing in new companies with substantial risk.

However, this common scenario has changed in recent years, when tech giants occupy most of the top positions for offering the highest revenues and profits, being the most attractive employers to young and innovative talents, their brand visibility, and growing reputation (Puhakka & Sipola, 2011). These young companies' unique service products, straightforward processes, real-time service delivery, and robust ethical and sustainable approach make them attractive to investors (Puhakka & Sipola, 2011). They sell their services in such a way that the entire seven billion population of the world is treated as a single market. Thus, relatively new companies get additional share premiums in the price war with old companies. This makes new firm more attractive to investors to balance an investment portfolio.

5.10. Investors' preference for individual performance over the combined performance

5.10.1. Summary of the findings

Sustainability variables enhance the adjusted R^2 significantly. Individual environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance together give a better estimate of the share price than combined ESG sustainability performance. The adjusted R^2 in Model 2 was reported as 0.283, with the accounting variables and combined ESG sustainability performance variables for the full sample. On the other hand, the adjusted R^2 was reported as 0.293 with accounting variables and individual environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance combined.

5.10.2. Discussion and evaluation of the findings

This study has used combined ESG sustainability performance scores and individual environmental, social, and governance performance scores to investigate their influence on the market share price. When the combined ESG sustainability score was introduced as an independent variable in the regression equation with the book value of the share (BV) and earnings per share (EPS) in the basic Ohlson model (1995), the adjusted R^2 jumped 11.33% for the full sample, 3% for FTSE100 companies, 4.08% for FTSE250 companies, 13.84% for Small-cap companies, 0.92% for FTSE4Good companies, and 17.48% for non-FTSE4Good companies. However, when the individual environmental, social, and governance score was introduced as an independent variable in the regression equation replacing the combined ESG score, the adjusted R^2 increased by 17.48% for the full sample, 12.41% for FTSE100 companies, 10.49% for FTSE250 companies, and 11.81% for Small-cap companies. At the same time, it increased 2.45% for FTSE4Good companies and 13.66% for NonFTSE4Good companies compared to the adjusted R^2 in Regression Model 1. Therefore, from the adjusted R^2 , it is clear that the individual environmental, social, and governance sustainability score carries higher value-relevant information for the investors than the combined ESG sustainability score because of their preference for particular sustainability issues.

The literature shows that standalone sustainability activities reporting, such as the CO₂ emission report and social performance report itself, carries less relevant information, as this sustainability report is a small part of the total corporate sustainability practices. From the results of this study, the adjusted R^2 jumps higher for all components of the full sample. For FTSE4Good companies, investors are always up to date on sustainability issues through sustainability indices, which facilitate horizontal, vertical, and cross-country comparisons with other firms (Searcy & Elkhawas, 2012). A firm will be dropped from the sustainability index listing if the firm's sustainability performance goes down or if another firm's sustainability performance outscores compared to the existing firm. Because of a high sustainability standard and updated sustainability communication through indices, FTSE4Good firms experience less fluctuation in their share prices when the actual sustainability score is added to the basic regression model. From the data analysis of this study, the individual environmental, social, and governance scores together carry more value-relevant information than the combined ESG sustainability score.

This study suggests that both social and governance sustainability scores have similar positive impacts on the market share price for the full sample despite strong negative impacts on performance. Therefore, there is no clear preference between social and governance performance for the full sample, which positively influences the share price more than the others. Investors value each dimension of sustainability differently. Budsaratragoon and Jitmaneeroj (2021) stated that applying the ESG sustainability strategy together brings more benefit for the firm, as the environmental, social, and governance dimensions carry a positive synergic impact that the investors value.

For the FTSE4Good companies, only environmental and governance performance positively and significantly influence the market share price. On the other hand, the social dimension of sustainability performance positively influences the stock price for FTSE250 companies, while environmental performance negatively affects the share price for both FTSE100 and FTSE250. Thus, to boost the overall share price, FTSE4Good firms should be weighted more heavily on the environmental dimension, while FTSE100&250 firms should emphasise the social dimension of sustainability.

Budsaratragoon and Jitmaneeroj (2021) suggested that although environmental, social, and governance elements have different weightings, investors put more value on companies with a holistic approach to ESG sustainability. However, only sustainability has minimal explanatory power on the variation of market share price until financial data are put together with sustainability information. Therefore, it could be unwise for any particular dimension of corporate sustainability to ignore the total synergic impact of ESG sustainability.

5.10.3. Practical implications

Stakeholders put a different level of emphasis on each element of ESG sustainability, including environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance, when it comes to their decision making. This study revealed that environmental performance dominates the value creation process among the ESG sustainability elements for FTSE4Good companies. On the other hand, social and governance sustainability performance plays a dominant role in the value creation process among ESG sustainability elements for the FTSE100&250 companies.

Therefore, investors setting up their sustainability information need to be there when they have both the combined and individual sustainability performance scores available. This research study suggests that the individual sustainability performance of all three elements could explain the share price variation on a larger scale than the combined ESG performance score. Thus, individual sustainability performance provides more value-relevant information to the investor than does the combined ESG sustainability performance.

These research findings bear crucial practical importance for management and the board, particularly when they set the policy to communicate their sustainability practices. Many firms publish just a portion of their sustainability report or individual elements of ESG sustainability, which may not satisfy users' information needs. The study revealed that some firms decided to report only part of their sustainability performance because they did not have notable sustainability activities in the unreported part. However, in a broader sense, each element of corporate sustainability should be reported to meet the users' information needs (Budsaratragoon & Jitmaneeoj, 2021). Reporting each component of ESG sustainability can reduce information asymmetry between the inside and outside users of the information (Martínez-Ferrero et al., 2016). It can ensure more value-relevant information for the investors to do a precise stock valuation, reduce perceived ESG risk, and reduce the cost of equity and debt to ensure the free flow of relevant information (Mervelskemper & Streit, 2017). Reporting all three aspects of corporate sustainability is associated with value relevance and enhances the investors' ability to price ESG activities in a positive direction.

5.11. Sustainability firm value ecosystems

Sustainability firm value ecosystems is a proposed value-driven sustainability model developed partly based on the findings of this study and partly from the conclusions of the literature. The ecosystem model starts with initial sustainability planning, investment, reputation building, capitalising reputation, and finally, achieving sustainability recognition. This model is highly involved with firm value; therefore, all action plans are proposed in each stage to ensure maximum firm value.

Stage One: Initial sustainability plan

The first stage of a firm's sustainability journey starts with meeting basic compliance relating to corporate sustainability practices. Regulators force firms to embrace sustainability practices up to this point. For example, UK employers must offer workplace pensions for every employee as part of an employment contract. Beyond the compliance requirement, it is up to the board to decide to what extent the firm will adopt sustainability practices. To start the initial journey, the firm needs to assess its capabilities and resources, as this stage will work as the foundation of further sustainability practices. Gaining industry-specific sustainability knowledge is an important part of the initial planning stage. At the same time, a particular department, such as the strategy department, must take the lead in establishing sustainability. In terms of value, the new approach has very basic impacts on the share price as nothing has changed yet. However, this stage is crucial as a stepping stone, as the future direction of the sustainability journey would be determined here.

Figure 15: Firm's Sustainability Journey.

Stage Two: Investment in sustainability

Stage Two involves actual sustainability initiatives beyond compulsory requirements. Once a firm understands sustainability practices and sets up a sustainability leadership role within the organisation, then it is time to ensure sustainability practices within the organisation. This step is highly associated with the firm value; therefore, spending resources on non-value-driven issues may diminish the firm value. The findings of this study confirm that environmental performance is value-driven for the FTSE4Good companies, and social and governance performance enhances share prices for FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies. This study advocates starting the sustainability journey by focusing on social performance, as social sustainability generates rewards more quickly than environmental performance. At the same time, the board needs to consider the time lag (Budsaratragoon & Jitmaneeoj, 2021) between sustainability investment and financial reward. Therefore, there could be initial negative effects on firm value because of initial negative sustainability effects, but the firm needs to focus on incremental performance continuously.

Stage Three: Building a sustainability reputation

Stage Three involves building a sustainability reputation by focusing on continuous investment, performance improvement, and regular reporting of sustainability initiatives. Better sustainability performance can reduce systematic risk and increase productivity. Once the business model is integrated with sustainability practices, the firm needs to communicate regularly with its wider stakeholders, including customers, shareholders, investors, lenders, regulators, and pressure groups. All of these stakeholders are part of corporate value systems; therefore, communication is key to building a sustainability reputation.

Stage Four: Capitalisation on sustainability reputation

Stage Four involves capitalising on the sustainability reputation developed in Stage Three. This stage represents a complex sustainability performance and firm value ecosystems, which have interactions among manifold value-enhancing activities. Value-driven corporate sustainability

can generate many benefits to enhance a firm's value. Sustainability practice can be used as a product differentiation strategy (Navarro, 1988; Bagnoli & Watts, 2003; Siegel & Vitaliano, 2007), increase customer loyalty (Luo & Bhattacharya, 2009) that leads to more debt control over product pricing, higher sales and higher prices (Elfenbein et al., 2012; Ailawadi et al., 2014; Hilger et al., 2018), reduce the firm's systematic risk (El Ghoul et al., 2011; Albuquerque et al., 2018), reduce the cost of capital (El Ghoul et al., 2011; Ahmed et al., 2019), and cost of debt (Ye and Zhang, 2011). In addition, sustainability practices reduce employee turnover by 25% to 30% (Vitaliano, 2010) and improve employee performance (Malik, 2014). In relation to the stock market benefits, this study found that environmental sustainability performance enhances share price for large firms and FTSE4Good companies.

In contrast, social sustainability performance improves the share price for FTSE100 and FTSE250 firms. Sustainability activities can be used as risk management tools. At the same time, they can protect share prices during a crisis (Schnietz & Epstein, 2005) and ensure higher stock returns during a financial crisis (Lins et al., 2017). Therefore, sustainability plays an essential role in a firm's value systems, while investors pay more attention to sustainability performance when financial performance is weak (Ng & Rezaee, 2015). As a result, corporate sustainability performance can be used as a stakeholder management and control mechanism capable of managing internal and external stakeholders. Therefore, this study suggests that a firm should improve value-driven sustainability performance and practice to enhance the firm's long-term value, ignoring the initial negative impacts of sustainability implementation.

Stage Five: Continuous Improvement and seeking the highest recognition for sustainability

Stage Five of the corporate sustainability journey involves working to ensure continuous improvement of environmental, social and governance sustainability practices. Total sustainability practice has a synergic impact on value systems; therefore, the firm should now focus on every aspect of sustainability performance. This study found that membership in prestigious sustainability indices enhances the share price compared to that of a nonmember. A higher sustainability rating also provides access to broader finance options. Therefore, in this stage, the firm should seek the highest recognition, frequently communicate with stakeholders

through sustainability reporting, carefully assess the feedback report from sustainability rating agencies, and find out the way to improve sustainability and control measures.

5.12. Summary

This chapter summarised, discussed, and evaluated the research results presented in Chapter Four. This chapter also discussed the practical implication of each research finding. Some of the research findings were consistent with previous research findings. At the same time, some findings do not agree with previous research results. However, the most notable findings of this research are opposing stock market reactions for FTSE4Good companies, FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies, and Small-cap companies. The research findings revealed that for each element of corporate ESG sustainability, no similar stock price reactions were found for the two separate sample groups. Environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance are unlikely to have similar impacts on the share price for all the sample companies.

The findings revealed that combined ESG sustainability positively affects the full share price sample. These findings can be used to optimise share prices through outstanding sustainability performance. At the same time, the share price for FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies is negatively associated with environmental sustainability performance, supporting the cost-centred view of sustainability spending. Previous research has revealed mixed stock market effects of sustainability practices. However, in recent days, the relative importance of sustainability practices has increased significantly, and sustainability guidelines have been developed and implemented.

Stakeholders treat sustainability practices differently than before, as the overall outlook of sustainability changes in a positive direction (Du et al., 2017). Therefore, many earlier researchers found a negative association between sustainability performance and share price, but recent studies discovered more positive associations (Ahmed et al., 2019; Ameer & Othman, 2012; Barnett & Salomon, 2011). At the same time, it is essential to consider how long the firm has adopted sustainability practices within the business. Sustainability investment requires a few years to generate rewards through sustainability reputation, corporate branding, premium product price, customer loyalty, and strong bargaining power with suppliers and

lenders (Ye & Zhang, 2011). Therefore, the negative association between sustainability performance and share price may likely change in the future.

Environmental performance dominates overall corporate sustainability behaviour and thereafter determines the direction of association with share price for the firm. For FTSE4Good companies, the market share price is positively associated with combined ESG sustainability performance and environmental performance, while no significant association is found for social and governance performance. On the other hand, environmental performance was negatively associated with share price for FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies, while a positive association was found for social and governance performance.

Along with the environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance, the firm's size, high environmental impact industrial background, sustainability reputation, and age of stock market listing play an important role in moderating the relationship between sustainability performance and share price. This result reveals that firm size strongly determines corporate sustainability practices and reputation (Kuzey & Uyar, 2017). Large firms can make consistent sustainability investments and thus can benefit from outstanding sustainability performance in the stock market. At the same time, a sustainability reputation can be developed through continuous development in sustainability practices and long-term plans.

An environmentally sensitive industrial background is a massive challenge in terms of achieving a sustainability reputation and outstanding performance. Operation in high-impact industries can make share prices significantly cheaper. This negative share price effect is severe for non-reputed firms. However, corporate age revealed an unexpected result of a negative association between a firm's age of stock market listing and share price. A young firm listed in the stock market has a positive association with share price, which means that newer firms are more attractive to investors than adult firms. At the same time, the analysis showed that individual sustainability performance reporting provides more value-relevant information for the investors than combined ESG performance reporting because of the investors' varying information needs and preferences.

This chapter summarised the research findings while providing guidance on how they can be used in practice to ensure maximum firm value. Along with the ESG sustainability variable, this research also included several additional independent variables such as firm size, environmentally high-impact industrial background, sustainability reputation, and age of stock market listing to achieve the research aim. The dynamism of corporate business increases every day because of our increasing needs, while Earth's vulnerability has been exposed simultaneously. Therefore, it is time to optimise our needs and vulnerability. This research was part of an effort to find the optimum solution for our incremental needs and vulnerability. The findings showed that fostering sustainability can address our vulnerability while still serving the investors' purpose.

Chapter Six: Conclusion

6.1. Introduction

This chapter provides a summary of this research study. This study set five research objectives in Chapter One. Section 6.2 demonstrates how each objective has been achieved. Additionally, this chapter presents the main contributions of this study, both to theory and to practice. Based on the research findings, some recommendations are made. At the end of the chapter, the limitations and some suggestions for further research are outlined.

6.2. Achieving the research objectives

This study set up five distinctive objectives to achieve the research aim. Various methodological approaches were adopted to achieve these objectives. This section discusses how each of the five research objectives has been achieved.

6.2.1. Objective One

The first objective of this study was *'To critically review the concept of corporate sustainability performance, value relevance, existing theory, models, and current corporate sustainability practice.'* This objective was designed to understand the main topics of this research extensively. Corporate sustainability is a relatively new topic in research. As part of sustainability, CSR has been discussed much more widely than sustainability. Corporate sustainability comprises economic, environmental, social, and governance sustainability. The term 'sustainability' has been used in various forms in the corporate literature, and this research reviewed many papers and articles related to corporate sustainability, the theory and model of sustainability, sustainability measurement, reporting frameworks, standards and guidelines, and sustainability indices worldwide.

The potential impacts of sustainability performance have been reviewed through reviewing theory, models, and research papers. To predict precisely the market value of the share, this study identified potential sustainability and moderating variables that were subsequently used within the regression model. Based on the review, this study has developed a conceptual framework that sufficiently accommodates relevant theories, accounting, sustainability, and moderating variables.

To assess the value relevance of sustainability performance, this study reviewed all possible methods of value-relevance studies and valuation models. Assessing the requirements, this study selected Ohlson's (1995) basic valuation model, while 14 sustainability and moderating variables were accommodated within the model. Following de Klerk and de Villiers (2012), potential scaling problems were addressed. This study formulated eight hypotheses to test the impacts of various aspects of sustainability performance. Some of these hypotheses validate the existing results from the UK perspective, while a few are entirely new to explore. The whole procedure, setting up the research aim and objectives, identifying relevant theories, selecting the model, data collection, data scaling, and development of regression models, makes it evident that the existing literature has been sufficiently reviewed and this study has been duly designed to achieve its objectives.

6.2.2. Objective Two

The second objective of this study was '*To assess the value relevance of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) sustainability performance individually and combinedly based on the sustainability performance.*' This objective was designed to assess the value relevance of corporate sustainability performance. This study has used a combined ESG performance and individual environmental, social, and governance scores to determine the effects of sustainability performance. The combined and individual sustainability enable this study to assess the relative importance of value systems. On the other hand, this study split the full sample into several separate sample groups to assess whether individual or combined sustainability performance created similar impacts on all the sample groups. Therefore, this study tested the hypotheses for each element of sustainability in each sample group.

The regression results revealed that ESG sustainability is positively associated with the full sample, FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, together with FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies. The environmental performance is negatively associated with the share price for all the sample groups except FTSE4Good companies, where environmental performance is reported to be positively associated with the share price. At the same time, social performance was positively associated with the share price for FTSE250 companies and NonFTSE4Good companies, while no relationship was found for FTSE100 and Small-cap companies and FTSE4Good companies. On the other hand, governance performance is positively and significantly associated with the share price for the full sample, FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies, but negatively associated with FTSE250 companies, while it is neither negatively nor positively associated with FTSE100 and Small-cap companies. Thus, sustainability performance does not create the same stock market impacts for all the companies, but makes similar stock market impacts for homogeneous companies.

Therefore, all these regression results and hypotheses show the value relevance of sustainability performance, which has been assessed successfully to fulfil Objective Two. The findings also provide valuable instructions related to corporate sustainability and long-term firm value.

6.2.3. Objective Three

The third objective of this study was *‘To assess the moderating role of firm size, industrial background, sustainability reputation and age of listing on the existing relationship between corporate sustainability and share price.’* This objective was designed to assess the moderating role of firm size, sustainability reputation, industrial background, and age of stock market listing. This objective further investigated the role of sustainability performance on the share price. Firm size affects both the share price and sustainability performance. Large firms hold larger resources that allow them to invest in sustainability projects and consistently generate a sustainability reputation.

Firm size and sustainability reputation are both positively and significantly associated with the share price. An environmentally sensitive industrial background is negatively associated with the share price. However, the negative stock price impacts are higher for non-reputed firms

compared to reputed firms. Young firms listed on the stock market are positively associated with the share price compared to the other listed firms. Overall, this study successfully achieved the third research objective. The findings partially answer the research questions and fill a gap in the literature. Additionally, the findings offer valuable guidance to corporate managers and boards on sustainability investment.

6.2.4. Objective Four

The fourth objective of this study was *‘To find out the managerial implications of environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance on firms’ value.’* This objective was designed to identify the managerial implications of the research findings. Sustainable business practice is a long-term corporate goal that cannot be achieved in the short term. Based on the research findings relating to the ESG, environmental, social and governance sustainability performance for the full sample, FTSE100 companies, FTSE250 companies, Small-cap companies, FTSE4Good companies, and NonFTSE4Good companies, this study has recommended the practical use of each research finding.

Therefore, investment in sustainable projects will cost additional funds that will be treated as a cost in the short term, but an investment for the longer term. To minimise negative stock market effects, firms should only commit to sustainable investment if they can maintain it in the long term. Long-term continuous improvement in sustainability performance creates a sustainability reputation, earning a stock market premium on share trade. At the same time, each element of sustainability impacts share prices differently; thus, this study advised independent managerial implications for each sample group based on the impacts of sustainability elements. This study strongly advises against using generalised sustainability for all firms, as it affects different firms differently. To maximise the share price, firms should use stock market-driven sustainability performance. Environmental performance drives share prices for FTSE4Good companies, while social and governance performance is more relevant for FTSE100 and FTSE250 firms. Thus, this study has successfully achieved the fourth research objective, as it recommended many managerial uses of the research findings.

6.2.5. Objective Five

The fifth objective of this study was *'To make recommendations on how corporate sustainability performance can be used in practice to maximise firms' value.'* This objective was designed to make policy recommendations to maximise the firm value. The findings of this research have manifold uses for various stakeholders. Sustainability is an extensive area that affects every inhabitant on Earth. Although this study mainly focused on investors' needs and firm values, the findings have several other practical uses.

Regulators and governments can use sustainability performance information for policy formulation to meet net-zero carbon targets, banks, lenders, and other credit rating agencies to assess environmental, regulatory, and operational risks to determine appropriate risk premiums. Corporate firms can use sustainability performance to signal future prospects and to create a long-term sustainability reputation. A sustainable investment manager can quickly identify the firm in which they need to invest. Therefore, corporate sustainability can integrate the whole sustainability ecosystem and ensure a sustainable future. Chapter Five has already explicitly described all these practical uses of the research findings, making it evident that this research has made sufficient policy recommendations to ensure maximum firm value and a sustainable future.

6.3. Contributions of this study

The contributions of this study have been categorised into theory and professional practice, and are discussed in Sections 6.3.1 and 6.3.2.

6.3.1. Theoretical contributions

This study has achieved its aim and objectives by assessing the value relevance of environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance of UK-listed companies categorised as FTSE100 companies, FTSE250 companies and Small-cap companies, as well as FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good companies. The most notable achievement has been

identifying the varying levels of value relevance for each corporate sustainability performance element for all sample groups. Some of the findings of this study have not been discussed before in the sustainability literature. The whole procedure of reviewing the literature, identifying gaps in it, formulating hypotheses, developing models, analysing the data, and finding the practical implications of the research results offer new insight into corporate sustainability performance and practice and open up the potential to extend this study for further research, as will be discussed in Section 6.6.

This study contributes to the literature in several ways. First, this study investigated the value relevance of corporate sustainability performance using a sustainability performance score evaluated by an independent third party. Previous studies addressed issues of value relevance of CSR and sustainability reporting or are part of sustainability reporting, such as greenhouse gas release reports, but ignored the actual sustainability performance in the UK setting. This study assessed the value relevance of the sustainability performance of FTSE100 companies, FTSE250 companies, Small-cap companies, FTSE4Good companies, and NonFTSE4Good companies, and found a non-similar association for each sample category. This finding can explain why the literature suggests a mixed association for the mixed sample. Small-cap companies have never been investigated in a value-relevance setting. Therefore, this study enriches the limited body of existing literature, offering insight into the value relevance of sustainability for UK-listed companies.

Second, this study investigated the stock market impacts of environmental, social and governance performance separately and combinedly (environmental, social, and governance performance as one value) and found different levels of association for different elements of sustainability. Only a few previous studies have attempted to differentiate sustainability performance and identify the relative importance of each element in the value creation process. Again, this study found a non-similar association between each element of corporate sustainability for each sample group. These findings rank investors' sustainability information needs according to priority while advocating the role of each sustainability performance in the firm value systems. Therefore, this study is a valuable addition to the knowledge on the value relevance of environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance for FTSE100 companies, FTSE250 companies and Small-cap companies, as well as FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies in the UK.

Third, this study investigated the role of corporate sustainability performance from several theoretical reference points. Although emphasis has been given to the decision usefulness of the investors, agency theory, signalling theory, and theory of accountability were equally important in designing the research. As multiple theoretical approaches were applied, this study used several moderating variables that influence the relationship between share price and sustainability performance. Using firm size, sustainability reputation, environmentally sensitive industrial background, and age of stock market listing revealed some unique findings that are a valuable addition to the existing literature on corporate sustainability and firm value.

This study made a final contribution by proposing a theoretical model of corporate sustainability and firm value ecosystems. This model has been proposed based on an extensive literature review and the findings of this study. The proposed model consists of five stages that offer guidance for the firm on each sustainability stage to ensure maximum share price throughout the sustainability journey. The details of the proposed model are discussed in Section 5.11. The sustainability and firm value ecosystems model is a comprehensive guideline that would assist the firm from the beginning of its sustainability journey to reach the top of the sustainability ladder, while at the same time recommending the best measures to maximise the share price based on the observations in the literature. This proposed model could be a practical reference point for a firm's sustainability journey. Therefore, the proposed ecosystems model is a valuable addition to the knowledge in the literature on corporate sustainability and firm continuum.

6.3.2. Contribution to the professional practice

This research was designed, data collected and analysed to assess the role of corporate sustainability performance on the share price. The findings of this study provide practical guidance for corporate managers and industrial practice. The main contributions of this study are as follows:

ESG, environmental, social, and governance sustainability are value-relevant to the investors

Based on the results of the hypotheses, ESG, environmental, and social sustainability performance provide value-relevant information to the investors and shareholders for FTSE100 companies, FTSE250 companies, Small-cap companies, FTSE4Good companies, and NonFTSE4Good companies. In contrast, governance performance was the only value relevant for the full sample. These results, particularly sustainability performance, provide new information to the market participants who use them in their decision making. Therefore, corporate sustainability performance provides decision-useful information to investors and shareholders. Thus, management should continuously provide timely sustainability information to reduce the information gap and minimise information asymmetry.

At the same time, this study also found that higher ESG and environmental performance can generate premium prices for the shares of FTSE4Good companies. On the other hand, social performance generates an additional share premium for FTSE250 firms, but environmental performance is negatively associated with the share price for FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies. Thus, sustainability performance can be used as a tool to control share prices in the market.

This study also found that investors and shareholders prefer environmental, social, and governance performance separately rather than having one combined ESG performance rating. Therefore, the firm should publish sustainability performance reports that demonstrate each performance separately while making comparisons between each element. Sustainability performance reports can be used as a bridge between management and other stakeholders to minimise the agency's duty to supply useful information and reduce information asymmetry. At the same time, investors and other stakeholders will get timely information to make the right decisions.

Therefore, these findings are valuable to the knowledge of corporate sustainability performance and practice, which advocates for more corporate involvement in sustainability activities to make the world safer for everyone.

Corporate sustainability performance can enhance and diminish firm value

Research results revealed that the performance of ESG, environmental, and social sustainability follow the different firm value routes for FTSE100 companies, FTSE250 companies, and Small-cap companies as well as FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies. ESG, social, and governance sustainability performance are positively and significantly associated with the share price for the full sample, while environmental sustainability is negatively and significantly associated with the share price. On the other hand, environmental performance is negatively associated with FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies and positively associated with FTSE4Good Index companies, but no association was found with Small-cap companies and NonFTSE4Good companies.

Social performance was positively associated with the share price for FTSE250 companies and NonFTSE4Good companies, while no significant association was found for FTSE100 companies and FTSE4Good companies. On the other hand, governance performance was positively and significantly associated for the full sample, FTSE250 companies, FTSE4Good, and NonFTSE4Good companies, while no significant association was found for FTSE100 and Small-cap companies. Therefore, sustainability performance does not follow the general trend, but creates value in a certain way for similar companies. FTSE4Good companies are large, possess a higher sustainability reputation, and hold a considerable amount of floating cash, while the opposite characteristics are found for the FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies. Previous research has not focused on the moderating characteristics of a firm, which makes a difference in creating firm value using sustainability performance.

This finding also justifies previous mixed associations, as they used a mixed sample. Therefore, the corporate sustainability budget for FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies should not follow the same rules to maximise the firm value. FTSE4Good companies should focus more on environmental issues while maintaining good social and governance performance, so the overall ESG rating does not fall. Similarly, FTSE100 and FTSE250 companies should emphasise social performance while maintaining a stable state of environmental and governance issues. Finally, it is the FTSE4Good companies that avail themselves of the best benefit from sustainability practices.

Therefore, these findings are a valuable addition to the knowledge of a corporate sustainability performance and practice that environmental, social, and governance sustainability may not generate additional value for every firm all the time. Management needs to decide which elements of sustainability the firm should emphasise based on individual circumstances. If firms choose inappropriate elements as sustainability investments, they may lose value. None of the previous studies has focused on each element of ESG sustainability and firm characteristics simultaneously. Thus, this is a significant undiscovered knowledge added to the corporate sustainability literature, which can help maximise firm value.

Corporate sustainability and value ecosystems

This research proposed a sustainability and value ecosystem, a simple but very effective flowchart representation of corporate sustainability. This sustainability value ecosystems model was proposed based on the observations of previous studies and the findings of this study. The corporate sustainability ecosystem is a five-step sustainability action plan which mainly describes what action to take at each stage of the sustainability investment. As this study focuses on firms' value and share prices, each of the five steps describes the best activities to maximise the firm value. In the beginning, when the firm makes sustainability investments or spending, it usually does not get any rewards; however, if the firm continues investing in sustainability projects for a certain length of time, it starts getting its benefit. The firm needs to brand its sustainability performance and create a long-term sustainability reputation at this stage.

Once firms are considerably stable in terms of sustainability performance and reputation, they can benefit from their dominant sustainability position. However, not every firm will build this reputation using sustainability, as it requires significant investment. Comparing the investment requirements, small firms should focus on the social aspects of sustainability, while large firms can emphasise environmental issues.

Sustainability ecosystems is a unique idea, putting the whole corporate sustainability and value concept in one illustration. This is a significant contribution of this study, which offers many practical suggestions for corporate managers heading towards value-enhancing sustainability investments.

Stakeholders expect a more sustainable approach from a larger firm

The findings of this study revealed that firm size is positively associated with share price, while larger firms undergo greater stakeholder pressure and media scrutiny. Any negative news and rumours about the large companies spread quickly and negatively affect their reputation. At the same time, larger firms suffer greater share price losses than smaller firms, while having a similar level of sustainability performance. These results indicate that investors are not willing to pay much for the shares. In other words, they penalise the larger firm by offering a lower price for their sustainability practice and performance. This finding describes the relative importance of sustainability practices and performance for bigger corporations. Therefore, this finding is a valuable contribution to the corporate sustainability literature to shield against decreasing the share price for the larger firm.

6.4. Recommendations

Based on the findings and literature review, this study put forward some practical recommendations for corporate managers, investors, shareholders, governments, regulators, lenders, bank and credit rating agencies. The recommendations are as follows:

Recommendations for corporate managers

This study mainly focused on corporate sustainability behaviour and its effects on share prices, thereby offering several recommendations for corporate managers. First, investment in sustainability is similar to investment in intangible assets, and in the long term, it generates a valuable return. Thus, the firm still not investing in sustainability should consider sustainability

seriously and update its business strategy. Otherwise, sooner or later, they will find that their strategy is out of date.

Second, the firm that has already started investing in sustainability should continue investing in the projects wisely as a long-term journey rather than a short-term goal. The management of these firms should keep in mind that not all sustainability activities are value-driven; therefore, they should emphasise value-driven sustainability investments (Dijken, 2007). The best benefits of sustainability investments come once a firm possesses a sustainability reputation. These firms should continuously focus on sustainability, ensure sound communication of sustainability activities with stakeholders, improve brand sustainability performance, develop bargaining power, and aim to be included in the sustainability index.

Third, the firm already included in the sustainability index should continuously focus on improving sustainability performance to stay in the index for a long time and become the industry leader in sustainability. Management should rebrand the firm's image based on its superior sustainability performance and put up entry barriers to the competitors. Firms should strongly negotiate any financing deal, as their environmental and operational risk profile is significantly lower compared to other firms.

Recommendations for investors and shareholders

Sustainable development aims for financial, social, and environmental safety for all the inhabitants of earth, and only sustainability investment can ensure that. Investors and shareholders can play a vital role in establishing and promoting sustainability. Considering the long-term impacts of sustainable corporate practice, shareholders should advocate for sustainability projects on the board, as it better protects their investment. At the same time, a firm with a sustainability reputation gets a better stock market return; thus, investing in a sustainable firm may provide a higher return than other firms.

Recommendations for governments and regulators

Governments and regulators can play a significant role in establishing and promoting sustainability in business. Recently, the UK government has shown some genuine initiatives to be carbon neutral by 2050. The government set a target to cut carbon emissions by 68% by 2030, 78% by 2035, and 100% by 2050 (GOV.UK, 2021). Now is the time to turn this policy into an action plan. Governments should check all industries, taking environmentally sensitive industries first. Some firms may be required to reshape their business model. At the same time, the government should give a flat-rate goal to every firm to meet the net-zero carbon target, while giving an additional target to large firms as they cause the greatest damage, since they also possess more floating cash and access to broader finance.

Regulators can play a vital role in helping the government to implement a net-zero carbon target. The regulator should make sustainability performance reporting mandatory to ensure that all investors and shareholders hold the same information as other insiders. The stock exchange should publish sustainability-related performance scores for each element of ESG sustainability for every listed company. Some firms are always reactive; they take action only when the law forces them to do so. Mandatory requirements for publishing sustainability performance reports may force them to take some sustainable action to report to the shareholders. At the same time, regulators should set sustainability reporting standards, policies, and guidelines that reflect the country's overall health and the government's sustainability target.

Recommendations for lenders, banks, and credit rating agencies

Lenders, banks, and credit rating agencies can significantly contribute to sustainability practices. Lenders and banks are the primary sources of corporate funds. The research findings revealed that better sustainability performance is the opposite of a firm's higher environmental, social, governance, and operational risk. Therefore, credit rating agencies, banks, and lenders should produce a sustainability performance-adjusted corporate risk profile for the firm, which reasonably reflects the firm's sustainability practices. This action will help every stakeholder in the sustainability ecosystem.

6.5. Limitation of this research

Every research study has research limitations, as no studies are limitation free (Simon, 2013). This study is solely quantitative and therefore bound to the limitations of quantitative research methods. However, considering the research questions and objectives, this study chose the best alternatives among the methodological choices. This study faces two notable methodological challenges: sample size and sustainability performance score.

This study used a sample categorised into FTSE100, FTSE250, and Small-cap companies, which were further categorised as FTSE4Good and NonFTSE4Good companies. This study used sample data of 1210 firms. Considering the number of independent variables, all regressions satisfied the minimum participant number threshold, but a larger sample size could have explored the relationship between dependent and independent variables in a more extensive way.

The second methodological limitation of this study relates to the sustainability performance score. This study collected the sustainability performance score from the Thompson Reuters Refinitiv database. Refinitiv measures sustainability performance based on its own sustainability performance indicators. In some cases, sustainability information was not available because of the lack of sustainability information from the company side. On the other hand, this study also used the FTSE4Good Index, which again includes the firm's own sustainability criteria. Fowler and Hope (2007) claim that sustainability indexes such as FTSE4Good favour large companies. However, FTSE4Good has in place very robust selection criteria, and they review the list twice a year, excluding any firm that fails to maintain the sustainability criteria.

6.6. Suggestions for further studies

The main focus of this study was to analyse the role of sustainability performance in firms' value. The study encountered some unexplained situations throughout the analysis. Therefore, further studies on these unexplained questions could provide a reasonable explanation. Thus, this study suggests that further research needs to be conducted in the following areas:

Further studies on governance sustainability performance

The Office for National Statistics (2018) reported that institutional investors in the UK control 81% of the share capital of listed companies. This study found that corporate governance performance is positively associated with the share price but negatively associated with FTSE250 companies. There are two potential explanations for this situation. First, institutional ownership demotivates management to be more transparent, and they only favour those governance activities that enhance the firm value or are imposed by the regulators for mandatory implementation (Haryono et al., 2016). Second, a strong regulatory regime is already in place. Further studies can be conducted to determine what other reasons could encourage investors not to pay for increased sustainability performance.

Further studies on the age of stock market listing and sustainability

This study first linked firm age with sustainability and found that the age of stock market listing is negatively associated with the share price. Therefore, this study suggests further qualitative research towards the attitude of senior board members of young and old companies concerning corporate sustainability.

Further studies on the point of the trade-off between the costs and benefits of corporate sustainability

The literature suggests that a firm's initial sustainability investment negatively impacts profitability and available resources. This study has found that sustainability performance is positively associated with the share price. At the same time, most of the initial investigations on CSR or sustainability reported either a negative association or no association, while recent studies incrementally show a positive association because of the initial negative cooling-off period.

Further studies should focus on finding the trade-off period when sustainability benefits marginally exceed sustainability costs. The focus should be given to identify the optimum time length when the cumulative benefits surpass the cumulative sustainability expenses. Further studies should also focus on whether investors and shareholders have any confidence and trust issues regarding the board's ability to pull out shareholders' financial benefits from implementing sustainability policy.

Sustainability firm value ecosystems

This study proposed a new concept called Sustainability Firm Value Ecosystems, which consists of five distinct stages. Corporate sustainability practice is a continuous process that requires ongoing guidance. Many studies have been conducted on sustainability, but they have not done so in systematic order. To date, corporate sustainability has no starting or endpoint, but the proposed model advocates a systematic procedure for a firm's sustainability journey based on the value-enhancing role of corporate sustainability performance. This study suggests further systematic research in each of the five stages of the ecosystem to fully develop the model.

6.7. Summary

The aim of this study was to analyse the role of sustainability performance in market value of share. Using Ohlson's (1995) valuation model, this study conducted a regression analysis to determine the association between a firm's share price and sustainability performance. To more precisely determine the relationship, the firm size, sustainability reputation, industrial background, and age of stock market listing have been added in the regression model as moderating variables. This study found several undiscovered features of the relationship between share prices and sustainability performance. The relationship between the share price and ESG, environmental, social, and governance sustainability performance has been determined for FTSE100 companies, FTSE250 companies, Small-cap companies, FTSE4Good companies and NonFTSE4Good companies. In the end, this study proposes a new idea for corporate sustainability and value ecosystems, which explains the whole process of value systems of sustainability and practical guidance at each stage. This study can be further extended by the suggested research in Section 6.6.4.

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